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Brief description

Interest in uptake of research products has immensely grown hence, the need to clearly express the researchers' envisioned utilization of derived data, findings, results, technologies and innovations. Therefore, the research by FoodLAND not only offers new knowledge, technologies and innovations but also offers pathways to their utilization and exploitation at the local country and specific regional levels. The results are presented in formats, such as nutritional recommendations (NRs), in which packaging of the FoodLAND results and deliverables envisions their sustainability in form of exploitable results. This report is a presentation of both the situational architecture, that landscapes the nutritional issues in FoodLAND project implementation sites and nutritional recommendations derived from FoodLAND's work; in readiness for their uptake and exploitation of the latter by the country governments both at national and regional/county levels. The main objective of the task was to generate nutritional recommendations; inclusive of backdrops that provide enhanced understanding of the context of the nutritional issues and possible pathways to the exploitation of the NRs.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AICS	Italian Agency for Cooperation and Development
ANC	Antenatal Clinic
API	Industry Promotion Agency
ASF	Animal Source Foods
BF	Breastfeeding
BoF	Bottle feeding
BMI	Body Mass Index
CBOs	Community based organisations
CECM	County Executive Committee Member
CHP	Community Health Promoter
CHV	Community Health Volunteer
CNAP	County Nutrition Action Plan
CNC	County Nutrition Coordinator
CoP	Communities of Participation
DD	Diet Diversity
DG	Dialogue Group
Dhs	Dirhams
DHS	Demographic Health Survey
DPH	Department of Public Health
DQQ	Diet Quality Questionnaire
EAR	Estimated Average Requirement
EBF	Exclusive Breastfeeding
EBF2D	Exclusively breastfed for the first two days after birth
EIBF	Early initiation of breastfeeding
ENPSF	National Population and Family Health Survey
EvBF	Ever Breastfeeding
ECD	Early Childhood Development
ENAM	Ecole National d'Agriculture de Meknès
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organization
FDS	Food Diversity Score
FGDS	Food Group Diversity Score
FPD	Farm Production Diversity
GDP	Gross domestic product
GoU	Government of Uganda
gr	Gramm
HB	Haemoglobin
HCP	High Commission for Planning
HDDS	Household Dietary Diversity Score
IFA	Iron and Folic Acid
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
IYCF	Infant and Young Child Feeding
INAT	National Institute of Agronomy
INNTA	National Institute of Nutrition and Food Technology
INRAT	National Institute for Research in Agriculture of Tunisia
INS	National Institute of Statistics
ISACM	National Institute of Agriculture of Shott Meriem
ITES	Tunisia Institute for Economic Studies
IYCF	Infant and Young Child Feeding

KEPC	Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company
KNAP	Kenya Nutrition Action Plan
KNBS	Kenya National Bureau of Statistics
MAI	Mediterranean Adequacy Index
MDD-W	Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women
MIYCAN	Maternal, Infant, Young child and Adolescents Nutrition
MOH	Ministry of Health
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
NCD-P	Non-communicable diseases- protect
NCD-R	Non-communicable Diseases -Risk
NGO-CEFA	European Training and Agricultural Committee
NRs	Nutritional Recommendations
OPM	Office of the Prime Minister
PEM	Protein-Energy Malnutrition
PMA	Performance Monitoring and Accountability
RCH	Reproductive Child Health
RDA	Recommended Daily Allowance
RGPH	General Population and Housing Census
SCCHF	Sub-County Community Health Focal Person
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SSBs	Sugar Sweetened Beverage
TDHS-MIS	Tanzania Demographic Health Survey-Malaria Indicator Survey
TNNS	Tanzania National Nutrition Survey
UNAP	Uganda Nutrition Action Plan
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
UoM	University of Mekelle
UoN	University of Nairobi
WB	World Bank
WFP	World Food Program
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package
WRA	Women of Reproductive Age

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1 CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

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1.1. General Background

FoodLAND project is being implemented under seven work packages (WP); WP1 to WP7 and WP2 is the focus of this report. The objectives of WP2 are to provide background knowledge of consumers' food preferences and behaviours and their socioeconomic drivers; to measure the level of dietary diversity and identify its major determinants for women and children; to detect the characteristics of the raw materials, ingredients, and food products that shape the diets.

Nutritional recommendations (NRs) which is an output under Task 2.4 and encased in WP2 is expected to deliver a report on NRs as the project Deliverable 2.6 to be submitted at the 36th project month. The general objective of the task of preparing the report on NRs was to generate and present nutritional recommendations inclusive of backdrops that provide enhanced understanding of the nutritional context and possible pathways to the exploitation of the NRs in the six FoodLAND project Pan-African countries.

The push for uptake of research products has immensely grown hence the need to clearly express the researches' envisioned form of utilisation of derived data, findings, results, technologies and innovations. As such, the research by FoodLAND has not only generated new knowledge, technological innovations and recommendations, such as the NRs, but it also offers pathways to their utilisation and exploitation at the local country and specific regional levels. Thus, the packaging of the results and deliverables envisions uptake, exploitation and sustainability of the derived results.

NRs, therefore, propel the research derived results towards uptake eventually leading to sustainable impact and longevity. The purpose of this report is to present NRs that emerge from the desk review and the original research that FoodLAND has conducted. It integrates suggestions from onsite significant nutritional stakeholders; in readiness for their uptake and exploitation by the governments both at national and regional/county levels. A situational architecture, that landscapes the nutritional issues in FoodLAND project implementation sites is included to suffice as a springboard from which uptake and exploitation of NRs is contextualised.

1.2 Objectives of Deliverable 2.6

The overall objective of the Task 2.4 was to generate nutritional recommendations that are relevant, suitable and feasible to implement within the six Pan-African countries that are partners in the FoodLAND project. To enable the generation of the NRs and thus the achievement of the overall objective, the UoN generated a protocol under the following four specific objectives: 1) to establish the situational architecture that describes the context in which the uptake and exploitation of the NRs would occur and from which nutritional recommendation would emerge 2) to generate a step-by-step detailed protocol for actualizing the development of the NRs while allowing close level of uniformity among the countries yet flexible enough to offer country level customization, 3) to generate NRs, 4) to validate the NRs and capture additional ones in partnership with significant nutritional stakeholders residing in the environs of the FoodLAND associated Food hubs and 5) to develop in advance a template in form a table of content to enhance uniformity in reporting the NRs across the countries. Recommendations should be structured such that a verb articulates the action to be taken. FoodLAND protocol adopted this approach.

1.3 General Protocol

For countries to customise, the UoN developed and presented a generic protocol for creating NRs that incorporated a timeplan in form of a Gantt chart. The chart provided a step-by-step detailed plan of implementation that also sufficed as a monitoring tool to the five countries to support timely completion of the task. The timeplan for the task spread over a period of four months; from the beginning of May to the end of August, 2023. The time use was sub-divided into eight blocks of two weeks. Each block with its allocated activity/achievement albeit some limited country specific elasticity. Intra and inter country meetings enabled consensus and concurrence on how to proceed with the task. Each country having identified nutritional gaps that need intervention packaged them in the form of the situational architecture. The NRs emerged from three key data sources; data extracted from the desk review (D2.5), FoodLAND studies on rural urban consumers (D2.3 and D2.4) and input from significant nutrition stakeholders. Thus, each country, through significant nutritional stakeholders engagement conferences, workshops or meetings validated the NRS formulated by FoodLAND and obtained additional NRs. These significant nutritional stakeholders included representatives of institutions, personnel of government sectors, households, beneficiaries of existing nutritional interventions, community members, Food hubs (producers) and FoodLAND teams. Envisioning utilisation of the NRs embraced four dimensions, namely, issue at hand; who is affected; action to be taken; and who should take action. The process was cognizant that creating NRs was not a table-rasa frame thus considered adding value through enhanced precision and optimization of the already on-going interventions, e.g., EBF.

The presentation of the NRs in the report is closely aligned to the table of content that was generated as part of the NRs protocol thus harmony has been achieved across country report sections. The report is organised as Chapters in which each country's NRs are contained and

the content creators and authors recognized. The spaces for Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda titled 'reservoir of nutritional recommendations' provide a panoramic view of the NRs by manifesting the number of recommendations, age group of the NRs beneficiary, who could implement the NR and comments. An additional appendix providing an elongated alternate view of NRs is posted at the end of the report.

2 CHAPTER TWO: REPORT ON NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR KENYA

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Executive Summary

Kenya is one of the six countries in Africa, where FoodLAND is conducting its project activities. Currently, Kenya is fighting the tripartite burden of malnutrition that is; undernutrition, over nutrition and micronutrient deficiencies. Evidently, the rates of undernutrition are gradually decreasing whereas those of overnutrition are increasing across the lifecycle groups at a national level. Different counties exhibit different levels of malnutrition, with some doing better than others. In Kenya, FoodLAND is conducting its activities in three out of the forty-seven counties; Kitui, Kisumu and Nyeri counties. The main objective of this work package (D2.6), was to generate nutritional recommendations that will be exploited to cause change and impact among the community members. The recommendations were derived from three main sources, desk review findings; results of FoodLAND urban and rural consumers surveys (conducted in January 2022 and January 2023) and significant nutrition stakeholder engagement conferences. The recommendations are categorised as direct, sensitive or facilitative and are divided along the different lifecycle groups; from 0-<6 months to elderly persons; in tandem with the existing Kenya government's nutrition intervention trajectory.

2.1 Introduction

Kenya is a country in the Eastern part of Africa and is situated right along the equator. It is bordered by Tanzania to the south, Uganda to the west, Southern Sudan to the north-west, Ethiopia to the north and Somalia to the East. Kenya has a population of 46.56 million people, of whom 49.5 % and 50.4% are males and females respectively. According to the 2019 census, a larger percentage of the population lives in the rural areas (68.8%) compared to those living in the urban areas (31.2%). As of 2019, the children of two years of age and below made up 3.67% of the population with more males (50.15%) than females (49.85%). A higher percentage of the population live in the rural areas (67.89%) compared to those living in the urban areas (32.1%). With reference to the census conducted in August 2019, women of reproductive age (WRA) form a quarter (25.4%) of the population, with 62.9% living in the rural areas and 37.1% residing in the urban areas (*Kenya Population and Housing Census, 2019*).

In a bid to monitor the population and health situation in the country, the government of Kenya, through the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), periodically conducts demographic health surveys (DHS). The seventh and the latest DHS was conducted in 2022, with the previous ones having been conducted in 1989, 1993, 1998, 2003 2009 and 2014. Maternal health and mortality, nutrition, breastfeeding and child health form part of the indicators of focus (National Bureau of Statistics Nairobi, 2023).

According to Article 53 of the Kenyan constitution, every child has a right to basic nutrition, shelter and healthcare (*Constitution of Kenya*, 2010). County nutrition action plan (CNAP) and Kenya nutrition action plan (KNAP) are strategic documents generated at county and national levels, respectively. The goal being to contribute towards achieving optimal nutrition for a healthier and better quality of life and improved productivity, for the country's accelerated social and economic growth. Currently, the development of the KNAP 2023-2027 is underway and offers a good platform for propelling FoodLAND's recommendation to the public arena.

Administratively, Kenya is governed by a two-tier devolved system comparing the national and the county governments. The country is divided into forty-seven (47) counties that have been allocated codes (from 1 to 47). Each county is governed by a governor who is supported by a county assembly. Under this structure, agriculture, nutrition, health, education (ECD, childcare facilities, village polytechnics and home craft centres) are functions that are devolved to the county (AFROCAVE, 2022). FoodLAND is conducting its project activities in three counties, namely; Kitui, Nyeri and Kisumu.

2.2 Protocol for nutritional recommendations

As a first step, the UoN operationalized the meaning of the term significant nutritional stakeholders for the purpose of the NRs process. The term was defined as referring to individuals (who included household members), government sectors, community groups and other human groups with interest in achieving good nutrition for humans.

Given the open form of this operational definition, a decision was made to limit the participants to a manageable group, of between 45 to 50 relevant participants taking into consideration the conversion of the NRs to exploitable results. Against that backdrop an inclusion criterion was applied that specified that only the government sectors that are more precise in their engagement in nutrition and who would therefore play an effective role in exploiting the NRs be included. As such, the following groups were prioritised and given a chance to be the participants; representatives of households, community groups who represent households and individuals in various forums (community health promoters/volunteers (CHP/CHV), SCCHFP, government ministries that are closely aligned to human nutrition interests and FoodLAND teams representing the UoN, and the food hubs aligned to FoodLAND (Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company (KEPC) and Kisumu Food Hub; it is closely aligned to the County Ministry

of Agriculture). The government sectors engulfed ministries of health (with special inclusion of representation of the county level nutritionists), agriculture livestock & fisheries, trade & industry, social & gender and the office of the County government. All, as policy makers, financial and partnership providers & mobilisers, implementers and evaluators are frontline players in human nutrition issues in Kenya. The roles the participants play are categorised as direct (where the beneficiaries of nutritional interventions fit), sensitive and facilitative, the latter being responsible for providing an enabling environment that includes policy formulation.

Recruitment of conference participants: FoodLAND contacted the County Director of the Department of Public Health (DPH) and floated the idea of the conference. The DPH guided on the required protocol thus the first contact was to be the Commissioner Executive Committee member (CECM). CECM then gave the okay to run the conference in the County and directed that the team liaise with the DPH thus a list of categories of the desired participants was submitted. The DPH, in a cascaded form, specified the categories within the ranks and guided the team to work with the County Nutrition Coordinator (CNC) as the conference liaison person and participants mobiliser. The logic of the cascaded structure being that the SCCHFP are directly linked with the CHP/V while CHP/V are directly linked to the households, the level at which the primary beneficiaries of NRs exist. Most important for exploitation of the NRs, the line-up is responsible for the implementation of cascaded interventions that emerge from NRs.

With the CNC's input, names were attached to the government participants. The CNC selected and invited the sub-county nutritionists who then identified and invited specific SCCHFP and CHP/V. The CHP/V and the latter recruited household level participants. The desire for UoN-FoodLAND was to achieve a cascaded representation from the governor's office, through the ministries, the community to the households. Thus, the conference had the FoodLAND study respondents represented by the household level participants.

Implementation of the conference: This was a two-day event with an official programme. The DPH officiated the opening ceremony while the CECM officially opened the Conference. Considering the uptake and exploitation of the NRs the participation of these two county influential officers is important. The participants from a far distance were given allowances to cover to-and-from the conference travel and accommodation for two nights. During the two days, the Conference gave participation allowance and provided lunch and refreshments.

Creating a springboard for critiquing and validating the FoodLAND already formulated NRs:

The Conference was briefed on both the FoodLAND project and its objectives as well as the conference, respectively. The UoN presented an abridged form of situational architecture of the counties and the already generated NRs. The participants divided into five dialogue groups (DG) interrogated the recommendations in the context of their knowledge of nutritional gaps/issues and those highlighted in the situational architecture. The DG identified gaps in the NRs and generated additional ones. They then presented at a plenary following which the participants representing each sub-county were put into second sets of DGs. They interrogated

the results of the initial DGs and proposed a way forward on what to do with the NRs; this launched conversion of NRs into exploitable results. They also generated action plans on how they would act on the NRs.

The two conferences were well attended, vibrant and achieved the set objectives.

2.3 Situational Architecture

Kitui County, otherwise referred to as county 15, is located in the Eastern side of Kenya and is roughly 160 km from Kenya's capital city, Nairobi. Its headquarters are in Kitui Central Sub-county, Kitui town. In terms of the area occupied, Kitui County is the 6th largest county. It sits on 30,496 Km². It lies within latitudes 0^o10S and 3^o0 South and longitudes of 37^o50E and 39^o East. It is one of the twenty-nine (29) counties that are classified as arid and semi-arid lands with an aridity ranging from 30% to 84%. Even though some parts of the county experience a sub-humid climate, most of the areas within Kitui County experience unreliable rainfall (Kitui County Integrated plan 2018-2022, 2018).

According to the population census conducted in 2019, Kitui County has a total population of 1,082, 136 persons with 48.3% male and 51.7% female. Children under the age of two years make up 6.8% of the population; (50.3% male and 49.7% female) whereas more than a quarter of the population (29.2%) is made up of women of reproductive age.

Nyeri County, county number 19, is located within the central part of Kenya It covers an area of 3,337.2 km² and it lies between longitudes 360 38" east and 370 20" east and between the equator and latitude 00 380 south. Its county headquarters is located in Nyeri town. Nyeri County is predominantly an agriculturally based county known for its growing of coffee, tea and food crops such as maize. The county experiences equatorial rainfall due to its location within the highland zone of Kenya (Nyeri County Integrated Development Plan, 2018).

Nyeri has a total population of 759,133 persons of whom 49.3% and 50.7% are male and female respectively. Children of two years and below form 5.8% of the population in Nyeri (50.4% males and 49.4% female). A quarter (25.2%) of the population in Nyeri is made up of women of reproductive age (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2019).

Kisumu County, with the county code 42, is one of the 47 counties in Kenya and part of the six (6) counties in the Nyanza region. The county lies between longitudes 330 20'E and 350 20'E and latitude 00 20' South and 00 50' South and sits on approximately 0.36% of Kenya's total land area. It is surrounded by Lake Victoria; the second largest freshwater lake in the world. Kisumu County is bordered by Siaya County to the west, Kericho County to the east, Homabay to the south, Vihiga and Nandi Counties to the North West and East respectively. The county is divided into eight (8) sub-counties namely: Kisumu East, Kisumu West, Kisumu Central, Muhoroni, Nyando, Seme and Nyakach and further into thirty-five wards.

According to the 2019 population census, Kisumu County has a total of 1,155,551 persons, of whom slightly more than half are female (51%) whereas 49% are male. Children below two years of age makeup 7.3% of the county's population, with an almost equal distribution among males and females, that is 49.96% and 50.04 % respectively. Slightly over one quarter (26.03%) of the population are women of reproductive age. A higher number of the county's population lives in the rural areas than in the urban and peri-urban parts of Kisumu County.

The current national prevalence rate of exclusive breastfeeding is 60%, this is a drop from 61% in 2014 (National Bureau of Statistics Nairobi, 2014, 2023). Though highly discouraged, 4% of children in Kenya are bottle-fed, with a higher percentage in the urban (8.3%) than the rural areas (1.9%) (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics., 2018). According to (National Bureau of Statistics Nairobi, 2023), only 31% of children in Kenya were fed an adequate diet, 37% consumed a diverse diet and 52% of non-breastfed children were given at least two milk feeds. Close to three-quarters (71%) of the children had been fed age-appropriate times. Consumption of savoury snacks, sweet snacks and sugar-sweetened beverages is gaining popularity in the under-fives bracket. The consumption of sweet snacks and sugar-sweetened beverages is higher in the urban population than the rural population(PMA, 2020, 2018).

The rates of stunting, underweight, and overweight among the under-fives has reduced from 26%, 11% and 4% in 2014 to 18%, 10% and 3% respectively in 2022 whereas the rate of wasting went up to 5% in 2022 from 4% in 2014 (National Bureau of Statistics Nairobi, 2014, 2023).

Among adolescents, boys have a higher propensity of being underweight than girls, whereas girls have a higher propensity of being overweight than boys. Snacking behaviour is quite common among adolescents but is largely determined by the socio-economic status of the students among other factors. The higher the socio-economic status the higher the levels of snacking. The most consumed snack is energy rich snacks (58.3%) with fruits being the least consumed (1.1%)(Muthoni, 2012).

Significant differences in body mass index (BMI) exist in the urban–rural setups in Kenya. There are more overweight and obese women in the urban areas than in the rural areas (Steyn et al., 2012). Between the years 2011- 2016, both among adult men and women, the rates of undernutrition were decreasing while as the rates of overweight and obesity were on the rise (Bentham et al., 2017).

Despite WHO recommendation of 180 eggs per person per year which translates to 3-4 eggs per week per person, according to the standard newspaper 2012. Thus with a consumption of 36 eggs per person per year (about 3 eggs per person per month) Kenyan's egg consumption is quite low. ("Why Kenyans Should Eat More Eggs Daily," 2012).

In Kenya, non-communicable diseases account for over half of the total hospital admissions and more than half (55%) of deaths that occur in the hospital. The key NCDs in Kenya are cancers, diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, cardiovascular conditions. FoodLAND's flagship in Kenya is diabetes. The prevalence of diabetes among adults in Kenya is

3.3% and is projected to rise to 4.5% by 2025 (WHO 2015). The prevalence rates are higher in Nyeri county (7.2%) compared to the other two counties.

The results of the rural consumers survey conducted in Kitui County in January 2023 showed that consumption of high biological value protein is quite low. Among women in Kitui; the rates of consumption were; eggs 14.7%, cheese 0.4%, yoghurt 8.6%, poultry 3.9%, unprocessed red meat, ruminant and non-ruminant; 15.7%, 1.7% respectively. Though the results showed that consumption of milk is high (78%), the adequacy of the quantity consumed is not certain (Figure 2.1). A similar trend of low consumption of high biological value protein was observed among children (Figure 2.2)

Figure 2.1: Consumption rates of the 29 food groups among women in Kitui county (rural)

Figure 2.2: showing the consumption rates of the 29 food groups among children in Kitui county (rural).

More than half of residents (64.3%) in Kitui rural experience serious food shortages; only 2.7% have what they need; 0.2% have more than enough. The scarcest foods are; fish (94.6%), meat (93.5%), cereals (93.2%) and fruits and vegetables (88%).

More than half (56%) in Kitui are dependent on handouts/remittances. Education status of women is fairly low; only 38.9% have primary level while only 48% have secondary and 12.4% have more than secondary level qualification. Comparing the diet quality of women in urban and rural areas, those in the urban areas consume diets of higher quality than those in the rural areas. In descending order, the MDD-W in the three areas of study was Kitui urban (82%), Nyeri urban (77.1%) and Kitui rural (65.2%). Notably, women in the rural areas consumed less of NCD-risk foods than those in the urban areas (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1: Comparison of diet quality of women in Kitui urban, Kitui rural and Nyeri urban

	Kitui Urban	Kitui Rural	Nyeri Urban	Nyeri Rural
MDD-W	82%	65.2%	77.1%	ND
All-5	79.8%	44.7%	73.3%	ND
FGDS	8.5±2.7	5.2±1.7	8.3±3.0	ND
NCD-P	4.7±1.8	3.42±1.4	4.8±2.0	ND
NCD-R	2.2±1.5	1.14±1.6	4.6±1.5	ND
GDR	11.6±1.8	11.3±1.6	12.2±2.0	ND

Within the Kenyan context, the government, through the ministry of health and aligned ministries has set in place strategies to improve the nutrition status of its citizens. Campaigns promoting exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months and continued breastfeeding up to two years of age has borne good fruits. Fortification, supplementation, diet diversification and public health control measures are the strategies employed by the government to curb micronutrient deficiencies. Routine iron supplementation for low birth weight infants and pregnant women, is an on-going intervention at the health facilities. The antenatal clinics (ANC) at the various health facilities provide pregnant women with an opportunity to benefit from the wide-ranging health services offered that include; nutrition education, HIV and AIDS testing, weight monitoring and IFAS supplementation. Globally the prevalence rates of NCDs is gradually increasing, this same trend is observed in Kenya. The Ministry of Health through the health facilities has set up NCD-related clinics to offer preventive and curative medical services.

2.4 Nutritional Recommendations

2.4.1 Nutritional recommendations for children 0 - <6 months

The most common nutritional challenges in this age bracket are; iron deficiency, dropping rates of EBF. The current intervention on routine iron supplementation targets only low birth weight babies. The recommendation cut across gender, geographical locations (rural and urban), education and economic backgrounds.

1) Administer routine daily iron supplementation to children below six months

- Ministry of Health to formulate and implement a policy on routine iron supplementation for children below six months of age.
- Health facilities to support mothers to administer routine iron supplements to children at four months of age.
- Community health promoters/volunteers to mobilise mothers to practise routine iron supplementation for children aged below six months
- Mothers administer oral iron 1 Mg/Kg of child body weight per day.
- Manufacturers to develop age-appropriate iron supplements
- Mainstream and social media to aggressively stimulate adoption of age-specific iron supplementation for children 0 to<6 months
- Research institutions to conduct longitudinal studies at county level to monitor iron status in the child's first six months of life
- Collaborating partners, national and county government ministries to facilitate funding for iron supplementation

2) Adopt innovative ways of elevating and protecting exclusive breastfeeding

- Health workers spur mothers to adopt more innovative ways of exclusive breastfeeding behaviour such as expressing breastmilk and skin-to-skin to contact.
- Mothers who spend any time away from the child to adopt practical, safe and hygienic ways of feeding the child on expressed breastmilk.
 - i. Adherence to hygiene expression, handling and storage of breastmilk should be emphasised.
- Spouse and other household members to continuously encourage mothers to practise exclusive breastfeeding.
- Government to enforce law mandating employers to provide lactation rooms for breastfeeding mothers.

3) Address re-emergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)

- Mother and child caregivers to sunbathe a child in minimal clothing exposing maximum skin to the sun, at least 15-30 minutes twice to thrice a week.
- Urban housing planners to design buildings that allow residences access to sunshine.

2.4.2 Nutritional recommendations for children 6-23 months

The most common nutritional challenges in this age bracket are; low quality undiversified diets, low consumption of nutrient dense foods, stunting, underweight, wasting, obesity, iron deficiency and rickets (vitamin D deficiency; lack of exposure to the sun and lack of vitamin D supplementation as the key predisposing factors), poor complementary feeding habits and continued breastfeeding. The latter are being addressed within the on-going national interventions. The recommendation cut across gender, geographical locations (rural and urban), education and economic backgrounds.

1) Improving diet quality of children aged six to <24 months by diversifying the diet to ensure inclusion of the per day recommended eight (8) food groups to meet the minimum target of five out of eight for breastfeeding and four out of seven for non-breastfeeding children.

- Include adequate amounts (using volume and frequency in consumption) of foods of high biological protein value and nutrient dense foods; meat, poultry, fish, eggs, dairy and quinoa in children's diet.

2) Implement actions towards reducing malnutrition (stunting, underweight, wasting, overweight, and obesity)

- Stunting- Continually feed children on adequate amounts of foods of high protein biological value (meat, poultry, fish, eggs, dairy).

- Wasting and underweight-ensure adequate caloric intake
 - i. Caregivers incorporate daily consumption of energy dense foods; ghee, avocado, nuts (peanuts and macadamia) in the children’s diet.
 - ii. Increase consumption of ghee (due to its high caloric content) as a substitute for commercial energy dense products in management and prevention of undernutrition (wasting and underweight) at community level.
- Overweight and Obesity
 - i. Equip mothers and supporting caregivers with capacity and skills to recognize overweight and obesity by adhering to growth monitoring.
 - ii. Equip mothers and supporting caregivers with knowledge on foods that predispose children to overweight and obesity and aggravate over nutrition status.
 - iii. Mainstream and social media to conscientize the population on overweight and obesity and its consequences on health.

3) Administer routine iron supplementation to children 6 - <24 months

- Manufacturers to develop age-appropriate iron supplements
- Mainstream and social media to aggressively stimulate adoption of age-specific iron supplementation for children 6 - <24 months of age
- Research institutions to conduct longitudinal studies at county level to monitor iron status in the child’s first two years of life
- Collaborating partners, national and county government ministries to facilitate funding for iron supplementation

4) Address re-emergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)

- Mother and child caregivers to ensure a child plays in minimal clothing exposing maximum skin, within acceptable limits, to the sun (especially at sunrise rise and sunset) at least 15-30 minutes twice to thrice a week.
- Community health promoters/volunteers to campaign for routine administration of cod-liver oil to children by mothers and child caregivers
- Social media to incorporate elements of social marketing alongside commercial advertisement of cod-liver oil.

2.4.3 Nutritional recommendations for children 2 - <5 years

The most common nutritional challenges in this age bracket are; low quality undiversified diets, low consumption of nutrient dense foods, stunting, underweight, wasting, obesity, iron deficiency and rickets (vitamin D deficiency). This is the period at which initiation of poor dietary habits, such as consumption of fast foods, ultra-processed packaged salty snacks, sugary sweetened beverages (soda) and sweets occurs. Considering that the issues cut across

gender, geographical locations (rural and urban), education and economic backgrounds so do the given nutritional recommendations.

1) Improve diet quality of children aged 2 - <5 years by diversifying the diet to ensure inclusion of the per day recommended seven (7) food groups to meet the minimum target of four out of seven.

- Mothers and caregivers especially at the household level to;
 - i. Feed children offal/ organ meat once a week
 - ii. Feed children on traditional vegetables and fruits everyday

2) Implement actions towards reducing malnutrition (stunting, underweight, wasting, overweight, and obesity)

- Stunting- Continually feed children on adequate amounts of foods of high protein biological value (meat, poultry, fish, eggs, dairy).
- Wasting and underweight-ensure adequate caloric intake
 - i. Caregivers incorporate daily consumption of energy dense foods; ghee, avocado, nuts (peanuts and macadamia) in the children's diet.
 - ii. Increase consumption of ghee (due to its high caloric content) as a substitute for commercial energy dense products in management and prevention of undernutrition (wasting and underweight) at community level.
- Overweight and Obesity
 - i. Equip mothers and supporting caregivers with capacity and skills to recognize overweight and obesity by adhering to growth monitoring.
 - ii. Equip mothers and supporting caregivers with knowledge on foods that predispose children to overweight and obesity and aggravate over nutrition status.
 - iii. Mainstream and social media to conscientize the population on overweight and obesity and its consequences on health.

3) Mitigate uptake of poor dietary habits

- Health workers to conscientize (knowledge and intention to act) the mothers and child caregivers on the period at which initiation of poor dietary habits, such as consumption of fast foods, ultra-processed packaged salty snacks, sugar sweetened beverages (soda) and sweets occurs.
- Health care workers to equip mothers and child caregivers with skills on how to negotiate with their children for healthy snacking and avoidance of unhealthy snacks.
- Mothers and caregivers to create a child-enabling environment for avoiding consumption of unhealthy snacks and instead adopt healthy snacking behaviour.

4) Administer routine iron supplementation to children 2 -<5 years

- Health facilities to administer iron supplementation alongside on-going routine vitamin A supplementation
- Manufacturers to develop age-appropriate iron supplements
- Mainstream and social media to aggressively stimulate adoption of age-specific iron supplementation for children 2 -<5 months of age
- Research institutions to conduct longitudinal studies at county level to monitor iron status in the child’s first five years of life
- Collaborating partners, national and county government ministries to facilitate funding for iron supplementation

5) Address re-emergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)

- Mother and child caregivers ensure a child plays in minimal clothing exposing maximum skin to the sun (especially at sunrise rise and sunset) at least 15-30 minutes twice to thrice a week.
- Community health promoters/volunteers to campaign for routine administration of cod-liver oil to children by mothers and child caregivers
- Social media to incorporate elements of social marketing alongside commercial advertisement of cod-liver oil.

2.4.4 Nutritional recommendations for Adolescents (ages 10-19 years)

The common nutritional challenge for adolescents has evolved from a background of stunted under-fives to adolescents who are shorter than their potential height. Adolescence is a stage in life that provides an opportunity for catch-up in height within the growth spurt phase. Against this backdrop, adolescents tend to be short, overweight/obese in addition to being micronutrient deficient, especially iron. This is the lifecycle stage at which poor dietary habits, such as over consumption of fast foods, ultra-processed packaged salty snacks, sugar sweetened beverages (soda) and sweets occurs. Their current diet is characterised by low quality undiversified diets, low consumption of nutrient dense foods and high consumption of ultra-processed snacks and sweetened beverages. Considering that the issues cut across gender, geographical locations (rural and urban), education and economic backgrounds so do the given nutritional recommendations.

1) Adopt diet diversification to improve diet quality

- Adolescents:- to make and own transformative nutritious conscious decisions
- Adolescents:- to adjust the three meals a day, especially breakfast, to resemble a whole meal that includes high nutrient dense foods in particular, those of high protein biological value and high fibre content (whole foods).

2) Adopt healthy snacking behaviour

- Adolescents:- to reduce consumption of highly processed salted snacks – crisps and sweetened beverages.
- Adolescents to convert to consumption of healthy snacks; groundnuts, fruits in place of highly processed snacks.

3) Curb iron and other micronutrient deficiencies

- Adolescents:- to elevate their consumption of iron rich foods such as locally available dark green vegetables, meats including organ meat and especially liver.
- Guardians, teachers and health workers:- to instil in adolescents the desire to ensure consumption of variety of vegetables and fruits.

4) Drink the recommended quantities of water;

- Adolescents:- to ensure they drink 6-8 glasses (240ml) per day.
- Parents/caregivers:- to procure colourful water bottles to stimulate the urge to drink water.

5) Reduce and prevent overweight and obesity among adolescents

- Adolescents:- to routinely monitor their waistline as an action towards maintenance of ideal body weight.
- Researchers:- to determine appropriate waistline cut-off points for female and males adolescents for the creation of a graduated tape measure.
- Adolescents:- to increase participation physical activities- games and sports such as soccer, basketball, netball, volleyball among others.

To motivate the adolescents to adopt transformational change, certain incentives are needed. The motivation will come from the different role-players in the adolescents' lives who include; peers, parents, schools and other communities that they interact with, health service providers and social media. Thus the need to incentivize through formation of communities of practice (CoP) to address issues such as body image (e.g., body image clubs) at school and community level. The CoPs may need guidelines that could be developed by the Nutrition and Dietetics Unit (NDU) of the Ministry of Health. Parents should provide an enabling environment to facilitate good dietary practices and adjustments by the adolescents. The school should adopt innovative strategies for supporting good dietary practices among the adolescents. The communities should involve the adolescents in their existing forums e.g. women groups (chamas), ten-cells household units (nyumba kumi), and chiefs' public meetings (barazas) as an avenue to negotiate and instil good dietary practices in them. Health service providers should provide adolescents with supportive transformational tools and skills to actualize the decision on appropriate food choices for diet diversification and improved quality. Riding on their high interest in social media, adolescents' within their CoPs should be able to identify the appropriate social media sites may positively influence them to adopt good dietary practices.

2.4.5 Women of reproductive age, pregnant women, lactating and teenage mothers

Historically, pregnant women, lactating mothers, including teenage mothers, in Kenya have been receiving comprehensive care that includes knowledge communication, iron and folate supplementation and the recently introduced calcium supplementation albeit in selected counties. However, there are no specific recommendations for women of reproductive age who are neither pregnant nor lactating. Thus they are considered under the recommendations made for the general population.

1) Improve diet quality by diversifying the diet using at least the 10 recommended food groups to achieve a minimum of five food groups a day

- Individuals to:- increase consumption of whole grain foods.
- Individuals to:- increase consumption of dark green and yellow vegetables.
- Individuals to:- increase consumption of variety of food groups to ensure inclusion of the recommended ten food groups.
- Health service providers to:- provide nutrition education to lead to transformational decision making and action on adoption of consumption of diverse nutrient dense foods.

2) Reduce and prevent iron and calcium deficiencies

- Individuals:- to increase dietary intake of foods rich in iron and calcium.
- Pregnant and lactating women to:- adopt the practice of routine assessment for status of calcium and iron through medical testing and check-up.

3) In addition to the recommendation stated above; develop a better nutritional environment for teenage mothers

- County governments to:- educate and give relevant skills on diversifying sources of income to solve issues of lack of enough food and income (food security).
- Household to:- provide adequate and nutritious food to teenage mothers.
- Teenage mothers to:- increase consumption of high biological value protein and nutrient dense foods.
- Teenage mothers to:- avoid intake of ultra-processed snacks and beverages
- Household and community members to:- offer social support to the teenage mothers to facilitate a sustainable conducive environment for appropriate nutritional behaviours.

2.4.6 Nutritional recommendations for adult men

Due to their sedentary lifestyle they are particularly predisposed to; overweight, obesity and NCDs that include; metabolic syndrome, Type II diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular

diseases, cancers, hypertension and gout. Poor dietary habits, undiversified diets and excessive consumption of alcohol are significant contributing factors.

1) Improve diet quality through diet diversification using the concept of the recommended 10 food groups.

- Adult men to:- consume foods from at least five food groups of the recommended ten food groups.
- Nutritionists to:- provide nutrition education on benefits of consumption of nutritious snacks for informed decision-making hence their consumption.

2) Limit/eliminate consumption of foods and substances that are hazardous to health

- Adult men to:- avoid foods that predispose them to nutrition related health hazards (refer to section 2.4.9).
- Adult men to:- moderate alcohol intake preferably to completely abstain; with the enabling help of household members, nutritionists, community health outreach cadres, counsellors and the faith-based organisations.

3) Offer to adult men transformational nutrition education on importance of nutritious healthy eating

- Adult men to:- reduce consumption of highly processed and salty foods.
- Adult men to:- be intentional in reading food labels and to act appropriately.

4) Improve level of physical activity of adult men

- Nutritionists and other health workers to:- sensitise adult men on the various ways of measuring physical activity performance (mobile phone apps etc).
- Nutritionists with the support of community-based outreach to:- engage in continuous conversations and dialogues with adult men as a channel of convincing them to adopt a more active and monitored physical lifestyle.

5) Adult men to ensure that they get health facility based regular nutritional and medical check-ups (a must- blood glucose, blood pressure, prostate)

- Adult men to:- create and follow a plan for routine nutritional and health check-ups.
- Community based health outreach to:- mobilise adult men to go for routine nutritional and medical check-ups.

2.4.7 Nutritional recommendations for the elderly persons

The common nutritional challenges for this age group are similar for both females and males and are mostly age related. Their diet is characterised by starchy staples, foods of low biological value protein, low nutrient density and limited variety and amounts of fruits and vegetables. In the absence of research-based evidence on their micronutrient status, nutrition status and

prevalence rates of NCDs, the recommendations given are based on the patterns observed in the preceding population lifecycle groups and input from FoodLAND's stakeholders engagement conferences.

The elderly is a special lifecycle population group with unique age-related challenges that include; dental, psychological, cognitive decline and other health challenges.

1) Improve diet quality through food diversification

- Nutritionists, through nutrition education to:- sensitise the elderly and their caregivers on the importance and consumption of a diversified nutrient dense diet, inclusive of foods of high biological value protein.
- Elderly persons with support from the caregivers to:- reduce consumption of starchy foods by offering smaller portions.

2) Improve nutritional and health status of the elderly

- Enhance dental care for the elderly persons
 - i. The elderly to:- take charge of their oral and dental health to facilitate ease and smooth mastication of food.
 - ii. The elderly with support of the caregivers to:- should have regular dental check-ups and take appropriate action.
- The household level support system of the elderly to:- comprehend the psychological propensity of people of this age group so as to provide conducive environment for consumption of nutritious diets.
- The elderly and their caregivers to:- obtain only from licensed practitioners nutritional information and aligned advice intended for application.
- The elderly to:- moderate and preferably abstain from alcohol consumption.
- The elderly to:- integrate intentional intake of drinking water for weight loss, good health and well-being.
- The elderly to:- ensure that they engage in age-appropriate physical exercises for weight management, muscle toning/building and well-being.

3) Conduct research for evidence-based action for the elderly

- Researchers to:- establish state of the art nutrition, including micronutrient status, of the elderly for precision based intervention.
- The government to:- include data collection of the elderly in its routine data acquisition systems such as in the demographic health survey (DHS).

2.4.8 Nutritional recommendations for the general household

The households are characterised by consumption of limited diversified diets, low consumption of high biological value protein, nutrient dense foods, seeds and nuts. This, most probably, arises from low income and resistance to adopt appropriate dietary habits.

1) Improve household diet quality by adopting better diet diversification

- Revive/establish kitchen gardens (individual or households in groups).
- Adopt growing and consumption of nutrient dense crops – such as quinoa
- Increase consumption of protein of high biological value- meat, poultry, fish, eggs, dairy
 - i. Households to increase the number of chickens kept for eggs for both dietary consumption and sale. To achieve this; they should have one egg-laying chicken per household member and an additional number for sale and to cover defaulted egg-laying.
 - ii. Adopt production of mala (fermented milk) and yogurt for household consumption and income generation.
 - iii. County government and development partners to:- support fish farming in the community to create, encourage and meet demand for high biological value protein.

2) Increase consumption of nuts and seeds across age groups among households

- Adopt consumption of pumpkin seeds (*rich in zinc, manganese and vit K*).
- Intentionally chew seeds in fruits-, such as, melon seeds, passion fruit seeds (intentional chewing and breaking to aid digestion- normally people do not chew, they swallow them whole and digestion does not break them for the consumer to access benefits within the seed). For example, passion fruit seeds are rich in magnesium, potassium, vitamin A and C.
- Adopt consumption of locally available nuts; macadamia nuts, groundnuts among others that are available with the market and reach of the consumers.
- Nutritionists should provide transformational awareness on the nutritional importance and benefits of consuming (including chewing/breaking) seeds.

3) Diversify the diet using the age based recommended food groups

- Nutritionists to:- provide transformational awareness to household members on the existing food groups for cognition and action (consumption).
- Households to:- take-up new behaviour based on acquired transformational awareness.
- Household head to:- prioritise household food and nutrition needs while continuously being stimulated by nutritionists and community-based outreach.

4) Reduce overweight and obesity rates at household level;

- **The household member to:**

- i. Conscientize household members on matters of overweight and obesity.
- ii. Upload a step-tracking application into the phones to monitor their daily activity (steps)
- iii. Ensure they walk preferably 7500-10000 steps a day.
- iv. Reduce portion sizes of the starchy staples- 'high-carb foods' (potatoes, sweet potatoes, rice, wheat products, maize).
- v. Increase portion sizes of pulses such as green grams, lentils, pigeon peas, peas and cowpeas and elevate consumption of high biological value protein foods.
- vi. Adopt intermittent fasting by reducing the number of meals consumed in a day- helps in weight management, blood sugar regulation and management of insulin resistance.
- vii. Acquire a tape measure and routinely monitor their waistline and take action if >40 for men and > 35 inches for women.
- viii. Promote increased uptake of existing mobile step tracking applications by creating awareness and interest through canvassing for increased use of the existing mobile step-tracking applications and data interpretation that lead to new practice.

5) Households to innovate means of increasing their own income to reduce dependence on remittances

- Households to:- link with relevant stakeholders who include; CBOs, SMEs and County governments.
- Households to:- enhance their propensity to take calculated risks to establish new income generating ventures.
- Household heads to:- be encouraged to prioritise household food and nutrition at the household level.

In cognisance of the current concerns related to climate change hence the suggestion that diets that are 'rich in animal protein' are a major contributor to the situation, there is need to explain that Kenyan diets are not yet in that category. Indeed, due to undernutrition, Kenyan nutritional guidelines recommend that people eat meat at least twice a week. With populations where stunting is a problem meat and other animal foods are efficient sources of protein of both high biological value and bioavailability hence more suitable in addressing undernutrition, especially among children. Meat being a nutrient dense food is also good nutrient source for the elderly persons let alone for all populations groups in the life cycle. In addition, micronutrients are more bioavailable in animal protein than in plant protein. Most Kenyan households and especially so in the regions where FoodLAND project operates have limited access to sea foods/fish. This is unlike in the more developed countries that easily substitute one high biological value protein food with another (seafood/fish). In a more general context, pastoralists populations mostly depend on animal (mostly cattle and goats) based foods (milk, meat).

- On the one hand consumption of meat is recommended under Kenya's guidelines whereas there is no evidence that confirms that consumption of diets rich in animal protein in Kenya are

significantly contributing to global warming. In this context generation of data to establish the status quo is recommended while at policy level Kenya should hence consider integration and operationalisation of the concept of low-greenhouse gas emission in food systems.

2.4.9 Nutritional recommendations for technological innovators, manufacturers and social media

FoodLAND has developed exploitable results that need uptake and subsequent sustainability. The three closely aligned to Kenya are; precision harvesting, strategic preservation (cold storage and solar dryers) and bio-based packaging. The nutritional recommendations can provide a platform for exploitation of these novel technologies that FoodLAND has generated. In the process of exploiting results, manufacturers may play an important role through value addition of existing products and making available, for uptake, the new technologies in the markets. The social media will play the role of informing and stimulating the consumers.

1) FoodLAND to avail prototypes of the novel nutritional related technological products to the industry

- FoodLAND to:- develop strategies for technology transfer of exploitable results.
- FoodLAND to:- transfer the technology to manufacturers.
- Policy makers and regulators to:- develop policies, regulations and legislate; to support uptake and scaling up of the novel technologies.

2) Manufacturer to engage in mass production of novel nutritional related technologies and labelling

- Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND; cold storage, solar driers, mango harvesting tool and bio-based packaging materials.
- Farmers to use novel precise fruit harvesting technology at fruit optimal maturity.
- Manufacturers with reinforcement from the national government to label foods that predispose individuals to health risks and hazards:
 - i. “Excessive intake of sugar is harmful to your health”
 - ii. “Excessive salt intake is harmful to your health”
 - iii. “Excessive consumption of ultra-processed snacks is harmful- avoid them”
 - iv. “Excessive intake of carbonated and sweetened beverages/drinks is harmful to your health”
 - v. “Excessive intake of fast foods is harmful to your health”
- Manufacturers should produce value-added graduated tape measures to enable monitoring of waistline in mitigating overweight and obesity.

3) Social media to break and disperse the news on the novel technologies

- Social media platforms should social-market and promote adoption of the nutrition related novel technologies developed by FoodLAND.
- Social media platforms should create channels and strategies for sustained social marketing of the FoodLAND generated technologies.

2.4.10 Nutritional recommendations based on novel diet quality indicators

FoodLAND developed a 29-food group diet quality questionnaire (DQQ), from which varied indicators may be calculated. These indicators include; All-5, FGDS, NCD-protect, NCD-risk, GDR among others. This section contains FoodLAND recommendations on two of the indicators; NCD-protect and NCD-risk (Table 2.2. and 2.3).

Table 2.2: Recommendations on Non-communicable Disease-Protect indicators

NCD-P	Recommendation
<3- Minimal protection (Red)	To raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the nine (9) designated food groups
3-4 – Medium protection (brown)	To raise their consumption by at least two to three (2-3) of the nine (9) designated food groups
>4 -<6- Upper medium protection (orange)	To alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the nine (9) designated food groups
>6- High protection (green)	Ensure they maintain not less than six, while they strive to raise to the nine (9) designated food groups
The nine (9) recommended Whole grains, Pulses, Nuts and seeds, Vitamin A-rich vegetables, Dark green leafy vegetables, Other vegetables, Vitamin A-rich fruits, Citrus, Other fruits	

Table 2.3: Recommendations on Non-communicable Disease-Risk indicators

NCD-R	Recommendation
<3- Minimal risk (green)	To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats and minimise consumption of the food groups listed in row 6.
3-4 –Medium risk (orange)	To ensure their level of risk does not deteriorate by completely avoiding consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats; minimise consumption of the food groups listed in row 6.
>4 -<6- Upper medium risk (brown)	To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats and minimise consumption of the food groups listed in row 6; create healthy diet peer groups to support one another in adopting and sustaining healthy dietary practices.
>6- High risk (red)	To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats; to seek diet counselling that integrates physical activity for adoption and consider non-consumption of the food groups listed in row 6; create healthy diet peer group to support one another in adopting and sustaining healthy dietary practices; to initiate regular monitoring sessions with a health provider.
Row 6: Food groups to avoid/ reduce to minimal consumption	

Soft drinks (sodas), baked / grain-based sweets, other sweets, processed meat, unprocessed red meat, deep fried food, fast food & instant noodles, packaged ultra-processed salty snacks.

2.5 A reservoir of the Kenya FoodLAND nutritional recommendations

A collection of the Kenya FoodLAND NRs is shown in Table 2.4. Column two in the Table 2.4 shows the stakeholders who generated the NRs in that FL = FoodLAND- UoN, Ny = Nyeri and Ki = Kitui Stakeholders Conferences. The NRs were based on direct, sensitive and facilitative recommendations. A total of **103** direct NRs (FL 40, Ki 19, Ny 44), **12** Sensitive NRs (FL 11, Ki 1, Ny 0), and **6** Facilitative NRs (FL 5, Ki 0 and Ny 1) were generated. In total there were 121 NRs formulated – 56 from FoodLAND, 20 Kitui, and 45 Nyeri. Kitui and Nyeri stakeholders’ conferences contributed 16.5% and 37.2%, respectively and FoodLAND-UoN contributed 46.3% of the total NRs.

Table 2.4: A reservoir of the Kenya FoodLAND nutritional recommendations

Nutritional recommendations for children 0 < 6months

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments Gender, location e.g., rural, urban/income/ education
Give routine iron supplements drops from four months to five years of age	FL-5 Ki-4 Ny-3	Health facilities	A higher proportion of children in the rural areas are fed other foods other than breast milk compared to their urban counterparts. (KIHBS 2018)
Administer routine iron supplementation for low birth weight babies		Health facilities	
Nutritionists to invoke adoption of more innovative ways of convincing mothers to adopt new feeding behaviour such as expressing breastmilk.		Nutritionists Mothers	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments Gender, location e.g., rural, urban/income/ education
Mother and child caregivers to sunbathe a child in minimal clothing exposing maximum skin to the sun, at least 15-30 minutes twice to thrice a week		Mothers/ Caregivers	
Urban housing planners to design buildings that allow residences access to sunshine		Architects/ urban planners	
On-going interventions but need aggressive advocacy for more extensive uptake		MoH	
Health personnel to encourage kangaroo mother-care for low birth weight babies by family members		Health personnel	
Health personnel to encourage skin to skin contact and direct breastfeeding		Health personnel	
Nutritionists to provide nutrition education on hygienic expressing, handling and storage of breastmilk		Nutritionists	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments Gender, location e.g., rural, urban/income/ education
Nutritionists to provide transformational education on EBF for six months		Nutritionists	
The County government to be procuring iron supplements		The County Government	
Government to enforce law mandating employers to provide lactation rooms for breastfeeding mothers; Nutritionists to lobby/advocate for lactation room for all working mothers		MoH Nutritionists	

Nutritional recommendations for children 6-<24 months

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Mothers to practice continued breastfeeding (18-24 months)	FL-4	Mothers	Stunting is higher among children in

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Mothers/ caregivers to increase consumption of ghee (due to its high caloric content) for management and prevention of undernutrition (wasting and underweight).	Ki-1 Ny-12	Mothers/caregivers	rural areas (20%) than children in urban areas (12%).
Mothers and caregivers to diversify the diet using the recommended 8 food groups		Mothers/caregivers	Stunting decreases with increasing wealth, from 28% in the lowest quintile to 9% in the highest quintile.
Administer routine iron supplementation to children 6 - <24 months		Mothers/caregivers	More children (22%) born to mothers with no education are stunted, as compared with 9% of children born to mothers with more than a secondary education.
Nutrition personnel to talk to producers to make ghee more available in affordable packages.		Nutritionists	
Community Health Promoters with the facilitation of the nutritionists to train the community on ghee making at household level		Community Health Promoters	In Kitui County children's diet

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritionists to create awareness about ghee to all caregivers of breastfeeding children; Ghee is not locally available and its quite expensive. It can be substituted with other oils, e.g., coconut, olive, canola, sunflower, among others.		Nutritionists	became better with increase in mother's level of education
Mothers and caregivers to incorporate high biological value proteins to the children's diet-		Mothers/caregivers	
Mothers and caregivers to increase (in variety and amounts) consumption of traditional vegetables in the children's diet		Mothers/caregivers	
Nutritionists to create awareness and provide transformational health education to all mothers about food groups.		Nutritionists	
More frequent household outreach by CHP to encourage consumption of more food groups, at least four		Community Health Promoters	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritionists to conduct transformational nutrition education on proper food preparation that preserve nutrients.		Nutritionists	
Mothers/ caregivers to give children above 1-year goat milk- Due to its numerous benefits such as ease in digestibility compared to cow's milk		Mothers/caregivers	
Mothers to seek medical advice on boosting breastmilk let down from professionals.		Mothers	
Health practitioners to give health education on dental health		Health Practitioners	
Nutritionists to advocate for consumption of healthy snacks; reduced consumption of sugary snacks (avoid sugary beverages)		Nutritionists	
Nutritionists to teach and encourage mothers on varied nutrient dense diet		Nutritionists; Parents/ MoH/Health facility)	

Nutritional recommendations for children 0-5 years

	No of Recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritional recommendations for promoting micronutrient adequacy			
Give offal/ organ meat once a week			
Mothers to feed children on traditional vegetables everyday			
Develop age-appropriate iron supplements			
Household members to ensure consumption of legumes (beans, cowpeas, green-grams, pigeon peas) when organ meat unaffordable			
Households to ensure consumption of locally available fruits every day.			

Nutritional recommendations for Adolescents

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Adolescents: to adjust the three meals a day especially breakfast to resemble a whole meal that includes high nutrient dense foods especially those of high protein biological value and high fibre content (Whole foods).	FL-4 Ki-1 Ny-5	Self	Females had a more diversified diet compared to their male counterparts (Wanja, 2019). Prevalence of underweight in adolescents is higher in males than girls while as prevalence of overweight/obese in higher in females than males
Adolescents:- to reduce consumption of highly processed salted snacks – crisps and sweetened beverages		Self	
Adolescents should drink water- 6-8 glasses (240ml)		Self	
Adolescents:- to increase participation in games and sports such as soccer, basketball, netball, volleyball etc.		Self	
Parents and caregivers: to buy colourful bottles; to aid in consumption of recommended amounts of water		Parents/Caregivers	
Adolescents:- to increase consumption of iron rich foods		Self	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritionists:- to provide transformational nutrition education on importance of eating healthy, consumption of breakfast, need for eating a diversified diet; Actor:		Nutritionists	
Adolescents should include in their diet proteins (e.g., eggs,) at least 3 thrice weekly		Self	
Nutritionists:- to give nutrition education on overweight and obesity		Nutritionists	
Adolescents:- to go for regular health screening		Self	

Nutritional recommendations for Households

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Households to:- adopt consumption of pumpkin seeds (rich in zinc, manganese and vitamin K).	FL-5 Ki-1	Individuals/ households	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Household members:- to intentionally chew seeds in fruits-melon seeds, passion seeds (intentional chew and break them to aid digestion- normally people don't chew, they swallow them whole- passion seeds are rich in magnesium, potassium, vitamin A, and vitamin C).	Ny-0	Individuals/ households	
Households:- to adopt growing and consumption of nutrient dense crops – such as quinoa		Individuals/ households	
Households:- to increase consumption of protein of high biological value- meat, poultry, fish, eggs, dairy		Individuals/ households	
Households:- to increase consumption of macadamia nuts		Individuals/ households	
Nutritionists:- to create awareness on the seeds' nutritional benefits.		Nutritionists	

Nutritional recommendations for Women of Reproductive Age

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritionists and other health practitioners:- to encourage women to engage in healthy eating and physical exercises	Ki-2 Ny-3	Nutritionists	<p>Women in Kitui urban consume diets of a higher quality than those in the rural areas</p> <p>Women in rural areas consumed NCD- risk foods in lower quantities than those in the urban areas</p> <p>In Kitui and Nyeri Counties, the diet quality of the women improved with increase in education level</p> <p>There are more overweight and obese women in the urban areas than in the rural areas.(Steyn et al., 2012)</p>
WRA:- to increase consumption of foods rich in- iodine and calcium		Self	
WRA:- to go for medical testing and check-up so as to ensure all indicators are at normal before conception		Self	
WRA:- to go for routine check for calcium and iron status		Self	
WRA:- to ensure they diversify their diet using the recommended 10 food groups; Include the use of whole grains and consumption of dark green and yellow vegetables		Self	

Nutritional recommendations for Pregnant Women

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
<p><i>In addition to the recommendations for women of reproductive age;</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The government should ensure iron and calcium supplements are made available 	Ny-2	Self	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pregnant women:- to go for routine check-ups, 			

Nutritional recommendations for Teenage Mothers

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
<p><i>In addition to the recommendations for women of reproductive age;</i></p> <p>The county governments should educate and give relevant skills on diversifying sources of income to solve lack of enough food and income issues</p>	Ny- 4	Government (MoH)	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NRs	Comments
Nutritionists:- to help teenage mothers to come up with strategies to increase calcium and iron intake		Nutritionists	
Households:- to provide adequate and nutritious food to teenage mothers		Households	
Teenage mothers:- to increase consumption of high biological value protein and nutrient dense foods		Self	

Nutritional recommendations for Lactating Mothers

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
<p><i>In addition to the recommendations for women of reproductive age;</i></p> <p>Government:- to enforce law mandating employers to provide lactation rooms for lactating mothers</p>	Ny-2	Government	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
Spouse and other household members:- to continuously offer support for lactating mothers.		Spouse/ other household members	

Nutritional recommendations for Adult Men

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
Nutritionists to encourage adult men to engage in healthy eating practices and physical exercises	FL-0 Ki-3	Nutritionists	
Adult men to moderate or completely abstain from consumption of alcohol.	Ny-6	Self	
Adult men to reduce consumption of highly processed salty foods		Self	
Adult men should create intention to read food labels and to act appropriately		Self	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
Nutritionists to:- provide transformative nutrition education, to adult men, on benefits of snacks consumption for informed decision and their consumption.		Nutritionists	
Adult men:- to go for regular medical check-ups (e.g., blood glucose, blood pressure, prostate cancer)		Self	
Nutritionist:- to motivate me to diversify their diet using the recommended 10 food groups (for daily consumption of minimum five groups), physical exercise.		Self	
Nutritionists and other health workers:- to sensitise adult men on the various ways of measuring physical activity performance (mobile phone apps etc.)		Nutritionists and other health workers	

Nutritional recommendations for Elderly

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
Encourage healthy eating and physical exercises	FL-0		
Nutritionists, through nutrition education to sensitize the elderly and the caregivers on the importance and their consumption of a diversified nutrient dense diet inclusive of foods of high biological value protein	Ki-1 Ny-6	Nutritionists	
Regular eye and dental check-up for appropriate action		Self/ their caregivers	
The elderly and the caregivers to obtain for application all nutritional and aligned advice from licensed practitioners		Self/ caregivers	
The elderly to moderate and preferably abstain from alcohol consumption.		Self	
Elderly to integrate intake of drinking water for weight loss, good health and well-being.		Self	

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	comments
The elderly to ensure they engage in age-appropriate physical exercises for weight management, muscle toning/building and well-being.		Self	

NCD- BASED, WEIGHT LOSS AND ADDICTION TO FOOD/EATING

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Upload a step-tracking application into the phones to monitor their daily activity (steps)	FL-7	Individuals	
Ensure they walk 7500-10000 steps a day	Ki-3 Ny-0		
Reduce portion sizes of the starchy staples (potatoes, sweet potatoes, rice, wheat, maize)			
Increase portion sizes of pulses such as green grams, lentils, pigeon peas, peas and cow peas as well as include high biological value protein foods.			

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Adopt intermittent fasting by reducing the number of meals consumed in a day- helps in weight management, blood sugar regulation and management of insulin resistance.			
Acquire a tape measure and routinely monitor their waistline and take action if >40 for men and > 35 for women			
Low carb movement- Create and join low carb movements.			
Educate people on role of different food groups on NCDs			
Assist household to establish minimum required diet based on locally available foods			
Provide more focused knowledge (precise) on nutrition requirements in NCDs			

Nutritional Recommendations for manufacturers/ industry

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Manufacture colour coded tape-measures to aid in waistline monitoring for weight management	Ny-2	Manufacturers	
Introduce warning messages on package labels of foods that predispose individuals to NCDs			

Research- based nutritional recommendations

	No of recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Conduct longitudinal studies at county level to establish iron status in the first two years of life	FL-4 KI-1	Public and Private research institutions	
Conduct research on the consumption of milk (quantities consumed)			
Conduct research on nutritional status and diet quality of adolescents			
Research on effect of mulberry fruit and leaves on human health. Rich in iron, Vit C, Vit K, Calcium. Helpful in lowering blood sugar, weight loss.			
Research on different locally and wild growing berries- nutritional and nutraceutical value			

Nutritional Recommendations on NCD-R

NCD-R	No of Recommendation	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
<p><3- Minimal risk (green)</p> <p>To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats and minimize consumption of the food groups listed in row 6.</p>	<p>FL-4</p>	<p>Individuals</p>	
<p>3-4 –Medium risk (orange)</p> <p>To ensure their level of risk does not deteriorate by completely avoiding consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats; minimize consumption of the food groups listed in row 6.</p>			
<p>>4 -<6- Upper medium risk (brown)</p> <p>To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats and minimize consumption of the food groups listed in row 6; create healthy diet peer group to support one another in adopting and sustaining healthy dietary practices.</p>			

NCD-R	No Recommendation	of Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
<p>>6- High risk (red)</p> <p>To completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats; to seek diet counselling that integrates physical activity for adoption and consider non-consumption of the food groups listed in row 6; create healthy diet peer group to support one another in adopting and sustaining healthy dietary practices; to initiate regular monitoring sessions with a health provider.</p>			
<p>Food groups to avoid/ reduce to minimal consumption</p> <p>Soft drinks (sodas), baked / grain-based sweets, other sweets, processed meat, unprocessed red meat, deep fried food, fast food & instant noodles, packaged ultra-processed salty snacks.</p>			

Nutritional Recommendations on NCD-P

NCD-P	No of Recommendation	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
<p><3- Minimal protection (Red)</p> <p>To raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the nine (9) designated food groups</p>	<p>FL-4</p>	<p>Individuals</p>	
<p>3-4 – Medium protection (brown)</p> <p>To raise their consumption by at least two to three (2-3) of the nine (9) designated food groups</p>			
<p>>4 -<6- Upper medium protection (orange)</p> <p>To alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the nine (9) designated food groups</p>			
<p>>6- High protection (green)</p> <p>Ensure they maintain not less than six, while they strive to raise to the nine (9) designated food groups</p>			
<p>The nine (9) recommended Whole grains, Pulses, Nuts and seeds, Vitamin A-rich vegetables, Dark green leafy vegetables, Other vegetables, Vitamin A-rich fruits, Citrus, Other fruits</p>			

B) SENSITIVE NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

	No of Recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Household to revive/establish kitchen gardens (individual or households in groups).	FL-3	Households	
Household to adopt production of mala (fermented milk) and yogurt for household consumption and income generation.			
Households to establish means of generating their own income to reduce dependency on remittances			
Early screening for cancer	Ki- 1	Self	
County governments and collaborative partners to promote fish farming (aquaculture) to increase production and consumption of fish. The farming can be done for example, at nyumba kumi level, women's group, men's groups etc.	FL-5	Relevant stakeholders e.g. MoA, MoE	

	No of Recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
County governments and collaborative partners to encourage increased production and consumption of ruminants and poultry; rabbits, chicken, quails, duck, turkey, guinea fowls (For rabbits- recommend the type that is kept in hutches)			
County governments to facilitate increased production and consumption of pigs and other large animals: cattle, goats			
County governments to promote increased consumption of mulberry fruit and leaves in the country			
County governments to promote growing and consumption of nutrient dense crops such as quinoa			

	No of Recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
<p>Technology-based</p> <p>Farmers to use novel precise fruit harvesting systems- FoodLAND developed precision mango harvesting tool.</p>	FL-1	Farmers	
<p>Manufacturers to engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND; cold storage, solar driers, mango harvesting tool and bio-based packaging materials</p>	FL-1	Industry/Manufacturers	
<p>Social media platforms to social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND</p>	FL-1	Media	

C) FACILITATIVE NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

	No of Recommendations	Stakeholder responsible for implementing	Comments
Build capacity on production of yogurt and mala	FL-1		
Promote increased uptake of existing mobile step tracking applications through creating awareness of the existing mobile step-tracking applications leading to practice.	FL-1		
Local authorities to provide playgrounds for children	FL-1		
Policy makers and regulators to develop policies, regulations and legislate; to support uptake and scaling up of the novel technologies.	FL-1		
Media to promote age-specific iron supplementation for children 0 to<5 years	FL-1		
Collaboration at multisector level	Ny-1		

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3 CHAPTER THREE: REPORT ON NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MOROCCO

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Summary

The nutritional situation of the Moroccan population has significantly improved in recent years due to several factors, including the country's economic development and government efforts through the national nutrition strategy coordinated by the Ministry of Health. However, the country still faces several nutritional challenges, including: malnutrition affecting part of the population, especially children; an increase in obesity, particularly in urban areas and among women, due to changes in dietary habits, sedentary lifestyles, and lack of physical activity; micronutrient deficiencies (iron, vitamin A, iodine, etc.); limited access to healthy and diverse food in rural areas due to isolation and transportation and logistics costs; and changes in dietary habits, particularly in urban areas, with the adoption of diets high in sugars and fats and increased preference for prepared and ultra-processed meals, to the detriment of more balanced traditional foods, largely due to the lack of appropriate nutritional education from a young age. All of these challenges require targeted interventions to improve population health indicators related to nutrition and to enable sustainable and effective economic development.

However, in Morocco, it should be noted that important related factors need to be taken into account, such as levels of physical activity, particularly for women, access to education and the labor market, the availability of healthcare, proximity to public services, the quality of infrastructure, water supply and the level of socio-economic development in the different regions, all of which can strongly influence the quality and diversity of the diet.

In Morocco, FoodLAND has conducted surveys in two major areas of the country (Food Hubs): the city of Meknes (urban) and the Beni Mellal region (both urban and rural). The main objective is to formulate practical and operational nutritional recommendations for each population group and lifecycle stage. These recommendations are based on a detailed review of existing scientific literature and the results of surveys conducted with urban and rural consumers (couples with women and children). The recommendations have been discussed and validated by stakeholders in the two concerned Food Hubs, which include consumer associations and project partners related to the field of nutrition. The recommendations are organized by lifecycle stage, intervention scale (regional or national), and type (prevention or remedy).

These nutritional recommendations emphasize health promotion and disease prevention, paying particular attention to vulnerable segments of the population such as children under 24 months (before weaning) and women of childbearing age and breastfeeding (16 to 49 years).

In this report, recommendations related to improving the quality of nutrition and diet, both in qualitative and quantitative terms, have been proposed with a view to boosting the protective effects through the use of a variety of Foods and nutrients in accordance with local eating habits.

These recommendations are, however, not exhaustive and complete in relation to the complexity and diversity of diets and socio-economic situations and therefore cannot be extended and applied to all situations without adaptation and contextualization.

3.1 Introduction

Historically and before the introduction of so-called modern consumption models initiated by European colonialism at the beginning of the 20th century, Morocco had less than 4 million inhabitants and was a rural country par excellence with 95% of the population living in rural areas. and relying on traditional agriculture. Agricultural production, in relation to living conditions and the aridity of the climate, was essentially made up of durum wheat, barley, fresh and dried vegetables, olive and argan oils and some typical fruits (almonds, grapes, grenadines, figs, dates, etc.).

Food products of animal origin were only consumed occasionally on major holidays and family and religious occasions, the quantities and frequencies of which essentially depend on the socio-economic level of the families. The diet was therefore essentially based on local products with regional variations linked to production potential and production and consumption habits in each region.

The Moroccan diet is mainly Mediterranean. It is a diet characterized by the consumption of cereals, legumes, fruits and vegetables. Cereals are the main food source of energy, they constituted more than 60% of the total energy intake. (FAO, 2011).

From a consumption model point of view, Moroccan cuisine is very diversified with a wide range of culinary recipes in relation to the availability of food products from each region. It is also influenced by the different neighboring regions (Africa, Western Europe, India, etc.), which explains the diversity of culinary practices in Morocco (SAM, 2014).

Indeed, Morocco is characterized by a great diversity of cooking preparations and dishes, the results of the diversity of local products and in relation to the preparation and cooking methods (FAO, 2011). Indeed, in the plains, wheat is the main cereal food while the inhabitants of the mountains prefer barley. In the north, olive oil is the most consumed oil while argan oil is widely consumed in the south. Rural residents often consumed barley or bean soup, as in the Jebala region in northern Morocco, while in the cities, harrira (soup made from flour and fresh vegetables) is a traditional standard.

However, several dishes are common between the different regions of the country, in particular, couscous, the method of preparation of which presents a regional particularity (Houbbaida & Monkachi, 2006).

From the 20th century, profound changes occurred in the eating habits of Moroccans under the influence of colonization after the Treaty of the Protectorate (1912), but also because of profound changes in the economy and significant changes in land use patterns (land privatization, agricultural mechanization, agro-food industries and specialization). The improvement in conditions of commerce and exchange, the increase in population and urbanization have induced a great nutritional differentiation in the urban environment compared to the rural ones, thus adopting a diet based essentially on the consumption model European associated with a relative abundance of food and the purchase of products in the market, especially in large urban areas. Rural regions, especially in the mountains and isolated areas, have been less influenced by these changes (Houbaida, 2008).

In this context, agricultural development policies well before independence aimed to strengthen the modern and intensive agricultural sector, thus contributing to the expansion of cash crops and the agri-food industry. This model of agricultural development was designed in the direction of improving production and valorization of available resources (water and land) without relation to the reduction of

local agro-biodiversity and essentially concerned the introduction of species and varieties of agricultural products in different environments in order to make investments profitable.

These agricultural policies have strongly influenced diets in Morocco, which have undergone numerous changes following changes in food availability and food prices. The socio-economic and technological development of the country, the improvement in income and the conditions of access to food products including through the market have induced a profound change in household preferences and significant modifications in dietary profiles.

This has also been strongly accentuated by the development of food marketing and the encouragement of the media for the consumption of commercial food products regardless of their quality and nutritional value (MoH, 2011).

Currently, this nutritional transition, which affects both rural and urban areas, is manifested in the food preferences of Moroccan households through the increase in the consumption of products of animal origin and preserves rather than fresh products of plant origin (vegetables and fruits) and a trend towards an increase in fast foods rich in saturated fats and carbohydrates whose nutritional benefit remains very limited (especially in urban areas).

Despite these dietary changes perceptible in Morocco over several decades, cereals still have a remarkable dominance in the diet. We essentially note that soft wheat has gradually replaced durum wheat and barley and mainly for the preparation of bread (not only because of its price). Eating bread is a habit for each meal as an accompaniment to the basic dish which presents a wide diversification (tagines of different types, stews with vegetables and/or legumes with or without meat, couscous, etc.). Today, couscous is less frequently consumed while pasta has become increasingly consumed (FAO, 2011).

Morocco is characterized by the significant weight of agriculture in the economy, but also by the great diversity of its biosphere. The active rural population represents 52% of the country's active population (LESECO., 2020). The contribution of the agricultural sector to wealth creation remains relatively significant and is around 14% of GDP. However, this contribution presents high volatility due to the sector's dependence on climatic conditions. Likewise, the sector has low productivity and agricultural production which is generally very poorly valued (processing, labeling and marketing).

In Morocco, food security does not really arise in terms of availability for consumers but in terms of accessibility. The food market is well supplied with raw and processed food products and is not subject to particular restrictions on import quantities (quotas and customs barriers). The challenges of accessibility arise specifically in terms of the health and nutritional quality of products and the distribution of added value between the actors of the food distribution systems (FDS). In particular, we note a very high elasticity of demand in relation to prices and income brackets for most food products (high diversity and substitutability) except for basic products which are essentially cereals and legumes.

Food distribution systems are undergoing profound transformations under the combined effects of five main factors:

- The growth of cities and the urbanization of the population;
- The emergence of a middle class;
- The development of the tertiary sector and supply services;
- The emergence of new retail sales methods.

In this sense, Moroccan consumers are mainly supplied by retail markets (for a wide range of products), as well as neighborhood shops, price, proximity, trust in the supplier being the essential factors of choice of supply locations.

Supermarkets play a marginal but increasingly important role in household supplies, especially for the middle and wealthy classes. We are also witnessing an increasingly clear separation between circuits dominated by large-scale distribution, intended for the wealthiest population categories and capable of obtaining supplies for a long period of time, and local circuits intended mainly for popular layers where purchases are made according to the needs and circumstances of each day and according to budgetary availability. In these local businesses, purchasing practices on credit in small quantities are more common.

The richest neighborhoods are supplied mainly by large retailers, but part of their population also often travels to markets and souks to purchase fresh and seasonal products (fruit, vegetables, fresh meat and fish) which offer more fresh local products, more possibilities for price negotiation and more human friendliness.

3.2 General overview of the current nutrition situation

Health and nutrition are very important factors in human development. Morocco is classified in the category of lower middle-income countries, between 1,006 and 3,955 dollars per capita (WB, 2022) it has hardly moved from this category since 2008 with a GDP per capita in 2022 of order of \$3,527.9/inhabitant. and is currently ranked 121st among 189 countries and territories (UNDP, 2020) with a score of 0.686.

However, the relative poverty rate (proportion of individuals whose average annual expenditure is below 14,667.74 Dhs/inhabitant/year, or \$1,445) recorded a decline between 2001 and 2019, since it passed from 20.4% to 17.7% but still remains at a relatively high level, especially in rural areas where it reached 36.8% in 2019 (ONDH, 2021). This can lead to long-term malnutrition, growth retardation, chronic non-communicable disorders linked to dietary deficits, increased morbidity and mortality and reduced physical performance. It presents a great economic loss for the country and can compromise all economic and social development strategies.

Protein-energy malnutrition (PEM), micronutrient deficiencies such as iron anemia (IAF), iodine deficiency disorders (IDD) and vitamin D deficiencies are commonly encountered nutritional problems, particularly in children in poor rural communities and poor urban neighborhoods.

Due to maternal undernutrition (underweight, low weight gain during pregnancy, nutritional anemia and vitamin deficiencies), 14.2% have growth retardation (moderate or severe). Stunting is linked to a number of long-term factors including insufficient protein-energy intake, frequent infections, long-term inadequate feeding practices and poverty. According to the Minister of Health (PNN, 2019), 3.1% are underweight (4.4% in rural areas compared to 2.1% in urban areas).

Regarding the prevalence of micronutrient deficiencies among women of childbearing age, the same source indicates that 34.4% have anemia, 30.3% have iron deficiency, 11.7% have folic acid deficiency and 31.3% have a vitamin D deficiency.

Regarding dietary diversity, we note that among children aged 6 to 59 months, 40.5% have low dietary diversity. Dairy products and starchy foods remain the most common food groups for at least 50% of this category of the population. The distribution according to area of residence shows that the diet of children from urban areas is more diversified. In fact, 65.8% of these children consume more than 4 different food groups compared to 54.5% in rural areas. Overall, the consumption of starchy foods and fruits and

vegetables remains the majority among this age group. Whereas milk and derivatives are more consumed in urban areas.

Analysis of individual dietary diversity scores (DSS) among women of childbearing age showed that 41% have a very undiversified diet with less than 4 food groups consumed. Fruits and vegetables, starchy foods and fruits and vegetables rich in vitamin A constitute the food groups most consumed by at least 50% of these women. The statistical analysis showed a significant difference between urban and rural areas with a more pronounced dietary diversity in the urban areas in relation to the standard of living of the population which helps with dietary diversification.

Morocco is a country in a phase of economic transition, the problem of malnutrition is becoming less and less important, on the other hand obesity and malnutrition are gaining ground and are progressing more quickly in urban areas than in rural areas. The main indicators at the national level show 28.4% of Moroccan women are obese (PNN, 2019). This rate is higher in urban than rural areas with 32% and 21.8% respectively. Among the factors involved are junk food, malnutrition, a sedentary lifestyle, lack of sporting activity and changes in eating habits (snacks, fast foods, etc.).

Among children aged 6 to 12, the body mass index (BMI) shows that 18.4% of children are overweight, including 5.4% who are obese. The comparison between urban and rural areas does not show any significant difference in terms of wasting and overweight. However, stunting is more accentuated in rural areas and obesity is more pronounced in urban areas with statistically significant differences.

3.3 Eating habits and nutritional problems

Morocco is a country in the midst of a nutritional transition which is accompanied by various changes and consequences in terms of dietary habits, the overall health of the population and the epidemiological profile. Thus, the different forms of malnutrition increasingly constitute a real problem that threatens the health of the Moroccan population, particularly women of childbearing age and children under the age of 5 (PNN, 2019).

It should be noted that nutritional disorders do not only result from food insecurity since children living in good conditions are subject to deficiency anemia, underweight or overweight or even stunted growth. This observation would be linked to the appearance of poor feeding practices, inadequate care, poor hygiene conditions and inaccessibility to health services (MoH, 2011).

Furthermore, the lack of information among the population, particularly regarding the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding and appropriate complementary feeding practices, as well as the role of micronutrients in improving nutritional status are all risk factors that affect nutritional status since childhood.

1- Consequences on eating habits

The analysis of food and nutritional developments in Morocco has had a set of consequences on eating habits, namely:

- Maintaining very high consumption of cereal products;
- Excessive consumption of animal products;
- Excessive consumption of lipids, mainly invisible and saturated lipids;

- The overall increase in energy intake;
- The significant intake of fruits and vegetables but which still remains below the intake recommended by international recommendations;
- Insufficient intake of dietary fiber;
- Carbohydrate intake based on the remarkable consumption of simple sugars to the detriment of complex sugars;
- The relatively diversified contribution of foods in the daily ration;
- The diversified distribution of different macronutrients in meeting energy needs (MoH, 2011).

2- Health consequences

The epidemiological transition associated with changes in the dietary behaviors of Moroccans is characterized by the increase in the rate of non-communicable diseases (Popkin, 2002, Maazouzi et al., 2005; MoH, 2008). Indeed, variations in lifestyle coupled with changes in eating habits, in particular excessive consumption of fatty substances, sugary products and restaurant meals could present a real additional risk factor for the development of hypertension, obesity, diabetes, dyslipidemia, cardiovascular diseases and even certain cancers (Benjelloun, 2002, FAO, 2011, Popkin, 2002).

Indeed, the National Population and Family Health Survey (ENPSF) of 2011 revealed that a proportion of 18.2% of Moroccans present chronic diseases, compared to a prevalence of 13.8% reported in 2004 (MoH, 2011; DE, 2008).

2.1 Overweight and obesity

The prevalence of overweight and obesity has seen significant developments in recent decades in Morocco. This is one of the main results of changing eating habits characterized by a tendency towards an imbalance in energy balance and unhealthy nutrition.

Data from the 2000 study (Tazi et al., 2003; MP, 2000) and the Ministry of Health survey (MoH, 2018) show a very remarkable increase in obesity among the Moroccan population, i.e. 13.2% of Moroccans in 2000 compared to 20% in 2017.

2.2 Diabetes

Diabetes also presents an alarming consequence of the nutritional transition in Morocco following the excess consumption of sweet products and the Moroccan tendency towards the heavy use of white flour, rich in starch. The prevalence of diabetes increased from 6.6% of diabetics in 2000 (18% among subjects aged between 50 and 60) to a proportion of 10.4% in 2017, mainly affecting women and elderly people in age groups 18 -29 years to 60-69 years (Tazi et al., 2003; MoH, 2019).

2.3 High blood pressure

High blood pressure is also a metabolic risk factor that affects a large proportion of the Moroccan population resulting from a dietary imbalance based on fast food whose salt level used exceeds WHO recommendations. Thus, existing data show that 33.6% of Moroccans aged 20 and over have high blood pressure (Tazi et al., 2003) with a significant increase between 2015 and 2017 in approximately 46.3% of surveys who declared taking medication. against hypertension (El Ghazi, 2010; MoH, 2018).

2.4 Micronutrient deficiencies

Another result of changes in eating habits is the deficiency of a certain number of micronutrients which generates complications on the health of the population depending on sex, age and also according to the medical history of each person.

Thus, the latest surveys carried out by the MoH and studies carried out at the national level have shown that:

- Iron deficiency was detected in 37.2% of pregnant women, 31.5% of children aged 6 months to 5 years, 32.6% of women of childbearing age (MoH, 2000). This has also been confirmed by previous studies on the increase in deficiency especially in children (El Hamdouchi et al., 2010).
- Iodine deficiency is around 63% among children aged 6 to 12, with disparities between regions (MoH/UNICEF, 2001a; MoH/UNICEF, 2001b).
- For vitamin D, 2.5% of children developed radiological rickets due to a lack of vitamin D (DSMI, 1992). A recent study showed that 47.5% of children have vitamin D insufficiency (Benjeddou et al., 2018) and that the entire population is affected by this insufficiency (Lamghari, 2018).

Other micronutrient deficiencies are also common among Moroccans, namely folic acid, zinc and calcium deficiency, which have a major impact on the health of the population (Allali, 2017; Bouziani et al., 2018).

3.4 Objectives

Overall Objective: To propose relevant, adapted, flexible and achievable nutritional recommendations in the two Food Hubs studied in Morocco (Meknes and Beni Mellal).

Specific Objectives:

- (i) To establish the situational architecture to inform nutritional recommendations
- (ii) To develop nutritional recommendations based on the food consumption habits and nutrient gaps in the Food hubs
- (iii) To document the protocols used in the development of the nutritional recommendations

3.5 Protocol for nutritional recommendations

The process of formulating dietary recommendations and specific guidelines was divided into several stages detailed below:

- Carrying out a systematic review of the literature in order to identify problems of imbalance and insufficient consumption of foods or nutrients based on previous scientific studies and research; (Literature review -Deliverable D 2.5).
- Analysis of data from the project with a view to determining the consumption profiles of the target groups (900 urban and 500 rural consumers in the two Food Hubs). A total of 1412 surveys

were conducted in the regions of Meknes and Beni Mellal and concerned 900 urban consumers of different sexes over 18 years old with a view to identifying household profiles with regard to supply, consumption food and the quality of nutrition (500 in Meknes and 400 in Beni Mellal) and 512 surveys of women of childbearing age in rural areas (15 to 49 years) with a child aged 6 to 23 months (Beni Mellal).

- The presentation of nutritional and dietary recommendations resulting from research work and studies carried out on a national scale, such as periodic reports and summary documents from the Ministry of Health on the state of food and nutrition in Morocco (ENPSF, PNN). The recommendations proposed by these studies and research are thus linked, compared with the specific results obtained through the surveys carried out and contextualized to the specific specificities of the areas studied;

With a view to further refining the nutritional and dietary recommendations intended for the local populations studied and local and regional partners such as farmer cooperatives, consumer associations, health service stakeholders, local development services and representatives of different communities, were asked to provide their contributions to further clarify the proposed recommendations and discuss the modalities of their adoption and dissemination to the target groups concerned (appropriation).

3.6 Situational architecture

Foodland (Food and Local, Agricultural and Nutritional Diversity) project aims to develop, implement and validate innovative, scalable and sustainable technologies. The technologies aim at supporting the nutrition performance of local food systems in Africa, while strengthening agro-biodiversity, food diversity and diversity of healthy diets. In Morocco, the project is implemented in two regions.

The nutritional transition has been well documented in several developing countries, several published studies confirm the link between the nutritional transition and the emergence of chronic diseases including obesity (Popkin, 2001). In Morocco, this transition is marked by:

- Food is gradually diversifying, especially for urban households and the wealthier classes. It includes more foods rich in micronutrients,
- Consumption of animal origin products remains very limited whereas the resources of the country, particularly in fish, are very important.
- Fast food become more prevalent in urban areas, encouraging the consumption of foods rich in sugar and fat.
- Coupled with a reduction in physical activity, these changes lead to the progression of overweight and obesity in the adult population.

3.7 Description of study areas

3.7.1 Rural consumers' profile

The first study area, in Beni Mellal region (rural area), concerns the northern piedmont of transition between the morphologies of plain and mountain. The foothills or Dir¹, is a place of fruit trees and olive

¹ Dir: means "belt". On the slopes of the High Atlas, this term refers to an area of low and medium hills and alluvial cones that operate the transition between the high limestone mountain and the plain. The soils are relatively rich. Karstic springs with

forests that cling to the low slopes and spread into the plain. It is characterized by a permanent greenness explained essentially by the abundance of water and the fertility of the soil. One of the characteristics of the piedmont is the presence of a transition zone between the Atlas and the plain of Tadla. It is an inclined plane of accumulation of a few kilometers wide, consisting of the coalescence of alluvial cones supported on the detrital formations mio-pliocene that form the bedrock of the plain.

The Dir, especially developed north of Beni Mellal, receives water from the Atlas either through springs, or through the effusion of the Jurassic water table under the alluvium. We can distinguish two piedmonts:

- The Northern piedmont: is located in the province of Beni Mellal. It extends between Tisqui and Zaouïa Cheikh and benefits from abundant rainfall and is the subject of our investigation.
- The southern piedmont is located in the province of Azilal. It benefits from a significant rainfall but less than that of the northern piedmont.

The specific objectives of this research on rural consumers were to assess the situation of children and women of childbearing age (16-49) on the basis of a standardized questionnaire for all the African partner countries. The list included indicators to assess market dependency for food products, food choices and habits, including the quality of local diets, information on household social profiles and issues related to empowerment, community participation and the role of women in decision-making.

The study was conducted in the rural area in 3 rural communes of the High Atlas foothills. The sample size consisted of rural women with a child under 24 months of age, aged between 15 and 49 years. Data on food quality, availability and supply networks were recorded using a web application developed as part of the FoodLAND project, and were used to verify the information provided on a consolidated basis and to validate data quality at national level. In addition to socio-demographic data, the survey collected data on all aspects related to quality of life, empowerment and the perceived role of women in the community.

The analysis of the region's demographic context, based on 2014 data (RGPH, 2014), indicates that the region's population would increase from 2.5 million in 2014 to 2.7 million in 2030, representing an overall growth rate of 8%. The average annual growth rate would be 0.52%, meaning that 13,700 additional inhabitants would be added to the population on average each year. In terms of demographic weight, the Beni Mellal Khénifra region, which accounted for 7.5% of Morocco's total population in 2014, would see its weight decrease slightly to almost 7% in 2030.

regular and abundant flow gush out there. The space is judiciously distributed between small perimeters irrigated by a traditional system of seguias (orchards and intensive horticulture), non-irrigated fields, wooded areas and rangelands.

Figure 3.3 Location map of the rural area studied (woman-child couple)

3.7.2 Urban consumers' profile

Field survey work in the cities of Meknes and Beni Mellal (prefectures) between February and March 2022 with the introduction of data on dedicated platforms (Otree and application developed by ENAM).

Meknes	500	In-lab Experiments and Survey
Beni Mellal	400	Households / out-of-store Survey

Meknes Prefecture:

Spanning an area of 1,786 km², the prefecture of Meknes is a predominantly urban subdivision (82.3% of the population resides in urban areas compared to 17.7% in rural areas). It occupies a strategic geographical position because on the one hand, it is located between two sets of mountains: The Pre-Rif and the Western Middle Atlas and on the other hand, thanks to the positioning of the city of Meknes, at the crossing of major arteries of communication between the block of large Atlantic cities (Casablanca, Rabat, etc.) and the provinces located in the center and the east (Fez, Oujda, Marrakech, Beni Mellal, etc.). It is crossed by the main highway and the railway lines (East – West).

In terms of administrative organization, the provincial territory is divided into 21 municipalities including 15 rural municipalities. Demographically, the legal population reached 835,695 inhabitants in 2014

compared to 715,285 in 2004. Thus, it recorded an average annual growth rate of 1.6% for the period 2004-2014. This rate is higher than that recorded at regional (0.9%) and national (1.3%) levels.

According to the 2014 general population and housing census (RGPH, 2014), the share of the urban population (concerned by our survey) of the prefecture of Meknes (82.3%) far exceeds that of the rural population (17.7%).

As for the age structure of the population, 58.2% of the inhabitants are aged under 35 and the population aged 15-59 represents 64% of the population of the province, which implies significant potential in terms of activity and labor force.

In terms of employment, the activity rate of the prefectural population reached 45.0% in 2014, an increase of 2.2 points compared to 2013 (HCP, 2018). Note that this activity rate is lower than that recorded at the national level (48%).

Beni Mellal Prefecture:

Beni Mellal is a city located between the Middle Atlas and the Tadla plain, in the center of Morocco and on the road axis of the imperial cities Fez and Marrakech, it is open to southern Morocco via the provinces of Er-Rachidia to the East, Khenifra to the North-East and Ouarzazate to the South-West. The city had 163,248 inhabitants in 2004 (34,959 households) and 192,676 in 2014, an increase of around 1.8% in the city's population due in part to the importance of the rural exodus in the region. It is one of the most important cities in central Morocco, which has recently developed thanks to the income of emigrants (Italy, Spain). Its Bel Koush kasbah, built in the 17th century.

As for the age structure of the population, 31% of the population is under the age of 15 and the population aged 15-59 represents 61% of the population, which implies significant potential in terms of activity and Workforce.

In terms of education, we note an illiteracy rate of around 48% and a population activity rate of around 33.6 in 2014, much lower than that recorded at the national level (48%).

Figure 3.4 Location map of the cities of Meknes and Beni Mellal (Urban consumers)

3.8 FoodLAND findings

3.8.1 Rural consumers profile: women of childbearing age (16-49 years)

Food Group Diversity Score: FGDS (10 food groups)

For a maximum score of 10 points, the FGDS is around 4.70 for all rural women (484 respondents) with a standard deviation of around 1.63 points. This score is lower recorded at the urban population level by 1.5 points (6.18). This can be explained by the low availability of diversified food products in rural areas in relation to market integration and income levels in rural areas.

Figure 5.3 FGDS average values by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

The analysis of the relationship between the levels of dietary diversity through the FGD scores with the different socio-economic variables studied (share of income spent on food, number of children, age group of the woman and her level education) shows that there is no effect of all of these variables on the performance of women of childbearing age in the region studied (Kruskal Wallis test).

Table 3.1 Tests for differences in FGDS in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	0.086	2	0.958	

Variable	Test	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
n. Children	Kruskal Wallis test	3.115	2	0.211	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	2.603	2	0.272	
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	5.808	4	0.214	

Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women of Reproductive Age (MDD-W)

For all rural women who participated in the survey, the score relating to dietary diversity for women of childbearing age was calculated on a sample of 484 women. The average score is 56.6% compared to 43.4% of women who cannot meet the minimum dietary diversity. This score is lower than that recorded for the same profile of women residing in urban areas (Beni Mellal and Meknes), i.e. 83.3% in urban areas compared to 56.6% in rural areas, i.e. 27 points loss. This difference marks a significant gap in dietary diversity among women between 16 and 49 years old between rural and urban areas. and presents a very high risk linked to dietary diversity with all the consequences that this has on the health of the child. and women in rural areas.

Figure 3.6 MDD-W by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

The analysis of the relationship between the levels of dietary diversity across MDD-W with the different socio-economic variables studied shows no connection of these variables with the performance levels of women of childbearing age in the region studied in relation to minimal dietary diversity (Chi-square test).

Table 3.1 Chi-squared test on relationship between MDD-W in the following variables

Variable	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Age	0.24	2	0.	
n. Children	1.08	2	0.5832	
Education	0.28	2	0.8701	
Income for food	5.72	4	0.2207	

ALL5

ALL5 expresses the consumption of the 5 food groups during the past day and night, i.e. at least one vegetable, at least one fruit, at least one legume, one nut or seed, at least one food of animal origin (ASF) and at least one starchy food.

The results obtained for the rural women surveyed show very low and even alarming scores regarding the diversity of food in rural areas and also confirm the scores of the two previous indicators, namely FGDS and MDD-W. Thus, only 12.6% of women of childbearing age with a child of breastfeeding age (6 to 24 months) meet the daily consumption criterion of the 5 recommended food groups.

The comparison with the results obtained in an urban environment in the town of Beni Mellal (the closest to the survey locations of the women-child couples surveyed), shows a difference of around 20% between the two environments, or 30.4% in town compared to 12.6% in rural areas of the same region.

This rate is the lowest among the 5 countries concerned by the FoodLAND project and shows that the problem of nutritional diversity is acute in Morocco, especially in rural areas where accessibility to diversified food products is low, not only because low purchasing power but also lack of availability. Eating habits also play a role in this deficit in dietary diversity due to the use of local food products, which are often not very diversified.

Figure 3.7 ALL5 by urban and rural area in Beni Mellal region

The analysis of the relationship between the levels of dietary diversity with the different socio-economic variables studied shows no connection of these variables with the performance levels of women of

childbearing age in the region studied in relation to the minimum dietary diversity expressed through the ALL5 indicator. This implies the difficulties of understanding the determinants of food diversity in rural areas in general in comparison with urban areas where the effect of self-consumed agricultural production can bias food availability and make it difficult to measure through socio-economic variables. economic such as the share of income reserved for the purchase of food.

Noncommunicable Diseases Score

NCD-Protect score

The NCD-Protect score reflects adherence to dietary recommendations on healthy components of the diet, it is based on dietary consumption of 9 healthy food groups over the past day and night.

The average NCD-Protect value for the entire population sample is 3.01 out of a maximum score of 9. This implies low dietary diversification among women of childbearing age. The town of Beni Mellal neighboring the survey area presents a higher score of around 0.3 points compared to the rural area studied.

This is explained by the same reasons mentioned above, namely the low diversity of food products available in rural areas and the low income which does not allow better accessibility to food products. Poverty can also be one of the causes of low scores obtained.

Figure 3.8 NCD-Protect average value by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

The statistical analysis confirms the statistically significant relationship between the level of income spent on food at the 5% threshold and the NCD-Protect score obtained. The results obtained show that

households whose income is mainly spent on food (+75%) have higher protection in relation to NCDs than households which spend less than 50% of their income on food.

Table 2.3 Tests for differences in NCD-Protect in the following variables

Variable	Test	Statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Gender	Kruskal Wallis test	0.829	2	0.661	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	2.714	2	0.257	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	1.615	2	0.448	
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	10.962	4	0.027	*

NCD-Risk score

The NCD-Risk score reflects adherence to dietary recommendations on diet components to limit or avoid (the processed meat food group is doubly weighted).

The results obtained show a very low score of 0.68 with a standard deviation of 1.10. This implies a very low prevalence for young women regarding the consumption of foods that pose a health risk. Residents of rural areas very rarely eat processed meats, sugary soft drinks and salty meals from fast food because of the very nature of the rural environment which constitutes a constraint on their availability (low economic interest due to the size of the market). Also, certainly the low purchasing power of rural communities implies very low consumption of processed products (drinks and canned or processed products).

It should be noted that the increase in income levels spent on food (+75%) favors the increase in the NCD-Risk score for rural women.

Table 3.3 Tests for differences in NCD-Risk in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Gender	Kruskal Wallis test	.1.532	2	0.465	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	0.864	2	0.649	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	0.957	2	0.652	
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	12.711	4	0.013	*

Global Dietary Recommendations (GDR)

Analysis of the results obtained shows that the score is around 11.33 for the entire population of women surveyed compared to 10.62 obtained in urban areas for the cities of Meknes and Beni Mellal. Overall, this score shows that the population's diet makes it possible to meet at least part of the recommended dietary recommendations.

Figure 3.9 GDR score average by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

We always notice that all the socio-economic variables (age, number of children and level of education) do not have a significant relationship with the scores obtained. Only the share of income from food explains at the 5% threshold the variations in the NCD and GDR scores. The increase in the share of income spent on food contributes positively to the GDR and to the increase in NCD-Protect but also in NCD-Risk.

Table 3.4 Tests for differences in GDR in the following variables

Variable	Test	Statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Gender	Kruskal Wallis test	.1.997	2	0.370	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	2.183	2	0.336	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	0.104	2	0.949	
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	12.793	4	0.029	*

Others DQQ Diet Quality indicators

Figure 3.10 Others DQQ Diet Quality Indicators

The 3 food groups that are consumed the least are prepared meats and sweetened soft drinks and salty or fried snacks (more than 90% of respondents do not generally consume these products) which do not lead to improvement of the quality of the diet. On the other hand, there is a shortage in two food groups, namely nuts and seeds and legumes. This profile resembles some differences with the profile of urban consumers, especially regarding the low consumption of the last two groups.

It is important to note that 93% of respondents reported eating animal products and fruits and vegetables in the last 24 hours. This corresponds well to the typical Mediterranean diet with meals based on meat and vegetables (Tajines and stews, etc.) and a dessert generally made up of seasonal fruits.

Table 3.5 Chi-squared Test on relationship significance between DQQ food groups and following variables

DQQ Food group	Age	n. Children	Education	Income for food
Vegetables of fruits	-	-	-	-
Animal source food	-	-	-	-
Sweet beverage	-	-	-	-
Sugar sweetened soft drink	*** ↓	-	-	-
Sweet foods	* ↓	-	-	-
Salty or fried snack	-	-	* ↑	-

DQQ Food group	Age	n. Children	Education	Income for food
Whole grain	-	-	-	** ↑
Pulse	-	-	-	** ↓
Nuts and seeds	-	-	-	-
Processed meat	-	-	-	-

3.8.2 Rural consumers profile: children between 6 and 24 months

The analysis of the quality of food and its diversification for children between 6 to 24 months was carried out by referring to the profile of mothers (age, number of children, level of education and the importance of income dedicated to food).

Dietary diversity plays an important role in children's physical and mental growth and development. However, meeting the minimum standards of dietary diversity for children poses a huge challenge, given the specificities of managing the diversification of children's diets during the breastfeeding period (6 to 24 months).

The evaluation of dietary diversity and associated factors for children (6-23 months) in rural areas of the Beni Mellal region was carried out by surveys with women of childbearing age (16-49 years) with a dependent child aged 6-24 months, i.e. a total of 512 children with a response rate of 100%.

Food group diversity score (FGD-C)

The average dietary diversity score for children is around 3.66 out of a maximum score of 10. Which implies that less than 4 groups out of 10 are consumed by children aged 6 to 24 months in the region. This may seem quite low, but it must be considered in relation to the age of the children because the diversification of children's diets must be done gradually over the period.

The variables age of the mother, her level of education and the income spent on household food do not appear to have any relationship with the dietary diversity of young children within the meaning of the FGD-C indicator.

On the other hand, the level of education of mothers appears to have a statically significant relationship with the dietary diversity of children. Mothers with higher education are abler to provide a diet of minimum recommended diversity (FGD = 5) to their children than those with a primary education level or less (FDG = 3.72). This can be explained by the fact that women with higher education are more likely to obtain or have information on the nutritional needs of children and to understand the educational messages available. Therefore, the higher the level of education, the more the level of diversification of children's diet is significantly likely to improve (KW test = 8.022, p-value = 0.018)

Figure 3.11 FGDS for children by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Table 3.6 Tests for differences in FGD-C in the following variables

Variable	Test	Statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Gender	Kruskal Wallis test	.0934	2	0.627	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	0.967	2	0.610	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	8.022	2	0.018	*
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	6.565	4	0.161	

NCD-Protect score

The NCD-Protect score reflects adherence to dietary recommendations on healthy components of the diet, it is based on dietary consumption of 9 healthy food groups over the past day and night.

The average NCD-Protect value for all children is 2.05 compared to 3.01 for their mothers out of a maximum score of 9. This implies low dietary diversification among children aged 6 to 24 months, certainly in relation to that of their mothers. This is explained by the same reasons mentioned above, namely the low diversity of food products available in rural areas and the low income which does not allow better accessibility to food products. Poverty can also be one of the causes of low scores obtained.

Concerning the NCD-Risk, the results obtained show a very low score of 0.42 with a standard deviation of 0.86. This implies a very low prevalence among children for consuming health-risk foods. Due to the lack of diversity in the diet before the age of two, we should expect this low rate in relation to that of mothers, which does not exceed 0.68.

It should be noted that the increase in mothers' education levels (higher or other) favors a significant increase in the NCD-Protect score of young children, this confirms the role of mothers' education in diversification. food and improving the quality of the family's diet in general, including for children aged 6 to 24 months. For the NCD-Risk, we note that none of the variables selected explain the variables of the scores obtained.

Figure 3.12 NCD-Protect and NCD-Risk for children by age, n. of children, education and income for food

Table 3.7 Tests for differences in NCD-Protect in the following variables

Variable	Test	Statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Gender	Kruskal Wallis test	.0580	2	0.758	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	1.101	2	0.577	
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	8.166	2	0.017	*
Income for food	Kruskal Wallis test	7.423	4	0.115	

Global Dietary Recommendations (GDR)

Analysis of the results obtained shows that the score is around 10.63 for the entire population of children compared to 11.33 obtained by the women surveyed. Overall, this score shows that the population's diet makes it possible to meet at least part of the recommended dietary recommendations, i.e. always a score greater than 10.

Figure 3.13 GDRS children by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Others DQQ Diet Quality Indicators

The quality of the diet calculated from the ten standard food groups shows that approximately 84% of the children received fruits and vegetables (semi-solid foods) during the previous day. The majority, more than 90% of mothers declared that their children had not consumed risky foods based on (prepared meats, sweet soft drinks, prepared salty meals) and more than 10% of women said they had prepared meals for their children based on cereal grains, roots and tubers, during the reference period.

Only a quarter (7%) received legume-based foods. When it came to animal foods, more than half (76%) received dairy and milk products excluding breast milk.

The overall quality of the diet of children in the region reflects low diversity, possibly in relation to the age of the children and confirms the low use of foods based on cereals, legumes and seeds for young children.

Figure 3.14 Others DQQ Diet Quality Indicators for children

Breastfeeding

Ever Breastfed (EvBF)

Breastfeeding plays an irreplaceable role in the survival, nutrition and physical and mental development of the child. Generally, traditional social behaviors favor breastfeeding and support its maintenance until the age of 24 months.

The results show almost 90% of the women surveyed practice breastfeeding for their children and that this rate is higher among young women in the 16-25 age group. This is higher than that presented in the national results concerning the practice of exclusive breastfeeding (63% in rural areas) which has clearly improved compared to the early 2000s.

Figure 3.15 Ever Breastfed (EvBF) by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Early initiation of breastfeeding (EIBF)

Early initiation of breastfeeding (EIB) is defined as “the provision of breast milk to infants within one hour of birth and ensures that the newborn receives colostrum. The results obtained show that, out of 512 postnatal mothers, 358 (69.9%) started breastfeeding within an hour after delivery. Mothers with more than one child appear more willing to breastfeed their babies in the first hour after delivery due, possibly, to the difficulties linked to the first delivery (caesarean sections, post-delivery complications) which can be important factors in delay in initiation of breastfeeding.

The level of income spent on food also appears to have a relationship with the EIBF indicator, the lower the percentage spent on food, the higher the early initiation of breastfeeding. This may be related to the woman's state of health after childbirth and its effect on her availability to introduce her baby to breastfeeding. Women with low incomes, mainly spent on food, and therefore poorer, are likely to have more difficulty regaining the strength necessary to breastfeed their babies. (Fatigue and delayed recovery). Other factors for variation in EIBF rates may be due to disparities in social and demographic factors in breastfeeding practice between social groups in the area.

Figure 3.16 Early initiation of breastfeeding by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Table 3.8 Chi-squared test on relationship between EIBF in the following variables

Variable	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Age	0.46	2	0.7934	
n. Children	20.10	2	4.3e-05	***
Education	1.44	2	0.4876	
Income for food	10.54	4	0.0322	*

Exclusively breastfed for the first two days after birth (EBF2D)

Analysis of the exclusive breastfeeding indicator after two days of birth shows a percentage of only 44% of women who continue to exclusively breastfeed their babies with breast milk, a decrease of approximately 25% compared to Early initiation of breastfeeding (EIBF). This implies that the introduction of food or simply liquids such as powdered milk or still water or other liquids generally occurs in the first two days after delivery for at least 35% of the women surveyed. Prescription medications, oral rehydration solutions, vitamins and minerals are not considered liquids or foods. However, herbal drinks and similar traditional medicines are considered liquids and therefore infants who consume them are not exclusively breastfed.

It appears from statistical analyzes that it is rather the wealthiest sections of the population who devote a small part of their income to food who practice supplementation for infants within two days of their life. That is to say a gap between the two extreme classes (the majority of income dedicated to food and less than 25% intended for food) of around 30%. The probability that an infant in the wealthiest family category is two times greater (2/3) of receiving a food supplement within two days of birth than in the poorest category (1/3).

Education also significantly allows the introduction of food other than breast milk for the infant during the first two days of birth.

Figure 3.17 EBF2D by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Table 3.9 Chi-squared test on relationship between EBF2D in the following variables

Variable	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Age	5.21	2	0.0740	.
n. Children	5.12	2	0.0773	.
Education	6.15	2	0.0461	*
Income for food	41.26	4	2.4e-08	***

Bottle feeding (BoF)

Bottle-feeding is practiced in 51% of the cases studied; it appears that the factors which influence this behavior are linked to the amount of income intended for food and the woman's level of education. 67% of women whose household spends almost all of their income on food (75 to 100%) practice bottle-feeding, while only 33% of those whose household spends less than 25% of their income on food 24% of people use a bottle to breastfeed babies under 24%. This can be explained by the state of health of the woman in relation to the satisfaction of minimum needs in terms of nutrition and dietary diversification which would result in the low availability of breast milk and consequently a greater recourse to a supplementation by bottle. Education acts to reduce bottle-feeding but not to the same extent as the effect linked to income.

Figure 3.18 Bottle feeding by age, n. of children, education and share of income for food

Table 3.10 Chi-squared test on relationship between BoF in the following variables

Variable	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Age	0.78	2	0.6782	
n. Children	0.74	2	0.6893	
Education	7.63	2	0.0220	*
Income for food	11.17	4	0.0247	*

3.8.2 Urban consumers' profile

The study was conducted among urban consumers (men and women) in the two cities of Meknes and Beni Mellal. The sample of consumers for each city was distributed according to the density of the neighborhoods in order to faithfully represent the population. A final number of 729 surveys out of the 900 carried out was retained for the analysis of profiles and the characterization of nutritional diversity because they do not represent missing data or non-response for all the questions in the survey, i.e. 365 surveys for the city of Meknes and 364 for Beni Mellal.

Household food security access: HDDS (12 food groups)

The total number of food groups consumed by members of a household (out of the predefined set of 12 food groups for Morocco) for the 12 food groups are as follows: 1. Cereals (yes/no/ don't know), 2. Roots and tubers (yes/no/don't know), 3. Vegetables (yes/no/don't know), 4. Fruits (yes/no/don't know), 5. Meat, poultry (yes/no/don't know), 6. eggs (yes/no/don't know), 7. Fish and seafood (yes/no/don't know), 8. Pulses, legumes, fruit shell (yes/no/don't know), 9. Milk and dairy products (yes/no/don't know), 10. Oils, fats (foods cooked in oil) (yes/no/don't know) , 11. Sugar, honey, etc. (yes/no/don't know) and 12. Miscellaneous (condiments, tea, coffee, etc.) (yes/no/don't know).

Figure 3.19 HDDS average values by city, gender, education level and income

Household dietary diversity (HDDS) is a measure of the nutritional quality of household diets. It is essential for strategies aimed at improving access to food. An increase in the average number of different food groups consumed is a quantifiable measure of improved household access to different food groups.

The relative dietary diversity of households suggests increased food security for vulnerable households and constitutes an indirect indicator of improved nutritional status in the country. The evaluation of the average number of different food groups consumed by households over the last 24 hours shows that, in both regions, this is relatively satisfactory with an average score of around 8.72. There is a small, but not significant, difference between the city of Meknes and Beni Mellal in relation to the size of each city. The city of Beni Mellal being a smaller city very connected to the rural environment with lower work opportunities compared to the city of Meknes, appears to have a relatively lower score 8.29 compared to 8.96 for Meknes. This is also explained by income levels, which are generally higher in larger, highly urbanized cities than in smaller cities.

There is no gender disparity in dietary diversity, with men consuming the same food groups as women, particularly plant-based foods and fruits. Men usually consume more soft drinks, coffee and fried foods, while women consume more sugary products and hot drinks.

The analysis of household dietary diversity by tertile of dietary diversity (low < 5 food groups; medium 5 to 8 and high > 8) shows that the food groups which are least consumed are mainly linked to fish and legumes. The cities studied are continental cities whose inhabitants are therefore less accustomed to consuming seafood compared to coastal cities. This must also be linked to the supply of these products on local markets (low availability).

Table 3.11 Tests for differences in HDDS in the following variables by city

City	Variable	Test	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
Beni Mellal	Gender	Wilcox test	11,596.00		0.0318	*
	Age	Kruskal test	7.57	3	0.0558	.
	Education	Kruskal test	43.15	2	<0.001	***
	Income	Kruskal test	48.95	4	<0.001	***
Meknes	Gender	Wilcox test	16,268.00		0.1598	
	Age	Kruskal test	3.96	3	0.2657	
	Education	Kruskal test	7.72	2	0.0210	*
	Income	Kruskal test	16.33	4	0.0026	**
Total	Gender	Wilcox test	55,594.00		0.5597	
	Age	Kruskal test	0.60	3	0.8958	
	Education	Kruskal test	32.20	2	<0.001	***
	Income	Kruskal test	51.37	4	<0.001	***

The analysis of the determinants of the dietary diversity scores at the household level (HDDS) shows that it is above all income and the level of education which positively influence the levels of household dietary diversity in the two cities. Improving income levels and education levels would therefore significantly improve the diversity of diets. This implies, even if the two variables present collinearity, that these two factors interact mutually in the sense of improving the diversity of urban households in the two cities through accessibility to food through income or purchasing power, but also through the level of education (improved food choices).

Diet Quality (DQQ)

Food Group Diversity Score (FGDS)

For a maximum score of 10 points, the FGDS is around 6.18 for all households in urban areas with a slight difference between the two cities of around 0.5 points (5.70 for Beni Mellal against 6.25 for Meknes).

Figure 3.20 FGDS average values by city, gender, education level and income

It is always the variables income and level of education which explain the difference in performance levels in terms of diversity of food groups. We also note that there is a difference in the diversity of food groups between the two cities studied. The city of Meknes presents significantly more diversity of food groups than the city of Beni Mellal. This can be explained by the diversity of the offer of food products in the city of Meknes in relation to the size of its market and its population, but also by the average income levels in the two cities which influence the potential of households. to access a more diversified diet.

The multiple pairwise comparison (with Bonferroni adjustment) shows that it is mainly low-income households (below the average) and high levels of education (secondary and above) which explain this difference in scores between households.

Table 3.12 Tests for differences in FGDS in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif
City	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	54981		2.72e-05	***
Gender	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	55440.5		0.435	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	9.558	3	0.023	*
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	43.99	2	2.8e-10	***
Income	Kruskal Wallis test	75.53	4	1.54e-15	***

Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women of Reproductive Age (MDD-W)

For all the women who participated in the survey, the score relating to dietary diversity for women of childbearing age was calculated in the urban area on a sample of 156 women. The average score for the entire sample is 83.3% compared to 16.7% of women who cannot meet the minimum dietary diversity requirement. This score, although it may appear satisfactory for the entire sample, generally implies that

one in 6 women presents a risk linked to dietary diversity with all the consequences that this could have on the health of the child and the state of health of pregnant women in urban areas.

Figure 3.21 MDD-W by city, age, education and income in urban area

The Chi-square test, measuring the relationship between the level of education and MDD-W ($\chi^2 = 14.01$, $df = 2$, $p = .0009$), indicates that the woman's education is a crucial factor affecting the levels of dietary diversity of women of childbearing age, especially in the city of Beni Mellal, made up of a population of women with a low level of education in comparison with the sample from the city of Meknes. Income is also important in explaining MDD-W scores, ($\chi^2 = 12.11$, $df = 4$, $p = .0166$) but less important in relation to education levels. This implies that despite the difference in household income levels, dietary diversity for women and especially in relation to their education levels. Women with higher levels of education are better able to diversify their diet compared to less educated women despite the difference in household income levels.

Table 3.13 Chi-squared Test on the relationship between MDD-W and the following variables at city level

Variable	City	statistic	df.	p. Value	Signif.
Age	Beni Mellal	1.82	3	0.6102	
	Meknès	2.58	3	0.4615	.
	Total	2.89	3	0.4092	
Education	Beni Mellal	14.01	2	0.0009	***
	Meknès	2.93	2	0.2310	
	Total	13.52	2	0.0012	**
Income	Beni Mellal	9.08	4	0.0591	.
	Meknès	4.13	4	0.3891	
	Total	12.11	4	0.0166	*

ALL5

ALL5 expresses in binary value 0 or 1 the consumption of the 5 food groups during the past day and night, i.e. at least one vegetable, at least one fruit, at least one legume, one nut or one seed, at least a food of animal origin (ASF) and at least one starch. The results obtained in the two cities show that only 34.6% of the people surveyed consume the 5 recommended food groups, i.e. only 253 respondents out of 731. This rate is the lowest among the 5 countries concerned by the FoodLAND project and shows that the problem of nutritional diversity is acute in Morocco, especially in towns and villages where accessibility to diversified food products is low, not only because of low purchasing power but also due to lack of availability. Moroccans especially like to eat fresh products which are not available every day at local markets.

Moreover, we note a slight and significant improvement ($\chi^2 = 5.32$, $df = 1$, $p = .00211$) when moving from the city of Beni Mellal (smaller city) to the city of Meknes, i.e. an improvement in the score of the order of 8% which implies that the constraints linked to the availability of fresh products of plant origin (especially fruit) and products of animal origin (especially fish) are constraints which add to the problems linked to power purchasing habits and income levels of urban consumers (accessibility).

Figure 3.22 ALL5 scores by city

The income and education level variables explain the difference in performance levels in terms of diversity of food groups expressed by binary ALL5 values. We also note that there is a difference in the diversity of food groups between the two cities studied. The city of Meknes presents significantly more diversity of food groups than the city of Beni Mellal. This can be explained by the diversity of the offer of food products in the city of Meknes in relation to the size of its market and its population, but also by the average income levels in the two cities which influence the potential of households. to access a more diversified diet. On the other hand, age and gender appear to have no effect on the scores obtained.

The comparison by city shows that it is above all, the households of the city of Beni Mellal through the levels of education and income which explain this difference in scores between the households of the sample, while in the city of Meknes no of these variables do not contribute to explaining the ALL5 scores obtained (by the relationship between dietary diversity expressed using the ALL5 indicator and the variables education level and income).

Figure 3.23 ALL5 by city, gender, age, education and income

Table 3.14 Chi-squared test on relationship between All.5 and the following variables

Variable	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
City	5.32	1	0.0211	*
Gender	0.04	1	0.8350	
Age	3.59	3	0.3093	
Education	12.75	2	0.0017	**
Income	26.87	4	2.1e-05	***

Noncommunicable Diseases Score

NCD-Protect score

The NCD-Protect score is a score of 0 to 9 that reflects adherence to global dietary recommendations on healthy components of the diet. The NCD-Protect score is based on consumption of 9 healthy food groups over the past day and night. A high score indicates the inclusion of more health-promoting foods in the diet and correlates positively with adherence to global dietary recommendations. The score is expressed as the average of a sample of the population.

The average NCD-Protect value for the entire urban environment is 3.66 out of a maximum score of 9. This implies low dietary diversification among the population of the two cities studied. The city of Meknes

presents a higher score of around 0.6 points compared to the city of Beni Mellal which can be explained by the same reasons mentioned above, namely the diversity of the offer of food products in large cities, the average income level and the positive effect of education on dietary diversification. The following graph shows that the NCD-Protect score increases significantly from “Primary and below” to “Secondary and above” education level and also improves with increasing income levels.

Figure 3.24 NCD-Protect average value by city, gender, age, education level and income

The statistical analysis confirms the statistically significant relationship between the level of income and education and the NCD-Protect score obtained. The following table shows that households with below-average income have lower dietary diversity than wealthier households due to their limited ability to meet dietary needs, especially in terms of food diversification. Furthermore, families whose head is younger (18-25-year-old age group) are less likely to suffer from this problem (4.1 vs 3.6). This may be related to the size of the household for young couples and its effect on the share of the budget devoted to food. Also, due to their inability to get involved in income-generating activities through their manual labor force, diversity and food insecurity is higher among households headed by older people.

Table 3.15 Tests for differences in NCD-Protect in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
City	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	52357.5		2.87e-07	***
Gender	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	56140		0.608	

Variable	Test	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	8.656	3	0.034	*
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	42.418	2	6.15e-10	***
Income	Kruskal Wallis test	80.035	4	1.71e-10	***

The multiple pairwise comparison (with Bonferroni adjustment) shows that these are mainly low-income households (below the average vs. other income groups) and especially located in the city of Beni Mellal and education levels low (primary and lower vs secondary and above) which explain this difference in scores between households.

NCD-Risk score

The NCD-Risk score is a 0 to 9 scale score that reflects adherence to global dietary recommendations on diet components to limit or avoid. A higher score indicates greater consumption of foods and beverages to avoid or limit. It correlates negatively with adherence to global dietary recommendations. The NCD-Risk score is based on consumption of 8 food groups to limit or avoid (the processed meat food group is double weighted). This is a negative indicator, expressed as an average score for a sample of the population studied.

Regarding the dietary factors associated with the risk of NCD-Risk, the results obtained for the two urban centers show an average score of 2.04 with a standard deviation of 1.99. This implies a relatively low risk for the population regarding moderate consumption of health risk foods. The city of Meknes presents a higher score (2.10) than Beni Mellal (1.98), mainly due to differences in food preferences in large cities which tend to eat much more processed food products, canned foods and sugary drinks. But this difference is not statistically significant.

It should be noted that increasing income levels favor an increase in the NCD-Risk score among the entire population. Indeed, the score in the “below average” income bracket is around 1.51 and tends to increase gradually depending on income until reaching a value of 2.76 for the “above average” income bracket. ". We also note that when age decreases, the NCD-Risk score increases significantly from 1.69 for the age group over 45 to 3.03 for the group of young people aged 18 to 25.

On the other hand, it is important to point out that the NCD-Risk increases with the improvement in educational levels in the population studied and goes from 1.41 for the “Primary and lower” level to 2.42 for the “Secondary and higher” level. i.e. a loss of one point in terms of compliance with dietary health recommendations. This is in contradiction with the results obtained above which show better diversification and overall quality of nutrition among the more educated and better-income population. Indeed, the increase in the quality of nutrition and the diversity of the diet is accompanied by a higher consumption of food products presenting a greater risk to health. This shows the weight exerted by the socio-economic environment, advertising around these products, their accessibility and availability on the change in consumption habits and their introduction into the diet of urban households. Young people with higher income and education are more sensitive to these changes in consumption behavior and therefore more exposed to the risk linked to the increase in processed food products (processed and canned products, sweetened or carbonated drinks, sugary products, etc.)

Figure 3.25 NCD-Risk average value by city, gender, age, education level and income

We note a highly significant relationship between the NCD-Risk score and the variables age (-), level of education (+) and income (+), i.e. an increase in the score of around 1.4 points on average going from the first to the last slice for the three variables. This implies that young people with more income and a good level of education are more exposed to the risks linked to non-communicable diseases compared to poorer, older or low-income populations. Contrary to what one might think, the general improvement in living conditions is not combined with better protection against non-communicable diseases but contributes to increasing their risks.

In this regard, it would be interesting to combine the improvement of educational levels with awareness programs on nutrition and the consumption of products with a high health risk (to be integrated into school programs). This will make it possible to improve the quality and diversity of the population's diet without increasing the risk to health (Better control of the consumption of products with a high health risk). Good dietary practices must be provided to the entire population with a view to better diversification and access to balanced food, but also to minimize the risks linked to the increase in consumption of products. health risk (healthy diet) in relation to the increase in purchasing power.

Table 16 Tests for differences in NCD-Risk in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
City	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	64878.5		0.494	
Gender	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	59551.5		0.425	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	43.233	3	2.2e-09	***
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	73.859	2	9.16e-17	***
Income	Kruskal Wallis test	66.678	4	1.14e-13	***

Global Dietary Recommendations (GDR)

The GDR is a derivate score with a range from 0 to 18 that indicates adherence to global dietary recommendations, which include dietary factors protective against non-communicable diseases. The higher the GDR score, the more recommendations are likely to be met. The GDR score is based on food group consumption during the past day and night. This score is expressed as the average score for the population and calculated as follows:

$$\text{GDR score} = \text{NCD-Protect} - \text{NCD-Risk} + 9$$

The summary analysis of the results obtained shows that the score is of the order of 10.62 for the entire population surveyed with a statistically significant difference between the two cities essentially linked to the increase in the NCD-Risk score in the city of Meknes. Overall, this score shows that the population's diet makes it possible to meet at least half of the recommended dietary recommendations (Herforth, 2021).

It is rather young people under 25 who have lower scores, but still above 10, in relation to the reasons explained above (increased levels of consumption of foods risking health: foods rich in sugar, canned foods, fried foods, etc.).

Figure 3.26 GDR score average by city, gender, age, education level and income

Table 3.17 Tests for differences in GDR score in the following variables

Variable	Test	statistic	df	p. Value	Signif.
City	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	55218		3.99e-05	***
Gender	Mann Whitney Wilcoxon test	54037.5		0.188	
Age	Kruskal Wallis test	19.712	3	1.95e-04	***
Education	Kruskal Wallis test	5.793	2	0.055	.
Income	Kruskal Wallis test	5.678	4	0.225	

Note here that income does not contribute to the improvement of the GDR score and that education contributes to the statistical threshold of 10% to the reduction of the GDR score. This implies a strong change in the behavior of young people which encourages the increase in the consumption of processed and sugary products in urban areas compared to groups over 45 years old (highly significant pairwise comparison of age groups). This is in accordance with the trajectories of dietary transitions at the scale of several countries which is very often accompanied by a reduction in diet quality and an increase in health risks.

Others DQQ Diet Quality indicators

Figure 3.27 Others DQQ Diet Quality Indicators by city

Generally speaking, the two food groups that are least consumed in the two cities are prepared meats and sugary soft drinks (more than 80% of respondents do not generally consume these products) which do not go into the sense of improving the quality of the diet. But we also note a lack of groups of products interesting for the balance and dietary diversity of households, which are nuts and seeds and legumes. It is important to note that 95% of respondents reported eating animal products and fruits and vegetables in the past 24 hours. This corresponds well to the typical Mediterranean diet with meals based on meat and vegetables (Tajines and stews, etc.) and a dessert in the form of seasonal fruit.

The analysis of the quality of diets from the point of view of diversity of food resources on the basis of the 12 food groups used in the evaluation of HDDS scores for households, shows the same trend as the other DQQ indicators except for the group fish where there is a low consumption rate of less than 30%. This is mainly due to the unavailability of fresh seafood in the two mainland cities. Moroccans generally do not like to eat frozen seafood.

Figure 3.28 Food groups consumption by city

Finally, the recommended food groups most likely to be deficient are fish, nuts and seeds, legumes and dairy products. The absence of these food groups can be a risk factor for nutritional insufficiency. Most of the respondents consume cereals (95%), vegetables (83%) and fruits (78%) which contribute to the adequacy of the diet and also protect against non-communicable diseases.

The majority (70%) of respondents consume meat as part of their daily diet, with a higher prevalence in the city of Meknes which is explained by better availability and diversity of the offer of food products, by the difference in income. At constant income, it is assumed that an improvement in educational levels accompanied by an awareness program on the consumption of products with a high health risk, especially for women, will make it possible to improve the quality and diversity of the feeding of the population.

Table 3.18 Chi-squared Test on relationship significance between DQQ food groups and the following variables

DQQ Food groups	City	Gender	Age	Education	Income
Vegetables of fruits	-	-	* ↓	** ↑	* ↑
Animal source food	-	-	-	-	* ↑
Sweet beverage	-	-	-	-	* ↓
Sugar sweetened soft drink	-	-	** ↓	* ↑	** ↑
Sweet foods	-	-	*** ↓	*** ↑	*** ↑
Salty or fried snack	* ↑	-	** ↓	*** ↑	** ↑
Whole grain	*** ↑	-	-	* ↑	*** ↑
Pulse	.	-	-	-	-
Nuts and seeds	-	-	-	*** ↑	*** ↑
Processed meat	** ↑	-	-	.	.

The results of the Chi-square test between DQQ and the 4 variables namely the city of residence, gender, age of the respondent, level of education and household income bracket show that education always has an effect positive impulse on the consumption of 6 categories of foods, 3 of which can be considered at

risk for health (sweetened soft drinks, sweet foods and salty or fried snacks) and 3 others that can improve the diversity and quality of diet (whole grains, vegetables and fruits and nuts and seeds).

The improvement in income is also accompanied by a significant increase in the consumption of 7 groups out of the 10 and a significant reduction at the 5% threshold in the consumption of sweet drinks, mainly tea which is very heavily consumed by populations in low income.

Furthermore, we do not note a particular difference in the consumption of different categories of food between men and women. This can be explained by habits of sharing the same meals within the household.

Concerning the age effect, we notice that older individuals consume fewer sweet, salty or fried products compared to younger people, but also slightly fewer vegetables and fruits. This implies a low exposure to dietary risks as younger populations are more oriented to the consumption of prepared food products and sweet and salty drinks purchased.

Passing from the town of Beni Mellal to Meknes we note a notable increase in the consumption of 3 groups of food products which are whole grains, salty or fried snacks and processed meats. This is essentially linked to the more rural character of the town of Beni Mellal, where consumers are less accustomed to eating catering or processing industry products, but also due to their low availability in a smaller town and less populated than the city of Meknes. Note that whole grains are mainly purchased in bakeries and rarely cooked at home, especially in large cities.

3.9 Nutritional recommendations by life cycle

ACTIONS TO IMPROVE DIET AND NUTRITIONAL DIVERSITY

- **Promote an adequate maternal nutrition environment**, including by ensuring appropriate supply of quality supplements at all levels and strengthening coordination, as well as improving access to antenatal care for women in hard-to-reach and isolated rural areas by advocating public authorities, local representatives and community organizations to commit to improving the mother's prenatal nutrition conditions. (Pregnant woman)
- **Develop and implement communication strategies aimed at changing behaviors, including strengthening community platforms to reach pregnant and postnatal women**, as well as targeting men and community leaders on the importance of prenatal care (Women of childbearing age).
- **Organize awareness sessions in appropriate places at the community level to provide advice on pregnancy management, childbirth, breastfeeding and nutritional supplements**. This will sensitize community members to assist and provide different forms of support to mothers within their respective communities (community self-help). (Women of childbearing age and young couples)
- **Support exclusive breastfeeding, the introduction of complementary foods around 6 months and, if the mother and child wish, the continuation of breastfeeding until the age of 2 years or more**. (Woman during breastfeeding)
- **Encourage hospitals, health centers and health care settings to implement maternal care practices that improve initiation, duration and exclusivity of breastfeeding**, such as those included in the ten stages of breastfeeding defined by the WHO. (Woman during breastfeeding)
- **Promote the dissemination of practical breastfeeding information** so that parents can make an informed decision regarding nutrition (exclusivity, duration and frequency) and supplementation (training session for parents from the pregnancy period). (Woman of childbearing age)
- **Encourage the organization of meetings and training to prepare for maternity** which must be organized regularly in hospitals, dispensaries, health centers and private clinics, so that each future mother can be trained and prepared for early breastfeeding of her child within ½ hour to 1 hour after birth. Health care teams should help and encourage women to breastfeed their babies immediately after delivery. (Young women)
- **Use all possible audiovisual resources to provide advice to parents in favor of exclusive breastfeeding and dietary diversification strategies** beyond 6 months. (Young couples, young women)
- **Implement strategies and practices favorable to exclusive breastfeeding** during the first 6 months of the infant's life by integrating community organizations and associations to improve support for local initiatives in favor of breastfeeding. (Women during breastfeeding)
- **Promote adherence to recommended IYCF practices**: Timely introduction of age-appropriate, adequate, safe and properly nourished complementary foods from 6 months of age ensuring good hygiene during food preparation and feeding to prevent infections. (Household, Youth, women)
- **Implement a national strategy to reduce disparities in access to healthcare services** between regions in favor of the most isolated and rural areas with a view to remedying inequalities in the provision of care intended for communities and particularly in order to eliminate inadequacies in terms of childbirth, counseling and guidance services. (Overall)
- **Promote, through adequate legislation, policies that protect breastfeeding** especially in urban areas where women are forced to work outside the home, including paid maternity (and paternity) leave, daily breastfeeding leave, protection of a woman's right to breastfeed, improving the conditions of social coverage for support for breastfeeding, childcare in the workplace, break time in the workplace with a

clean and private place aimed at supporting women for maintaining breastfeeding. (Children, national, regional)

- **Implement specific measures in rural areas to support the nutrition of the poorest families** and specifically for young couples (subsidies, food support, etc.) with a view to improving access to food resources for pregnant or breastfeeding women. This will be less costly for society than subsequently treating secondary diseases linked to NCDs in connection with failures in breastfeeding and its consequences on the overall health of children (weight deficiency and various deficiencies, illnesses and allergies, etc.). (Overall)
- **Monitoring and analysis of data relating to breastfeeding up to the age of 2** at different levels and strata based on known breastfeeding disparities. These data should be stratified according to areas and socio-economic characteristics of the population so that breastfeeding disparities can be identified and areas requiring specific interventions can be targeted. A strong participatory information platform intended for the public sector but also for private pediatricians on a national scale on the nutrition and vaccination of children would be interesting to set up in relation to the vaccination notebooks which have become compulsory for children and can contribute to fuel more exhaustive scientific studies and research on the overall state of health of young children, including the specific aspect linked to the quality of breastfeeding and its socio-economic determinants. (Children, national, regional)
- **Develop an effective strategy and regulations on the marketing of breast milk substitutes** with a view to discouraging the use of powdered milk and bottle-feeding through more rigorous control of the quality of products intended for breastfeeding babies and infant feeding and especially through taxation and limitation of misleading advertising practices around the benefits of powdered milk and products intended for infant feeding on the physical and mental health of children. (Children under 60 months).
- **Development of specifications for school canteens and university restaurants** for a healthy and diversified diet and which must be annexed to the contractual documentation in the event of outsourcing of public catering services in the same way as the technical and financial documents. Training of catering service managers in controlling the nutritional quality of menus presented to children, adolescents and adults in relation to their nutrient content and dietary diversity in order to promote healthy diets in public catering places. (Overall)
- **Establish a rigorous control system for the sale of food and snack products** in the environment of schools and universities in order to promote healthy eating behaviors. (Overall)
- **Minimize the use of processed foods rich in salt, sugar and fats.** The problem linked to consumer food preferences regarding a healthy and balanced diet is very difficult to address in a collective and instantaneous manner. The adoption of a particular dietary behavior is a long process which can begin at a young age and take several trajectories in relation to external stimuli and the economic possibilities of individuals and households. Generally, **nutritional education** begins from the family home and can be influenced positively or negatively by the external environment in the direction of improving the quality of nutrition. To minimize the consumption of foods with a high content of sugar, salt or fat or any other risky ingredient, we can only proceed by providing advice and the necessary information on the risks and dangers linked to the excessive consumption of these products for the health, longevity and general mental and physical state of individuals depending on age, sex and the specific situation of each group (pregnant, breastfeeding women, people with high physical activity or mental, students, elderly, young, etc.). By connecting groups of people to their real life context and their socio-economic profile, it is easier to make them understand the levels of risks they are supporting and to convince them of the benefit of changing their environment. eating behavior for a healthier and more diversified diet. Generally, it is the presentation of the dangers of maintaining an inappropriate diet that influences consumers to change their behavior sooner than the benefits of changing the diet. In this sense, **more aggressive and targeted**

awareness campaigns on products with high health risks should be encouraged in the specific case of overconsumption of sugar and salt, ultra-processed food products and fast food with a high fat content. In order to promote healthier eating behaviors, it is possible to solicit **public media** to broadcast **commercials** targeted and even provocative in order to show the consequences of poor dietary behavior on the quality of life, health and longevity, with regard to tobacco for example. Legislation can play an important role in this regard by **requiring labeling and the need to detail the composition in terms of calories, sugar content, fats (saturated and unsaturated), food additives, vitamins, minerals....** For products with a high sugar content, for example, or ultra-processed products (crisps, sweet biscuits, energy drinks, etc.) and to avoid encouraging their illicit trade, in the event of a ban, it is possible to imagine **labeling obligations bearing information on the risks of excessive consumption**. Conversely, products of better quality and less dense in sugar, salt and fat can be awarded **distinctive labels in the same way as fortified “Saha wa Salama” products to encourage their consumption**. Furthermore, other solutions of a tax or financial nature **differentiated taxation on specific products** can be imagined to create price differentiation favorable to the consumption of the most beneficial products for health. Generally, in the absence of appropriate legislation, we note that the prices of food products with a greater health risk are lower or at the same level as those of more balanced foods (generally more expensive products). This is partly in connection with the marketing strategies of large agri-food firms which apply aggressive dominance strategies to capture market shares at the expense of the quality and nutritional value of the products (food market). olive oil for example). Another solution can be considered in relation to **adapting the dimensions of the packaging according to the destination of the product**. It is recommended to adapt the weight or volume of the product according to the needs of the end consumer (children, adults, adolescents, etc.) and to include this statement on the labeling in order to inform the consumer of the maximum recommended quantity and the warn about health risks linked to overconsumption of the product (obesity, hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, addiction, etc.). (Overall)

SPECIFIC ACTIONS FOR THE PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF NCDs

- **Strengthen national and regional capacities, governance, multisectoral action to accelerate the response to the prevention and control of NCDs.** Generally, the prevention of risks linked to the health of the population requires, in addition to governance, multi-sector and multi-actor intervention with a view to optimizing actions according to the performance levels of each stakeholder in relation to the different actions to be taken. to expect. In Morocco, the prevention of NCDs is above all a task dedicated to the services of the Ministry of Health through hospitals and private medical consultation structures. The Ministry of Education only intervenes in a summary and ad hoc manner through school programs to inform students about the risks of NCDs and the importance of a healthy and balanced diet. Multisectoral action must therefore be broader and integrate other public and private structures (Ministry of Youth and Sports, Ministry of Labor, Ministry of Agriculture, NGOs, Consumer Associations, etc.) in order to disseminate information and practical advice on the prevention and control of NCDs through a more diffuse and extended advice and guidance strategy covering all categories of the population and several dimensions. In this sense, it is recommended to develop a global strategy for the prevention and control of NCDs which integrates all public, private, association and NGO stakeholders with a view to implementing a more effective prevention and control approach. Eventually, it would be wise to set up a formalized national structure at the level of the Ministry of Health which coordinates, monitors and evaluates actions and programs for better governance.
- **Strengthen the consumer self-efficacy and personal engagement:** Capabilities specific to consumer eating behavior require the integration of useful knowledge and information, skills, attitudes and values. The willingness to decide in favor of healthy eating behavior is often based on attitudes and values while

relying on dynamic learning from available information and data. Nutritional education intended to reduce the risks of NCDs must therefore have the main objective of teaching the common consumer (child, young person or adult) the correct decision-making mechanisms and processes concerning the choice of foods to eat. consume. This involves developing the necessary subjectivity in the consumer-decision maker in order to be the master of his or her food consumption behavior instead of passively following standard consumption trajectories. Nutritional education programs must therefore focus above all on improving the consumer's decision-making autonomy performance in terms of the value of a healthy and balanced diet because often, this is not information on the risks linked to consumption. of specific foods or products that are lacking, but above all it is the ability to make the decision independently of the context in which this consumer finds himself (Social, historical, cultural, etc.).

- **Establish a mechanism for over-taxing advertisements on high-risk NCD products:** In order to reduce the pressure of advertising on the consumer in favor of purchasing food products presenting a high risk with regard to non-communicable diseases, higher taxation of advertising on the basis of the risk levels that they present for health, must be as effective as direct taxation of the product itself because misleading information from advertising often compensates for the price difference resulting from direct taxation through market share gains by the company. The information provided by advertising plays a role in stimulating consumption even in the presence of a consumer with strong decision-making subjectivity, promoting the reduction of risks linked to NCDs.
- **Reducing modifiable NCD risk factors and underlying social determinants through the creation of health-promoting environments.** All of the specific and collective interventions at the level of target groups and population categories as detailed in this document go in the direction of reducing the risks of NCDs and must therefore be taken into account in national and regional strategies.
- **Strengthen and orient health systems towards the prevention and control of NCDs and underlying social determinants** through primary health care. A strong collaborative medical information platform intended for the public sector but also for private doctors on a national scale on the quality of health and nutrition would be interesting to set up in relation to medical monitoring sheets for children and adults. and can help direct health advice specifically towards NCD prevention. Current information systems, even if they are useful, do not allow global integration of data and medical information collected throughout the entire life cycle of patients and are therefore incapable of allowing effective monitoring of information on the evolution of their health.
- **Encourage more comprehensive scientific studies and research on the overall health status of adults and children in relation to the prevention and fight against NCD diseases** and their socio-economic determinants. (Children, adults, women, men, national, regional, environment, etc.).
- **Establish a monitoring and evaluation system for actions undertaken for the prevention and fight against NCDs** and monitoring of trends and determinants of NCDs in order to evaluate the performance of the strategies put in place and the progress made.

ACTIONS AIMED AT ENCOURAGING THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF THE POPULATION

- **Implement public education and awareness campaigns to encourage physical activity.** The results obtained show that women in urban areas suffer more from overweight and obesity than women in rural areas (29.2% versus 28.4%), women with normal build are mainly women who have had higher education (52.4) while overweight and obesity predominate among women with no or low levels of education and women are generally more affected by problems linked to lack of physical activity than men. Public media and investment in the promotion of sport in general combined with specific programs for different groups and communities aimed at supporting behavioral change in physical activity levels.

- **Providing physical activity advice and guidance for children, adolescents and adults**, according to their profiles and their level of risk with regard to NCDs in the context of routine primary health care services.
- **Implement school-based programs that include physical education** quality, availability of adequate facilities and programs to support physical activity for all children and adolescents.
- **Providing convenient and safe access to public open spaces** (garden and sports and play area for children and adults) of quality and with adequate infrastructure to support walking and cycling.
- **Promote physical activity through organized sports groups**, clubs, programs and sporting and para-sporting events.
- **Promote private investment in clubs and sports halls** through a reduction in tax and the taxation of sports equipment.
- **Strengthen the training of sports instructors at the urban level**, especially aimed at clubs and sports halls, with a view to encouraging children to join at an early age.
- **Adapt the context and organization of sports venues to the specific requirements and needs of women** with a view to encouraging them to practice sport in the required conditions.

COMPLEMENTARY POLICIES PROMOTING HEALTHY DIET

- **Promoting healthy food environments:** It goes without saying that food requires that places of production, storage, processing and preparation of food (kitchens, restaurants, canteens, snack bars, etc.) are healthy and have the human and technical resources to meet the requirements of healthy and nutritious production and food. In this sense, in addition **legislation relating to the health control of agricultural products** (field production control) and **agri-food** (food industry), it is necessary to carry out controls in the very places where meals and menus are prepared for public catering. In addition to controlling product quality, it is necessary to carry out an **evaluation of the nutritional, balanced and diversified quality of recipes and menus presented to customers in restaurants and public canteens** and develop a participatory approach with users with a view to improving the nutritional quality without diminishing the sensory appreciation and taste of the dishes and menus presented. In the majority of cases, these diet transformations would not cost more than current menus and will just require adaptation to ensure better diversification with minimal risk regarding NCDs.
- **Taxation of energy-dense foods and low-nutritional drinks:** As has been noted in the urban environment, the increase in dietary diversification, especially among the wealthiest population and young people, is accompanied by a deviation in the diet towards food products presenting a high risk of diseases non-transmissible (overweight, obesity, hypertension, various anemias, etc.). In this sense, an adaptation of taxation on products with high energy density, products with a high sugar content, drinks with low nutritional value and ultra-processed salty products could improve the quality of the population's diet and the preserving the risks linked to poor eating habits caused essentially by the improvement of purchasing powers and by the influence exerted by aggressive marketing strategies for these products on consumer behavior in general.
- **Regulation of food marketing:** It often turns out that the quality indicators of products intended for human consumption are not specified or respected by manufacturers in the agri-food sector. Often the marketing of food products is based on vague and misleading criteria which promote the consumption of products without a direct link to their nutrient content and quality. In this sense, very precise regulations must be developed to discourage and even sanction misleading or vague advertising on the quality of food products. The case of olive oil in Morocco is very edifying, because advertising is done exclusively for low quality olive oils by referring to misleading advertising qualifiers "Extra quality" which

is very close to the classes of quality defined by the IOC and national legislation regarding the quality of olive oil.

POLICIES AND INVESTMENTS IN NUTRITIOUS FOOD

Investment in production, storage, processing and logistics technologies for food, agricultural and agri-food products aimed at increasing productivity and sustainability favorable to nutrition and the diversification of food systems.

- **Promote and invest in improving the availability of drinking water in rural areas.** The economic crisis and inflation, combined with the effects of last year's drought (2021-2022) combined with the COVID pandemic, appear to have increased households' concerns about their near future, particularly regarding the availability of food and water. An effort on the part of public authorities and local officials is necessary to address the constraints linked to access to drinking water in rural areas with a view to improving food and hygiene conditions, particularly for children 6 years old.
- **Review production, distribution, trade and marketing strategies for food products that pose a health risk** (high levels of sugar, salts, oils, ultra-processed, overly fortified, energy drinks, sugary drinks, etc.) through taxation, limitation of access (tobacco and alcohol), import quotas (sweets, biscuits, processed chocolates, ultra-processed products, canned products, etc.). We generally note that when income levels increase we often see a deviation in consumption towards products presenting a greater NCD risk compared to products of better nutritional quality. This will certainly be in relation to aspects linked to consumer tastes and preferences, but also to the aggressive effects of advertising around these products.
- **Improve production, trade, distribution and marketing for quality local food products with high nutritional potential.** Subsidy levels in the food and agriculture sectors should be reviewed, particularly for commodities, to avoid taxing foods that are nutritious and have a positive effect on farmers' income levels. The consumer subsidy for wheat flour (national flour) is justified even if the levels of bread waste are too high in urban areas. On the other hand, subsidies for oilseed production through the subsidization of agricultural inputs and the establishment of import barriers sometimes penalize consumption in relation to prices on the world market and the possibilities of adapting production systems. local. There are several agricultural products that can be produced more cost-effectively for farmers and consumers. These are penalized through various customs or tariff measures which discourage their production in favor of a certain number of other agricultural products under the pretext of the country's food sovereignty and without any connection with the quality and diversification of food for the consumer (typical case of support for the sugar sector in Morocco). The government should conduct a thorough objective review of current agricultural policies to ensure that production of nutritious foods is supported at optimal levels rather than taxed with a view to avoiding low or excess consumption levels for dietary diversification. efficient and economical.
- **Support the integration of food supplements intended for children and adults for a better balanced diet** to avoid vitamin and mineral deficiencies (Vitamin D, A, B, Iron, Iodine, Ca...). This could be done through a better tax policy for fortified and nutrient-dense products and also through the encouragement of scientific research on new agricultural products richer in nutrients and vitamins and adapted to the specific needs and dietary habits of the population (wheat rich in gluten, salt rich in iodine, oil rich in vitamins and iron...). (30.3% of Moroccan women have an iron deficiency and 49.7% of anemic women have an iron deficiency). Furthermore, the national survey (PNN, 2019) on nutrition revealed regarding the evaluation of knowledge of the "Siha Wa Salama" logos relating to fortified products and "iodized salt" by households that 76.4% and 71 % of households did not know the "Siha wa Salama" and "iodized salt" logos respectively. This implies an additional effort on the part of public authorities to make

known the importance of these logos in evaluating the quality and guiding the purchase of food products in general.

- The fragility of the agricultural sector and its dependence on rainfall limit the responsiveness of the food supply, including cereals. In Morocco, policies that favor the production of staple crops, such as seed and credit subsidies, price supports, and import barriers (particularly for wheat), have tended to discourage production traditional crops other than staple crops, such as pulses and olive growing for several decades. This has led to large fluctuations in the prices of pulses and olive oil in relation to imports (generally higher prices). Policies should instead promote investment by specifically targeting the strengthening of the production capacity of pulses, vegetables and fruits in all seasons and all other high value-added products in order to increase the availability of nutritious foods. This while capturing signals from the global commodity market in order to take advantage of excess supply or increased demand for exportable or importable agricultural products and **effectively adapt national agricultural production systems in a dynamic and flexible sense.**
- **Promote and support national capacities in high-quality research and development for sustainable nutrition-focused agriculture:** Investment in research, innovation and popularization in the value of nutrition is very important and remains the only effective way to respond, through solutions adapted to the national and local context, to the problems linked to improving conditions feeding the population. Research on the valorization of agro-biodiversity in favor of nutrition, the improvement of production, storage, transport, transformation and valorization technologies are the only available and effective means to be able to propose technical solutions capable of to improve the efficiency of local food systems. In this sense, the State must provide greater support for research and innovation programs in food and human nutrition. These programs must be able to propose technical solutions to improve the production of food products and the quality of nutrition in general, but also highlight the potential of local production systems for improving the living conditions of farmers. Solutions must therefore be adapted to different contexts in order to maintain local traditional systems while seeking to better exploit their technical potential and know-how (without disruption). These strategies should not necessarily aim to increase production levels, but must focus on food performance in terms of nutritional density, economic efficiency (valorization, reduction of production losses, processing and consumption), opportunity economical and sustainability.
- **Improving food supply, distribution and logistics chains in rural areas** through investment in the road network, transport and market infrastructure. The results obtained, specifically in rural areas, with regard to the diversity of diets are alarming. This implies that the problem of access to food in rural areas arises both in terms of availability of food products on the market in addition to the problem of purchasing power. Indeed, because of the costs linked to transport, the prices of food products not produced locally are more expensive compared to the urban environment, mainly due to problems linked to transport logistics and isolation. People in rural areas eat meat, fish and fruits more rarely because of their low availability in local markets due to the low economic interest for traders due to the size of the market, but also in connection with the problems linked to transport and distribution costs. In this sense, a sustained effort must be made by the public authorities through investment in the road network (rural roads), logistics and trade infrastructure (markets, souks, local shops, etc.) with a view to increasing the benefit of trade in food products in the most isolated rural areas.

CONSUMER-ORIENTED POLICIES PROMOTING HEALTHY DIETS

Policies to reduce poverty and income inequality through strengthening nutrition-sensitive social protection mechanisms, including

- **Strengthen the food aid system through public catering systems (school canteens and collective catering) and subsidies for the neediest families.** The establishment of direct aid mechanisms for the most vulnerable sections of the population is necessary to remedy the problems of undernutrition, especially in rural areas, where the possibilities of finding means of subsistence are very limited. The results obtained, through several indicators, for the specific case of the woman-child couple in rural areas of the Beni Mellal region are very revealing of the situation of rural populations in relatively isolated areas with poor access to the labor market (HDDS, MDD-W, ALL5, GDR...). Furthermore, it is important to point out that sometimes for purely economic objectives, university restaurants and school canteens have moved towards standardized and not very diversified meals based essentially on frozen products or semi-prepared foods (frozen products, canned goods, cold meats). ...) with simple and economical cooking recipes without any connection with nutritional quality and dietary diversification. In this sense, if economic reasons always remain important to take into account, the state will have to set an example, through these public catering places, in terms of respecting healthy, diversified and nutritious food standards.
- **Adapt the system of monetary transfers intended for the poorest populations:** In Morocco, monetary transfers from the city to the countryside are very developed and diversified through a very important network of public and private money transfer organizations within the country but also Moroccan residents abroad which constitute an important source of foreign currency for the country and contribute significantly to improving the living conditions of the poorest populations. In this sense, it would be interesting to think about encouraging transfers of a social nature, through appropriate taxation mechanisms with a view to relieving the poorest populations of the burdens linked to the cost of transactions. This could encourage the issuers of these transfers to support these social aids and improve the living conditions of the poorest populations who are highly dependent on these financial contributions with regard to the diversification of diets and access to healthy and nutritious food.
- **Improving subsidy and taxation policies in the agriculture and agri-food sector.** In Morocco, fluctuations in the prices of agricultural products not subject to price control are very strong (vegetables, fruits, meats, legumes, fish, etc.) in connection with the cost of inputs, the quality of precipitation (importance of irrigation) and the market situation for agricultural products. The state sometimes intervenes with a view to lowering producer prices by subsidizing agricultural inputs, securing livestock by subsidizing livestock feed and adapting customs barriers in favor or against imports. These interventions which tend to maintain the prices of agricultural products at standard levels with low fluctuations are often costly for the taxpayer and result in a reduction in the possibilities of small farmers, often the poorest, to benefit from favorable market conjectures in with a view to increasing their income and their incentives to produce, but also their accessibility to healthier and more diversified diets (does not intervene when prices are too low in order to support poor producers in rural areas). Consequently, these policies penalizing food and agricultural production (through direct or indirect taxation) should be reviewed and improved according to the different local agricultural products with a view to improving agro-biodiversity and reducing the negative effects on the production of local nutritious foods. Subsidies of basic products such as flour, edible oils and sugar sometimes often benefit urban consumers. In this sense, subsidy levels in the food and agriculture sectors should be reviewed, in relation to the benefits linked to low-income farmers for better social equity and to preserve the production of local nutritious foods, the agro-biodiversity of agricultural areas and maintaining social solidarity between the city and the countryside.
- **Promote policies in favor of sustainable consumption and the reduction of food waste:** The low prices of essential food goods (breads and derivatives) often lead to overconsumption of these products at the

expense of other more diversified and less accessible products in relation to market prices. Bread is a very perishable product and its quality decreases significantly after 12 hours of baking. In this sense, it would be interesting to study the possibilities of reducing taxation on prepared breads with a longer shelf life in addition to adapting the price of bread on the market with a view to avoiding waste. Currently the price of “**Farine nationale**” flour is regulated on the market in the same way as the price of bread made from this flour in bakeries (baguette and pancake made from subsidized flour). Bakery processing and preparation technologies should also be encouraged to offer bread products with a longer shelf life that can help reduce waste. Several other products can be the subject of more targeted strategies to encourage sustainable consumption and waste reduction (vegetables, fruits, fish, prepared foods, etc.). In this sense, it may be useful to study the possibilities of adjusting taxation on household appliances intended for the preparation and preservation of food products with a view to reducing food waste.

- **Support a diversified and quality diet for children and adolescents beyond 6 months through the development of guides to good food and nutrition practices** intended for parents and adolescents. These good eating practices must be taken into account in school programs with a view to showing children, depending on their ages, the benefits of a healthy and balanced diet on their physical and mental health. These guides should also make it possible to discourage children and adolescents from consuming ultra-processed foods and products, too salty or too sweet (often cheap) and to offer them menus as attractive in terms of taste which could encourage them to prefer the most health-friendly and balanced diets, even if it means spending more money on quality.
- **Support for nutrition education:** Overall, the results obtained in the specific case of our surveys in Meknes and Beni Mellal show that education plays an important role in the quality of food with notable differences in relation to purchasing power. In this sense, support for nutritional education through school programs and specific training modules for young couples and women at the start of pregnancy and during the breastfeeding period, for example, can go in the direction to improve the overall diet of the population. It turns out that when consumers have useful information on healthy diets to follow and the most interesting foods to eat, they are always able to choose a food basket that does not differ greatly from the potential optimal basket.

NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS BASED ON TECHNOLOGIES DEVELOPED UNDER THE FoodLAND PROJECT

- **Promoting more productive and sustainable agriculture** making it possible to raise production levels and increase availability throughout the year through the improvement of processing and conservation techniques.
- **Promote the production and consumption of enriched and fortified foods** through the choice of the best seeds and varieties for better quality nutrition and the choice of the best storage technologies.
- **Improving agricultural production using precision agricultural technologies** in production, crop protection, harvesting and storage. The use of precision technologies in agriculture should make it possible both to improve production levels and resource use efficiency, but also to improve the sustainability of local production systems through optimal use of resources. agricultural inputs (pesticides, seeds, irrigation water, etc.)
- **Encourage labeling, organic production and distinctive quality signs and labeling of food products** in order to help consumers better choose the healthiest, diversified and nutritious foods. Better segmentation of the market for agricultural and food products is necessary in order to highlight quality products. This can only be done through the use of quality indicators and the improvement of legislation concerning product labeling obligations, in particular through the creation of labels and distinctive signs

and quality statements allowing consumers to choose in an informed manner and encourage producers to direct production towards the most profitable market niches.

Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Morocco

Table 3.19 Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Morocco (see details above)

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Promote an adequate maternal nutrition environment	Prevention	Pregnant woman	National
Develop and implement communication strategies aimed at changing behaviors, including strengthening community platforms to reach pregnant and postnatal women.	Prevention	Women of childbearing age	National
Organize awareness sessions in appropriate places at the community level to provide advice on pregnancy management, childbirth, breastfeeding and nutritional supplements		Women of childbearing age and young couples	National
Support exclusive breastfeeding, the introduction of complementary foods around 6 months and, if the mother and child wish, continued breastfeeding until the age of 2.		Woman during breastfeeding	National
Encourage hospitals, health centers and health care settings to implement maternal care practices that improve breastfeeding initiation, duration and exclusivity.		Woman during breastfeeding	National
Promote the dissemination of practical breastfeeding information		Woman of childbearing age	National
Encourage the organization of meetings and training to prepare for maternity	Prevention	Young women	National
Use all possible audiovisual resources to provide advice to parents in favor of exclusive breastfeeding and dietary diversification strategies beyond 6 months		Young couples, young women	National
Implement strategies and practices favorable to exclusive breastfeeding	Prevention	Women during breastfeeding	National
Promote adherence to recommended IYCF practices		Household Young women	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Implement a national strategy to reduce disparities in access to healthcare services.		Global	National, regional, local
Promote, through adequate legislation, policies that protect breastfeeding		Children, national, regional	National
Implement specific measures in rural areas to support the nutrition of the poorest families		Global	National, Rural
Monitoring and analysis of data relating to breastfeeding up to the age of 2		Children, national, regional	National, Regional
Develop an effective strategy and regulations on the marketing of breast milk substitutes		Children under 60 months	National
Development of specifications for school canteens and university restaurants		Global	National
Establish a rigorous control system for the sale of food and snack products in the environment of schools and universities.	Prevention	Global	National
Minimize the use of processed foods high in salt, sugar and fat for the prevention and control of NCDs. (nutritional education, more aggressive and targeted awareness campaigns on products with high health risks, advertising spots, labeling and the need to detail the composition in terms of calories, sugar content, fat (saturated and unsaturated), food additives, vitamins, minerals, etc., labeling obligations bearing information on the risks of excessive consumption, distinctive labels in the same way as fortified products to encourage their consumption, differentiated taxation on specific products, adaptation of the dimensions of the packaging according to the destination of the product)		Global	National
Strengthen national and regional capacities, governance, multisectoral action to accelerate the response to the prevention and control of NCDs.	Prevention	Global	National
Strengthen the consumer self-efficacy and personal engagement		Individuals	National
Establish a mechanism for over-taxing advertisements on high-risk NCD products		Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Reduce modifiable NCD risk factors and underlying social determinants through the creation of health-promoting environments		Global	National
Strengthen and orient health systems towards the prevention and control of NCDs and underlying social determinants	Prevention	Global	National
Encourage more comprehensive scientific studies and research on the overall health status of adults and children in relation to the prevention and fight against NCD diseases (Children, adults, women, men, national, regional, environment, etc.).	Prevention	Global	National
Establish a monitoring and evaluation system for actions undertaken for the prevention and fight against NCDs.		Global	National
Promoting healthy diets in the school environment , university and public canteens/restaurants;	Prevention	Global	National
Establish precise and detailed specifications for public catering including compliance with health, dietary and nutritional requirements in order to promote healthy diets in public eating places.		Global	National
Limit snacks in public places, especially for children and people at high risk of NCDs and strengthening quality control of food products in the environments of Schools and Universities.	Prevention	Children, teenagers adults	National
Implement quality school physical education programs with adequate facilities and grounds and specific support programs for physical activity for children.		Children, adolescents	National
Providing convenient and safe access to quality public open spaces and adequate infrastructure to encourage walking and cycling.		Children, teenagers adults	National
Promote physical activity in groups and clubs and through organized sporting programs and events.		Global	National
Promote private investment in clubs and sports halls through a reduction in tax and the taxation of sports equipment.		Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Strengthen the training of sports instructors at the urban level , especially aimed at clubs and sports halls, with a view to encouraging children to join at an early age.		Global	National
Adapt the context and organization of sports venues to the specific requirements and needs of women with a view to encouraging them to practice sport in the required conditions.		Women	National
Promote nutritional education for all life cycles and target groups (schools, universities, businesses, youth centers, retirement homes, communities, associations, etc.)	Prevention	Global	National
Encourage advertising aimed at promoting healthy, balanced and diversified diets (radio, television, social networks, advertising spots, brochures, practical guides, leaflets, bulletins, etc.);		Global	National
Encourage healthy and diversified eating in restaurants and private snack bars through the health and quality control of food and the granting of distinctive labels.		Global	National
Reduce salt and sugar consumption by reformulating food products to contain less salt and sugar and by setting target levels in foods and meals.		Global	National, Regional
Reduce salt and sugar consumption by establishing a favorable environment in public institutions, such as hospitals, schools, workplaces and retirement homes to enable the implementation of low sodium and glucose options.		Global	National
Inform and warn consumers about salt and sugar levels contained in foods and food products prepared or processed by the implementation of specific labeling (specific labels)	Prevention	Global	National
Eliminate industrial trans fatty acids by developing legislation prohibiting their use in the food chain.		Global	National
Reduce sugar and salt consumption by taxing effectively sweet drinks and salty food preparations.		Global	National
Reduce the consumption of foods high in fat, salt and sugar and sugary drinks by children and adolescents by developing legislation limiting and discouraging the promotion of these products especially to children and adolescents	Prevention	Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Adapt tax mechanisms to reduce sugar and salt consumption through a strategic reformulation of products, marketing and sales.		Global	National,
Protect, promote and support exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life and until the age of two years and beyond, with safe and adequate complementary feeding and a dietary diversification program.		Young women	National,
Implement appropriate subsidies or taxation to encourage consumption legumes, fish, nuts and seeds.		Overall, households	National,
Discourage the consumption of energy drinks through over-taxation, labeling and differentiation of the product by unfavorable distinctive sign and the adaptation of small packaging. Limitation of advertisements through control of the veracity of content and specific surcharges.	Prevention	Global, adolescents, adultes	National,
Improving food supply, distribution and logistics chains for better availability throughout the country, including in isolated areas. Through investment in the road network, transport and market infrastructure.		Global	National,
Promote the replacement of trans fats and saturated fats with unsaturated fats through reformulation, labeling and tax and agricultural policies.		Global	National,
Adapt and limit portion and packaging sizes to reduce energy intake and the risk of overweight or obesity.		Global	National,
Implement nutrition education and counseling in different contexts (e.g. in preschools, schools, workplaces, clinics and hospitals) to increase the consumption of fruits, vegetables, legumes, dried fruits and seeds	Prevention	Global	National,
Implement nutritional labeling to control energy intake total (kcal) of foods		Global	National,
Implement a media campaign on healthy diets to reduce the consumption of total fats, saturated fats, sugars and salt and to promote the consumption of fruits and vegetables, fish and legumes.	Prevention	Global	National,

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Advocate for adequate diets for women before, during and after childbirth and appropriate supplementation.		Women	National,
Promoting dietary diversification among women planning pregnancy.		Young women	National,
Promoting the socio-economic empowerment of women in order to increase the practice of dietary diversity.		Women	National, Rural
Implementation of the dietary diversity screening guide when visiting health establishments. Health professionals should be able to advise mothers on how to increase the quality of the diet, particularly that of children under two years of age.	Prevention	Overall, young children	National
Encourage farmers to follow access training on the quality of agricultural products and put in place technical support measures to promote the production and consumption of healthy, diverse and nutritious foods.		Farmers	Rural, Regional
Encourage the reduce the consumption of carbonated drinks and products that are too energy dense or too high in sugar and fat for women during the last months of pregnancy and during the breastfeeding period.	Prevention	Pregnant woman, breastfeeding	National
Implementation of specific measures in rural areas to improve the conditions of use of local food resources available but also their good use at the local level and in the household.		Global	Rural
Strengthening health systems to provide child-centered care at different levels of the health system		Children	National
Providing essential medicines and medical technologies for the benefit of women and children with a view to assessing and guiding women on ways to improve their diet and prevent risks related to pregnancy and NCDs.		Women, children	National, Regional
Promote community actions that support children and families living with noncommunicable diseases, to ensure that children enjoy the best possible quality of life.		Families, children	National
Strengthening national health insurance schemes to cover non-communicable diseases affecting children and adults by reducing the costs of treatment and medical consultations.		Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
<p>Strengthen health systems and specific actions related to health and nutrition for older people, in particular the prevention of age-related diseases such as loss of muscle mass and bone fragility. With the progressive aging of Morocco's population, systems for monitoring the health of older people are necessary to be in place (specific information system).</p>		Global	National, Regional
<p>Improving food supply, distribution and logistics chains in rural areas through investment in the road network, transport and market infrastructure.</p>		Global	Rural
<p>Facilitate access to health benefits for older people by establishing mechanisms for access to care that are more favorable to the provision of these services.</p>		The elderly	National
<p>Improving food price control systems, particularly fruits, vegetables and seafood with a view to allowing better diversification of diets, especially in rural areas where the problem arises both in terms of accessibility and availability.</p>		Global	National
<p>Ensure that macroeconomic policies to control food markets, including basic products, do not benefit any social category depending on another (producers vs consumers, urban vs rural, rich vs poor, etc.) in order to preserve resources and avoid economic waste.</p>		Global	National
<p>Support the consumption of local food products in order to improve regional trade, farmers' income and maintain agro-biodiversity.</p>		Global	Local, Regional, National
<p>Raise consumer awareness of the importance of collecting useful information on food consumed through reading the information on the labeling (quality, origin, labels, brands, nutritional indications, distinctive signs, etc.) with a view to directing consumption towards the healthiest, nutritious and diversified food products</p>		Global	National
<p>Support and promote family planning in order to maintain minimum capacities to meet the needs of households, including access to sufficient, healthy and diversified food.</p>		Family, households	National
<p>Promote the production and consumption of enriched or fortified foods by differentiating taxation, subsidizing investment, labeling, reducing tax burdens and supporting consumer prices in relation to the specific needs and deficiencies of each category of the population (infants, adolescents, pregnant women or women in pregnancy). breastfeeding, adults, elderly people, athletes, etc.).</p>		Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
Promote and invest in improving the availability of drinking water in rural areas.		Global	Rural, Regional
Review production, distribution, trade and marketing strategies for food products that pose a health risk (high levels of sugar, salts, oils, ultra-processed, overly fortified, energy, sugary drinks, etc.).	Prevention	Global	National
Improve production, trade, distribution and marketing for local food products		Global	Local, Regional
Support the integration of food supplements intended for children and adults for a better balanced diet to avoid vitamin and mineral deficiencies (Vitamin D, A, B9, B12, Iron, Iodine, Ca, Mg...).		Children, adults, household	National
Promote and support national capabilities in high-quality research and development for sustainable agriculture focused on nutrition.		Global	National
Increase customs duties, taxes and prices of tobacco products and products assimilated		Global	National
Strengthening enforcement of global advertising bans tobacco at the point of sale.		Global	National
Strengthen enforcement of laws regarding exposure to second-hand tobacco smoke in all indoor workplaces, public places and public transport.		Global	National
Ban the retail sale of tobacco (cigarettes) in public places and tobacco shops , especially near schools and universities.		Global	National
Criminalize the sale of tobacco to minors through legislation and an appropriate control mechanism.		Minors, adolescents	National
Strengthen legislation prohibiting the sale and illicit trade and smuggling of tobacco.		Global	National
Strengthen labeling discouraging tobacco consumption , which is sometimes not well presented on cigarette packages or presented in a diffuse manner.	Prevention	Global	National

Recommendations	Action Area	Live cycle period	Intervention scale (stakeholders)
<p>Implement effective and targeted media campaigns on the negative effects of tobacco on health to educate the public about the harms of smoking and passive smoking through more effective targeting of the most exposed population categories (adolescents, individuals with low levels of education or low income).</p>	Prevention	Global	National
<p>Promoting more productive and sustainable agriculture making it possible to raise production levels and increase availability throughout the year through the improvement of processing and conservation techniques.</p>		FoodLAND	National
<p>Promote the production and consumption of enriched and fortified foods through the choice of the best seeds and varieties for better quality nutrition and the choice of the best storage technologies.</p>		FoodLAND	National
<p>Improving agricultural production using precision agricultural technologies in production, crop protection, harvesting and storage.</p>		FoodLAND	National
<p>Encourage labeling, organic production and distinctive quality signs and labeling of food products in order to help consumers better choose the healthiest, diversified and nutritious foods.</p>		FoodLAND	National

Conclusions

We clearly see that improving education levels and income generally allows for better diversification of the diet for the entire population surveyed. However, this diversification of the diet is very often accompanied by an increase in the consumption of categories of food products presenting a relatively high health risk and which concern the dietary factors associated with the risk of NCD. The results on NCD-Risk for the two urban centers show an average score for the city of Meknes (2.10) higher than that of Beni Mellal (1.98), mainly due to differences in food preferences which tend to be more oriented towards catering and purchasing food products prepared in the city of Meknes due to the improvement in the standard of living. Note that increasing income levels encourage an increase in the NCD-Risk score among the entire population.

In rural areas, the food situation is more complicated for women of childbearing age with very low levels of dietary diversification and very limited purchasing power compared to urban areas. In the context of the rural environment studied, the problem of nutrition arises in terms of availability but also accessibility. The study found a significant association between the DD of the woman-child couple and the share of income spent on food and the level of education of the mothers. These two variables play an important role in improving levels of dietary diversification, but it is important to point out the bidirectional effect linked to education on the risks linked to communicable diseases precisely because of access to a more diversified diet. but also at greater health risk with regard to NCDs.

Satisfaction of minimum nutritional needs remains limited in terms of diversification but probably also in terms of minimum quantities required. Households that spend a significant part of their income on food are less sensitive to problems linked to the risk of non-communicable diseases. These disadvantaged populations, not necessarily practicing agricultural activity, often depend on unstable, risky and unsustainable sources of income and are thus unable to access food that is generally more expensive and very often increases the risk of non-communicable diseases.

Overall, we note that the diet of women of childbearing age is not adequate and more than 16% of women between 16 and 45 years old do not meet the MDD-W criteria. The average score is 56.6% compared to 43.4% of women who cannot meet the minimum dietary diversity. This score is lower than that recorded for the same profile of female residents in urban areas, i.e. 83.3% in urban areas compared to 56.6% in rural areas, i.e. 27 points difference. This difference marks a significant gap in dietary diversity among women between 16 and 49 years old between rural and urban areas. and implies a very high risk linked to dietary diversity with all the consequences that this can have on the health of the children and women in rural areas.

For the quality of food and breastfeeding, we note that overall dietary diversity is low among children aged 6 to 24 months and does not exceed 4 food groups on average per day. This is in relation to the levels of diversification of women and the family which are also low in the rural area studied. The low accessibility to food and sometimes its availability contributes to the reduction in dietary diversity and the quality of the diet of young children.

Low income levels and low education of women are the determinants which appear to have a significant impact on the performance levels of feeding children under 24 months, including in the practice of supplementation and bottle-feeding. The quality of breastfeeding (initiation, exclusivity and availability) is directly influenced by the nutritional and health status of mothers in relation to family income levels and mothers' education.

When promoting dietary diversity for children, particular attention should be paid to household food insecurity (levels of food accessibility) and socio-demographic characteristics of mothers (level of education and number of dependent children). In the future, it could be more effective to target interventions aimed at raising mothers' awareness of the importance of dietary diversification for children before they reach the age of 6 months, with a view to supporting mothers for improving the diversity and quality of the diet and ensuring its positive dynamics during the transition period towards complete weaning (food diversification program from 6 months). Furthermore, efforts could certainly be undertaken to improve or facilitate access to healthy and nutritious foods in quantity and quality. To do this, the implementation of measures specific to rural areas integrated into the national nutrition strategy could allow not only the improvement of the conditions of use of available food resources but also their proper valorization during the first two years of life. of the child.

Actions are therefore needed to strengthen and protect positive eating habits and curb or reverse those associated with increased risk linked to various forms of malnutrition. If education levels and incomes improve they must necessarily be accompanied by an improvement in dietary diversification which involves access and affordability of various nutrient-rich foods but also the minimization of potential risks linked to Excess consumption of food products associated with a high risk of non-communicable diseases. Steps should therefore be taken to reduce the consumption of sugary foods and ultra-processed foods such as soft drinks and packaged salty fast foods in urban areas.

Despite the problems related to access to food in rural areas, we note that the scores relating to the NCD indicators are very satisfactory compared to those in urban areas. This confirms the results obtained concerning the negative knock-on effects caused by the increase in dietary diversification on the increase in health-related risks. Improving conditions of access to food is often not accompanied by changes in food consumption and dietary profiles which tend to increase the risks linked to non-communicable diseases regardless of the environment (rural or urban).) and the socio-economic profile specific to each category of consumers.

Young people are in any case more exposed to health risks related to food than older people, including in the specific case of rural women of childbearing age. This means greater sensitivity of young people to incentives for changes in eating habits in relation to income levels and the availability of risky food groups in each region.

In this sense, early prevention of NCDs and their consequences should be at the heart of public health management policies. Countrywide nutrition plans and strategies cannot ignore the importance of social determinants of health, including gender, socio-economic status, age and levels of accessibility to food resources. These social determinants are necessary to understand in relation to their effect on the health and nutrition of populations to adapt interventions to different local and regional contexts.

In Morocco, the strategy to combat the risks of NCDs focuses, in a fragmentary manner, on prevention and secondary treatment by attacking overweight and hypertension, once they have appeared, with the aim of to reduce the development of NCDs or to slow their progression once they are established.

While these approaches help reduce morbidity and mortality and should be continued, some are prohibitively expensive. In this sense, the integration of primary prevention strategies for the risks of NCDs could help slow the growth of NCDs by preventing the development of risk factors.

The challenges of promoting health behaviors and reducing risk factors for noncommunicable diseases are considerable. They encompass socio-economic determinants specific to individuals, families, communities

and the global environment in which they live. For young people to engage in issues related to NCD risks, they must be able to engage in autonomous learning processes with a view to acquiring the skills required to use appropriate means and mechanisms of learning in the daily decision-making related to food and health.

These capacities must be at the heart of school programs to enable the reduction of primary risks of non-communicable diseases. This is achieved through appropriate learning and capacity development to promote sustainable health-promoting behaviors.

Thus, factors relating to education (engagement, learning and capacity development supporting decision-making favorable to health and the reduction of NCDs) must be taken into account in the impact assessment approaches of health strategies. health at the appropriate scale with a view to monitoring specific actions aimed at encouraging and promoting effective and appropriate learning. Therefore, measuring the impact of education programs aimed at contributing to the reduction of primary NCD risks requires multidisciplinary approaches recognizing the central role of schools in learning.

Furthermore, when promoting dietary diversity for children, particular attention should be paid to household food insecurity (levels of accessibility to food) and the socio-demographic characteristics of mothers (level of education and number of dependent children). In the future, it could be more effective to target interventions aimed at raising mothers' awareness of the importance of dietary diversification for children before they reach the age of 6 months, with a view to supporting mothers for improving the diversity and quality of the diet and ensuring its positive dynamics during the transition period towards complete weaning (food diversification program from 6 months). Furthermore, efforts could certainly be undertaken to improve or facilitate access to healthy and nutritious foods in quantity and quality. To do this, the implementation of measures specific to rural areas integrated into the national nutrition strategy could allow not only the improvement of the conditions of use of available food resources but also their proper valorization during the first 2 years of life. of the child.

It is strongly recommended that health establishments offer mothers a sustained nutritional education program regarding dietary diversity and good child feeding practices even before delivery and at the start of pregnancy. Information and introductory materials on the nutrition of women and infants can be distributed to young women during child vaccination visits (which can be annexed to the compulsory vaccination book at the level of the 'entire country) in different formats). CDs may also be of interest to illiterate women.

It would also be interesting, as part of future studies to be carried out in the region, to determine the adequacy of nutrient intake, the comparison of nutrient intake and the nutritional status of children, as well as the value nutritional value of local foods available.

It is clear that we must meet the challenge of changing local food systems so that everyone can access nutritious food or overcome a lack of income to afford a healthy diet, while ensuring that production and food consumption contribute to environmental sustainability, but also, aim to maintain positive eating practices and habits and counteract changes associated with the various risks linked to excessive or unbalanced consumption of food groups presenting a risk of worsening of non-communicable diseases (malnutrition, deficiencies, obesity, anemia, etc.).

There cannot be a single solution on the scale of the entire country. Obstacles and constraints must be assessed in relation to local and regional contexts in relation to production potential, positive consumption

habits and potential gains for the environment in order to achieve the necessary transformations. The results obtained on the quality of food and nutrition in our work can therefore serve as a starting point to refine the necessary actions at the scale of each area and serve as a scientific reference for the evaluation of the progress made during of the next few years.

The expansion of the urban population requires immediate attention with a view to promoting the inclusion of urban food security in national, regional and municipal development programs and plans, assisting low-income urban households, particularly women by targeting food transfers or vouchers to those in need of nutrient-dense foods and providing practical family nutrition training for young women focusing on the quality and nutritional value of foods and the food hygiene.

It is important to note that our study was not carried out at the national level, which means that the scores of the indicators on diet diversity and quality presented in our work are not generalizable at the level of the entire country. However, the sample size of our study is sufficient for its specific objective which was to assess diet diversity and nutrition quality in the two Food Hubs studied. The results obtained, even if they are not validated for all the regions concerned, can serve as reliable scientific support, reference and proof for developing targeted regional nutrition strategies.

The work, however, presents some weaknesses that should be noted. Firstly, its cross-sectional nature makes it difficult to conclude that the results of this research represent those of an entire year in an agricultural area, due to seasonal variability in terms of food availability in relation to harvest season and income variations. The current study was carried out during a lean period (February – March). It would therefore be interesting for future research to be carried out during periods of better food availability in order to compare and evaluate these seasonal variabilities in a rural environment strongly impacted by agriculture.

Another weakness of this research is linked to the measurement of children's dietary diversity which did not allow us to capture differences in diet quality depending on the age of the children. Despite these limitations, this research is innovative in that it examines the contribution of socio-economic and environmental factors and their effects on the dietary performance of woman-child couples in a highly contrasting rural region.

Finally, it is important to have reliable and complete baselines that make it possible to evaluate the impact of interventions on beneficiary (and non-beneficiary) populations. To do this, particular attention must be paid to the definition of baseline indicators so that they are easily measurable and compatible with the monitoring-evaluation tools put in place.

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4 CHAPTER FOUR: REPORT ON NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TANZANIA

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Operational definitions

Minimum dietary diversity: achieved when ≥ 5 out of 10 specific food group are consumed by an individual over the course of a day.

Recommended food groups: daily consumption of five food groups recommended by in food-based dietary guidelines around the world: fruits; vegetables; pulses, nuts, or seeds; animal-source foods; and starchy staples. A score of 5 indicates minimal adherence to dietary guidelines, because people who did not consume the food groups definitely did not meet dietary guidelines.

NCD-Protective score: is based on food consumption from 9 healthy food groups during the past day and night. The NCD-Protect score is a score with a range from 0 to 9. A higher score indicates inclusion of more health-promoting foods in the diet, and correlates positively with meeting global dietary recommendations. It is expressed as the average score for the population.

NCD-Risk: is based on food consumption from 8 food groups to limit or avoid during the past day and night (one food group, processed meat, is double weighted). The NCD-Risk score is a score with a range from 0 to 9. A higher NCD-Risk score is closely related to higher ultra-processed food consumption. A higher score indicates higher consumption of foods and drinks to avoid or limit, and correlates negatively with meeting global dietary recommendations.

Executive summary

Tanzania is experiencing multiple forms of malnutrition, namely undernutrition, micronutrient deficiencies and overweight and obesity. All these forms affect cognitive productive and reproductive aspects in different ways. Although there is good progress in reducing the prevalence of stunting, rapid increase in overweight and obesity is observed which adds a new dimension to the strategies for addressing malnutrition. Prevalence of anemia has remained high over years which is a threat to children and women's survival. Some of the contributing factors to this scenario include changing consumption patterns and lifestyles, especially of those living in urban areas.

Generally, there is variation in prevalence of malnutrition across the regions in Tanzania where by other regions with high food production have persistently high prevalence of stunting. Given the various factors associated with malnutrition including social and behavioral aspects, there is a need for specific dietary recommendations according to locality and population eating habits.

In Tanzania, FoodLAND project is implemented in three Food Hubs in Dar es Salaam and Morogoro regions. During implementation, desk review was conducted to gain an insight of the nutritional

situation in the regions where the project is being implemented. In 2021/2022, consumer surveys that involved adults males and females were conducted in Dar es Salaam and Morogoro urban. Furthermore, mother-child pair survey was done in Mvomero district to assess consumption behaviors and child feeding practices. It was observed that the diets for women and children is less diversified with low consumption of animal source foods. Although almost every household was keeping some chicken, eggs were mainly sold and barely given to children. Again, consumption of deep fried foods was observed even in the rural areas. Through desk review and stakeholders consultations, the nutrition recommendations were therefore developed to address the existing gaps in nutrition. The recommendations targeted children and adults with some emphasis for pregnant and lactating women. They range between simple community messages to some of them being at the policy level. The recommendations are expected to help the extension workers, nutrition officers and community health workers to support household members to improve food production and consumption of diversified diets for improved nutritional status.

4.1 Introduction

The United Republic of Tanzania is among the largest countries in East Africa with an estimated current population of 61,741,120. More than a half of the general population are females (31.6 million) (United Republic of Tanzania, URT, 2022). About 15.4% of the population are children under five years, 15% children age 5 to 14 years, 47.3% women of reproductive age (15-49), 53.4% are the working population (15-64 years), 6% elderly population (60 years and above) (NBS, 2022).

The population census conducted in 2022 revealed that about two thirds (40,196,497) and a third (21,544,623) of the Tanzanian population, respectively, live in rural and urban areas (United Republic of Tanzania, URT, 2022). The Demographic and Health Survey and Malaria Indicator survey (TDHS-MIS) report of 2022 suggests that the current national level fertility rate is six (6) in the rural and four (4) in the urban areas.

Since independent to date, majority of Tanzanians depend on agriculture for their livelihoods. In 2020, having had a significant decline in poverty level from 34% in 2007 to 26% in 2018, Tanzania was officially included among lower middle income countries (World Food Programme, 2023). It also achieved well to meet the required level of food due to availability of food surplus (Table 4.1) (URT, 2019).

Table 4.1: National level of food crops production versus requirement for 2018 to 2019

Total	Cereals (Tones)	Non cereals (Tones)	Total (Tones)
Production	9,537,857	7,354,112	16,891,974
Requirement	8,627,273	4,942,012	12,569,285
Gap (+)	910,584	2,412,105	3,322,689

Source: URT, (2019)

National Nutritional Situation

Nutritional status of children below five years

Despite the attained achievements, a significant share of the population is food insecure with a high rate of malnourished especially children under the age of five years and women of reproductive age (WFP, 2023). For example, about 30% of the children under five years are stunted and 9% are severely stunted (Figure 4.2). About 3% of the children are wasted and 12% are underweight (Table 4.2). Only 19% of the children between 6 to 23 months are able to attain a required minimum dietary diversity while 7% and 30% consume unhealthy food and sweet beverage, respectively. Intake of sweet beverage and unhealthy food consumption were higher in urban (48% and 11%, respectively) than in rural (23% and 6%, respectively) (Figure 4.3). However, there is an increase in children who are exclusively breast fed from 32% in 1999 to 64% in 2022 (TDHS-MIS, 2022). Overall prevalence of anaemia among children was 59%, higher prevalence among those of age 6-23 months (73%) compared to those of age 24 to 59 months (52%) (TDHS-MIS 2022).

Table 4.2: National and regional prevalence of malnutrition of children below 5 years of age

Cluster	Stunting (%)		Wasting (%)		Underweight (%)	
	Stunted	Severely stunted	Wasted	Severely	Underweight	Severely
Total	30.0	8.9	3.3	0.9	12.0	2.7
Rural	33.4	10.3	3.1	0.9	12.7	3.0
Urban	21	5.5	3.4	0.9	10.4	1.8

Source: TDHS, (2022)

Figure 4.1: Trend of nutritional status of children below five years of age (TDHS-MIS, 2022)

Figure 4.2: Percentage of children age 6 to 23 months meeting recommended feeding practice and consumption of unhealth foods (TDHS-MIS, 2022)

Although there is a slight decrease, prevalence of anaemia among children has been persistently high. According to TDHS-MIS 2022, about 59% of the children are anemic (Figure 3).

Figure 4.3: Trends of anaemia among children

Nutritional status of women of reproductive age

The Tanzania National Nutrition survey report of 2019 revealed that 31.7% women of reproductive age are overweight, 7.3% and 1.6% of non-pregnant women and pregnant are underweight. In addition, anaemia is still a challenge despite a decline from about 45% in 2015-2016 to 29% in 2019 (TNNS, 2018).

Generally, there is variation in prevalence of malnutrition across the regions in Tanzania where by regions with high food production persistently have high prevalence of stunting. Given the various factors associated with malnutrition, including social and behavioral aspects, there is a need for specific dietary recommendations according to locality and population eating habits. FoodLAND project is being implemented in three Food Hubs, Morogoro (rural and urban) and Dar es Salaam. Hence, the dietary recommendations will focus on the three Food Hubs where food consumption data were collected (urban and rural consumer surveys implemented in WP2).

Objectives

Overall Objective: **Overall Objective:** To formulate nutritional recommendations that are relevant, suitable and feasible within the rural and urban Tanzanian Food Hubs

Specific Objectives

- (i) To establish the situational architecture to inform nutritional recommendations
- (ii) To develop nutritional recommendations based on the food consumption habits and nutrient gaps in the Food Hubs
- (iii) To document the protocols used in the development of the nutritional recommendations

4.2 Protocol for nutritional recommendations

The process for the development of nutritional recommendations followed the steps listed below:

- Conducting a systematic literature review to identify the existing nutritional gaps from previous studies done at both the national and the Food Hub levels.
- For the purpose of identifying nutritional gaps existing in the project Food Hubs, the project collected consumer data among both rural and urban populations. The data were analyzed to identify food consumption habits and dietary behaviors in the respective Food Hubs. Nutritional gaps and factors contributing to the observed consumption were identified from the survey data and the literature on nutritional situation which was conducted as a deliverable in WP 2.4. A total of 512 women of reproductive age (15 to 49 years) with a child age 6 to 23 months were interviewed to represent rural consumers (Mvomero). In urban Morogoro and Dar es Salaam, the surveys involved both women and men aged 18 or more years who are responsible for buying food groceries for home consumption. In Morogoro urban, a total number of 474 consumers were interviewed and 432 consumers for Dar es Salaam.
- Review of other nutritional recommendations that exist in the country such as Tanzania Food Based dietary Guidelines, Infant and Young Child feeding guideline, Guideline for School feeding and guideline for adolescents nutrition.
- Nutritional recommendations were drafted based on the reviews as well as problem identified from the Food Hubs.

- To obtain more recommendations different stakeholders such as health service providers, from cascaded health institutions such as dispensaries, nutrition officers, agricultural extension officers and community representatives were sensitized on the identified nutritional problems and requested to provide recommendations on how they can be alleviated.
- Information collected from the stakeholders was used to update the recommendations proposed by FoodLAND.

4.3 Situational Architecture

FoodLAND project aims to develop, implement and validate innovative, scalable and sustainable technologies. The technologies aim at supporting the nutrition performance of local food systems in Africa, while strengthening agro-biodiversity, food diversity and diversity of healthy diets. In Tanzania, the project is implemented in two regions, Morogoro rural (Kilombero and Mvomero districts) and urban (Morogoro municipality) and in Dar es Salaam. (Figure 4.4). The project started by assessing consumers’ and producers’ preferences and behaviors and the food-related decision-making processes and factors.

Figure 4.4: Foodhubs map (Morogoro urban, Mvomero and Dar es Salaam urban)

Description of the study areas

Dar es Salaam profile

Dar es salaam is one among the regions in Tanzania characterised with growth of economic activities, availability of social services and high population due to rural urban migration (Todd *et al.*, 2019). The region is the centre of Tanzania's industries, finance and administration. Based on the current census report of 2022, there is an increase in population from 4.3 million in 2012 census to 5.4 million in 2022 that account to about 9% of overall country population (URT, 2022). In terms of population distribution, about 31.5% of the population are children below 15 years, 66% are the working population age between 15 to 64 years, 2.4% are dependency with age above 64 years (URT,2022). Dar es Salaam has a total of 684 health services facilities and 1188 secondary and primary schools (URT, 2023). Despite availability of social services and business opportunities the problem of malnutrition among children under five is still alarming, as the recently Demographic and Health Survey report, (2022) show that approximately 18% of children are stunted while 4.3% are wasted, 10% underweight and 70% are anemic.

On average majority of children aged between 6 to 23 months consumed at least 3 food groups only 29% are able to meet a recommended minimum dietary diversity with a consumption of at least 4 food groups. Moreover, the level of nutrition status among women of reproductive age is also unsatisfactory due to high level of obesity (24%) and 6.4% are underweight. Out of 209 pregnant women only 34% were able to take iron folic acid supplements for more than 90 days, while 14% did not take any iron folic acid despite of been aware of its nutrition benefits while 6% are not aware of its existence (Table 4) (TNNS, 2018).

Morogoro Profile

The region is located in the Mid – Eastern part of Tanzania mainland. Administratively, Morogoro Region is divided into nine districts councils namely, Kilosa, Ulanga, Morogoro, Morogoro municipality, Mvomero, Gairo, Ifakara, Malinyi and Mlimba. The 2012 Population and Housing Census shows the total population of Morogoro region in 2012 was about 2.2 million. Out of that, 71.3 percent (1.5 million) were residing in rural areas and 28.7 percent (0.6 million) resided in urban areas. Also the Census results and 2020 population projection shows that population growth rate of Morogoro region from 2012 to 2020 was 3.0 percent. In rural areas, the population growth rate was 2.1 percent while in urban areas the population growth rate was 2.9 percent. Population projection of 2019 shows that Morogoro region has population of 2,744,933 with almost equal number of males and females (Morogoro Region Socioeconomic Profile, 2020). About 41 percent of the region's population were children aged less than 15 years, 4.3 percent were the elderly aged population (65 years and above), while 54.4 percent were the working age group (15 – 64 years) according to the 2012 Population Census A variety of crops is grown in this zone. Food crops are mainly maize, Irish potatoes, banana, peas, yams, beans, groundnuts, wheat, cassava and horticultural crops. Major cash crops include coffee, oil seeds, vegetables and fruits such as pineapple and oranges. About 62 percent of the households in Morogoro region had access to improved drinking water sources and 38 percent of households had access to unimproved water sources.

According to the Tanzania Demographic Health Survey and Malaria Indicator Survey, prevalence of chronic malnutrition in Morogoro region is high at about 31% similar to the national average with an

estimated wasting rate of 4% which is above the national average and underweight of 10%. Studies show that undernutrition is particularly high among low-income rural Tanzanian households, mainly because they consume carbohydrate-rich, staple-based diets low in minerals and vitamins (Madzorera *et al.*, 2021, MoH *et al.*, 2023). The Tanzania National Nutritional Health Survey report of 2018 (TNNS, 2018) data show that out of 176 pregnant women, 29% consumed iron folic acid supplements for more than 90 days, 11% did not take any iron folic acid supplements while 9% of the pregnant women were not aware of its availability (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3: Intake of Iron Folic Acid Supplements

Region	none (%)	<60days (%)	60-89 days (%)	90 days (%)	don't know
Dar es salaam	14	34	12	34	6
Morogoro	11	37	14	29	9

Source: TNNS, (2018).

Mvomero Profile

Mvomero is one among Morogoro region district located at latitude 06°26' South and longitude 37°32' East (URT, 2017). Based on the current population census the total population for the district is 421, 741 almost equal number of males and females; and 110,940 households (United Republic of Tanzania, URT, 2022). Some of the economic activities taking place in the area includes agricultural (some of the crops grown includes maize, millet, cassava, sweet potatoes, beans, rice, sugar cane, cotton, and vegetables), fishing, mining, quarrying and livestock keeping. About three out of 4 of the residents are employed in agricultural and majority are small-scale farmers while 3.2% are employed in livestock keeping, fishing, and hunting. The District has 71 health facilities 3 are hospital, 8 health centres and 60 dispensaries. In terms of education services Mvomero district has a total of 141 primary schools, 24 secondary schools and 4 vocational training centres (URT, 2017). Despite of its agriculture potentiality, the problem of food insecurity is still a challenge among residents. In 2017 about 62% of children aged below five years were reported to experience cough problem, 15% diarrhoea and 31 fever that was high than the national average. The District was identified to have a high prevalence of Global Acute Malnutrition of about 8% that was due to inadequate food consumption (Comprehensive Food Security and Nutrition Assessment Report, 2017).

Nutritional gaps for actions

Previous research (Literature review- Deliverable D 2.5)

Nutrition problems and food consumption patterns reported in different studies conducted in Tanzania varied across population groups. On this report, nutrition gaps considered are more focused on selected regions where FoodLAND Food-Hubs are located. The stated problems are across all settings; rural and urban, age groups, ethnicity, and gender.

Children of age 0 – 6 months

In Dar es Salaam, there is a poor practice of breastfeeding (BF) initiation within one hour after birth to almost half of the population (51%) and exclusive BF is merely practiced (9.1%) as reported in TDHS 2015/16. Similar problem was reported in Morogoro, 63.2% of newborns were initiated to BF within 1 hour after birth, and only 12.4% of children were exclusively breastfed. The lowest the wealth quantile and education level of the mother the higher the percentage of children who were not breastfed within one hour of birth and exclusively breastfed. Due to poverty, women tend to prioritize most of their time in income generation activities; this affects their involvement on EBF their children. Also, low education level can affect adherence of mothers to health and nutrition recommended practices provided during RCH visits through nutrition counselling sessions. Formal education has an influence on individual's critical thinking capacity and level of understanding.

Children of age 6 – 59 months

When an infant reaches six months of age, a need for energy and nutrients starts to exceed what is provided by breast milk. Hence, it is crucial to introduce complementary foods to meet those needs. In order for energy and nutrients needs to be met mothers/caregivers must adhere to the Infants and Young child feeding (IYCF) recommended practices. In Dar es Salaam, this was poorly practiced, it was reported in TDHS 2015/16 that only 16% of the mothers with children of aged 6 to 23 months practiced at least 3 IYCF recommended practices, while in Morogoro it was less practiced (5.2%). In Dar es Salaam, more than half of the population (52.5%) did not meet the minimum dietary diversity requirement, similar to the study findings by (Vitta et al., 2016) who reported only 49% of children age 6–23 months met the minimum dietary diversity requirement in the same region. The situation was reported worse in Morogoro, only 19.4% of children aged 6 to 23 months consumed 4 or more food groups. In both regions only 4 out of 10 children met the required minimum meal frequency. In Dar es Salaam 61% and 89% of children aged 6 to 23 months had consumed iron rich foods and vitamin A rich foods respectively in the past 24 hours. In comparison, the lower percentage of children consuming iron rich foods and vitamin A rich foods was reported in Morogoro (13.4% and 67.2% respectively). This partly explains higher anaemia prevalence among children aged 6 to 59 months in Morogoro (66%) than in Dar es Salaam (60%); both a severe public health concern. Also, limited adherence to intake of deworming medication (59.5% and 49.2%) in Dar es Salaam and in Morogoro respectively) and micronutrients supplementation (2.6% and 2.3% received iron supplement; 49.5% and 51.2% received vitamin A supplement, in Dar es Salaam and Morogoro respectively). Stunting and underweight prevalence in Dar es Salaam are low (18.4% and 9.7% respectively) as reported in preliminary findings in TDHS-MIS 2022, however, it has increased by 3.8% and 3.3% respectively compared to prevalence reported in TDHS 2015/16. This indicates the continuity of poor child care practices that affects proper IYCF practices among children under the age of five years. On other hand, in Morogoro, there is a decrease in stunting, wasting and underweight prevalence compared to the previous TDHS report (MoHCDGEC et al., 2016). Despite the decrease of stated malnutrition indicators, more interventions are required as stunting is still a public health concern (31%).

The introduction of complementary foods before the recommended time together with the poor quality of foods provided to children both aged below 6 months and above negatively affect the children's nutrition statuses. In TDHS 2015/16 wealth quantile and education level was reported to have an influence on IYCF practices. In Tanzanian communities, the role for child care is primarily mother's; therefore the engagement of mothers with young children in economic activities limits their

time for childcare. Might be in terms of not been able to afford diverse foods or lack of enough time to prepare appropriate meals, feeding of children, and visit the RCH clinics for child growth monitoring and acquire nutrition counselling. In urban settings such Dar es Salaam and Morogoro urban mothers with higher levels of wealth quantile and education are likely to adhere to the IYCF recommended practices. The higher the education level the more likelihood to have better economic status due to opportunities for employment, improve their access to diverse foods and childcare assistance. On the other hand, lack of nutrition awareness might be contributing to the increased malnutrition prevalence. Though nutrition counselling recommended is to be provided during each RCH visits according to WHO recommendations, some studies have reported that nutrition counselling is the least provided service during visits in developing countries (Billah et al., 2022; Ghosh-Jerath et al., 2015; Kaleem et al., 2020; Torlesse et al., 2021).

School aged children and Adolescents

There is limited number of studies targeting adolescents in the country, most of them include adolescents with school aged children. It was reported in 2019 School Malaria and Nutrition Survey that children aged 5 to 19 years consumed only 2 out of 5 food groups per week. In Morogoro, (Chen, 2012) reported the low dietary diversification practice among adolescent females (10 to 19 years) with the mean dietary diversity of 3 ± 0.9 . Similarly, a study conducted in rural Morogoro by (Stuetz et al., 2019) among children 6 to 9 years indicated low intake of fruits (19%) and vegetables (29%) as well as vitamin A rich fruits/vegetables (34%). The higher levels of consumption of different food groups were consistently observed in Dar es Salaam region (Ministry of Health Community Development Gender Elderly and Children (MoHCDGEC), 2021). The region has high overweight and obesity prevalence (13% and 3.2% respectively) among children 5 to 19 years than Morogoro (6.8% and 1.3%) (Ministry of Health Community Development Gender Elderly and Children (MoHCDGEC), 2021). Due to urbanization, Dar es Salaam do not produce much food, however the city has access to almost all types of foods. As children ascend from childhood to adolescence their food habits changes and the gain independence in food choices. Hence, their food choices rely on the level of nutrition awareness, food available within their surroundings and access to them. Different studies mentioned snacking as common practice among adolescents especially females, mostly the energy dense snacks with empty calories, explaining the overweight/obesity prevalence. In SMNS 2019 report, 65.9% of school aged children and adolescents in Dar es Salaam were reported to consume snacks at school almost everyday, the highest percentage compared to other regions in the country. No micronutrients deficiencies reported, however, 33.7% of children were anaemic with higher anaemia prevalence among adolescents (56.6%) than younger children (33.1%). This might be attributed to the increased micronutrients requirements and significant iron loss experienced by girls due menstruation in adolescence.

Women of reproductive age (WRA)

In TDHS 2015/16 Dar es Salaam was reported as a region with leading prevalence of overweight/obese (47%) among the WRA. Also, about half of WRA (53%) were anaemic. High overweight, obesity and anaemia prevalence might be due to poor dietary diversity practices among WRA. A study conducted by Madzorera *et al.*, 2020 reported a median dietary diversity of 3.0 among WRA in Dar es Salaam. As a result the presence of urban poor living within the city, low wealth quantile might attribute to poor dietary diversification. The little earning obtained is allocated in purchasing of food to satisfy hunger

and not much attention is on the nutrition quality of food. In Morogoro, (Stuetz et al., 2019) reported overweight and obesity prevalence of (23.4% and 10.2% respectively) higher than underweight prevalence (4.8%) among WRA. Same to Dar es Salaam, anaemia is a public health concern among WRA in Morogoro (47.3%).

Pregnant and lactating women

Anaemia among pregnant women has always been a problem, in the country there was 57% anaemia prevalence which is higher than that of lactating mothers and women who neither breastfeed nor lactating (TDHS 2015/16). In Dar es Salaam, 84% of pregnant women took iron tablets or syrup at any time of their pregnancies. However, despite from having many hospitals, healthcare centres and dispensaries, only 29% of pregnant women took iron tablets or syrup for more than 90 days during their pregnancy. Currently in preliminary findings reported in TDHS 2022 there is a percentage decline of pregnant women who took iron supplements at any time during pregnancies (84%). Adherence to daily intake of iron supplement remains questionable as the anaemia prevalence is still high. Factors such as history of abortion, nutrition education awareness, and proper service provision during ANC visits have been reported to influence iron supplement intake adherence in developing countries (Assefa *et al.*, 2019; Titilayo *et al.*, 2016). Barriers to supplementation adherence commonly reported in developing countries include bad taste, experienced nausea, constipation, dark colour of the stool, and vomiting (Mshanga & Masetta, 2022). Studies concerning lactating women are limited in the country. Most studies are focused on the breastfed infants leaving out the breastfeeding mothers.

Adult men

Limited number of studies targeting adult males have been conducted in the country. In Dar es Salaam, a study conducted by Majili *et al.*, (2017) among adults aged 25 to 64 reported more than 50% of the subjects consumed at least 8 food groups; indicating good dietary diversification practices. However, roots and tubers were less consumed followed by ASF specifically eggs and milk and milk products. High consumption of fruits and vegetables was reported among adult men, 89% and 92% respectively. Fruits and vegetables are important since they play a big role as NCD protective foods. Contrary to Dar es Salaam, low fruits consumption (26% and 21.4% respectively) among adults 18 years and above was reported in studies conducted by (Kinabo et al., 2016) and (Minja et al., 2021) in Morogoro. (Kinabo et al., 2016) reported less energy and nutrient intake adequacy (except for iron and zinc) from foods consumed by males compared to females in Morogoro urban. Also, energy and nutrients intakes among male adults from Morogoro urban was less compared to other Morogoro councils under the study.

Elderly persons

A study conducted in Dar es Salaam by (Balegu, 2014)) reported fruits and vegetable consumption as a problem among elderly. The study reported the mean fruits and vegetable consumption of 2.61 ± 1.19 servings per day among elderlies aged 60 to 95 which was lower than the WHO recommendation of at least five serving (400g) daily intake. The intake varied greatly with economic status ($p < 0.001$).

General household

Mean HDDS reported in a study conducted by (Kinabo et al., 2016) was five, indicating households meet the minimum recommended dietary diversification. However, cereals have been reported as the

most frequently consumed food group by households while animal source foods consumed the least, especially eggs. Similar findings were reported by (Minja et al., 2021) whereby cereals were consumed by 99.7% of the households followed by oil and fats (98.9%). Furthermore, the majority of households consumed 4-6 food groups; medium dietary diversification (Minja et al., 2021).

FoodLAND findings

Study on rural Consumers (Age, Education and Income) (Deliverable D2.4)

Respondents Age

The average age of respondents was 26 years old, minimum 16 years and maximum 49 years. Majority were of age range 16 to 25 years. Of 512 respondents, 52% were able to attain a primary education while 41% had no formal education (Table 4.4). This means that half of the respondents have the ability to read and write thus any agricultural and nutrition intervention should consider the level of education in a study area.

Table 4.4: Respondents level of education

Levels	Observation (n)	Percent
Illiterate	209	40.82
No qualification/literate	6	1.17
Primary	266	51.95
Secondary	29	5.66
More than secondary	2	0.39

Respondents Income

The average household income generated from agricultural was higher than all other sources. This suggest that majority of the respondents depends on agricultural for their live hoods and income followed by non-farm activities (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5: Household income from different sources

Sources	Mean	St.Dev.	Min	Median	Max
Farm income	69,565	101,293	0	30,000	1,00,000
Non-farm income	43,361	80,843	0	10,000	600,000
Remittances	1,591	9,921	0	0	180,000
Subsidy/aid	1,414	9,663	0	0	160,000

Food groups consumed among women of reproductive age (Rural).

The major food groups consumed were starchy staple foods made from grains, dark green vegetables, other vegetables (72%) and legumes; with low consumption of animal source foods such as milk, fish, beef and eggs. A high consumption of cereals, vegetables and legumes is due to availability as a large proportion is produced within the household. The results also revealed that there is a high consumption of deep fried foods (33%) and sweetened tea/coffees/ milk drink (35%) that can increase risk for Non communicable diseases (Table 4.6).

Table 4.6: Foods and drinks consumed by women of reproductive age

Food categories	n	% respondents	Food categories	n	% Respondents
Staple Foods Made From Grains	470	91.8	Unprocessed Red Meat (Ruminant)	29	5.6
Whole Grains	82	16.2	Unprocessed Red Meat (Non-Ruminant)	9	1.8
White Roots/Tubers	189	36.9	Poultry	11	2.12
Legumes	226	44.1	Fish & Seafood	145	28.3
Vitamin A-Rich Orange Veg	16	3.1	Nuts & Seeds	54	10.6
Dark Green Leafy Vegetables	362	70.7	Ultra-Processed Packaged Salty Snacks	8	1.4
Other Vegetables	370	72.3	Instant Noodles	2	0.4
Vitamin A-Rich Fruits	126	24.6	Deep Fried Foods	168	32.8
Citrus	17	3.3	Fluid Milk	22	4.3
Other Fruits	164	32.0	Sweetened Tea/Coffee/Milk Drinks	178	34.8
Grain Sweets	77	15.4	Fruit Juice	36	7.0
Other Sweets	44	8.6	SSBS (Sodas)	27	5.3
Eggs	14	2.7	Fast Food	8	1.4
Cheese	2	0.4			
Yogurt	13	2.5			
Processed Meat	0	0			

Food groups consumed for children 6-23 months (Rural)

There was no different in food consumption pattern between children and mothers. High proportion of children consumed staple foods made from grains (82%) and used vegetables as a relish. Only about 10% of the children consumed milk and majority of the children were still breastfed (88%). However, less than 5% ate eggs or poultry in a day preceding the survey (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7: Food and drinks consumed by children age 6 to 23 months

Food groups	n	%	Food groups	n	%
Staple Foods Made From Grains	41	82	Unprocessed Red Meat (Ruminant)	24	5
Whole Grains	12	25	Unprocessed Red Meat (Non-Ruminant)	6	1
White Roots/Tubers	91	18	Poultry	9	2
Legumes	18	36	Fish & Seafood	10	21
Vitamin A-Rich Orange Veg	6	1	Nuts & Seeds	38	7
Dark Green Leafy Vegetables	27	54	Ultra-Processed Packaged Salty Snacks	2	0
Other Vegetables	28	56	Instant Noodles	1	0
Vitamin A-Rich Fruits	10	20	Deep Fried Foods	13	27
Citrus	13	3	Fluid Milk	50	10
Other Fruits	13	26	Sweetened Tea/Coffee/Milk Drinks	11	23
Grain Sweets	73	14	27 Fruit Juice	10	21
Other Sweets	64	13	28 Ssbs (Sodas)	12	2
Eggs	13	3	29 Fast Food	0	0
Cheese	1	0			
Yogurt	8	2			
Processed Meat	0	0			

Women and child dietary diversity

Regarding the categories of dietary diversity, the results show that both children and their mother had a minimal dietary diversity with a consumption of less than four food groups. However, a high percent of minimal dietary diversity was observed to children (78) compared to women (66%). Only 34% and 21% of children and women respectively were able to attain a medium dietary diversity (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Dietary diversity categories for women of reproductive age and children

Consumption of NCD-Protective and Risk for women of reproductive age

Comparing with mother’s and child consumption, results show no differences in food consumption pattern between women and children. Foods such as vegetables, fruits and pulses were the common NCD-protective food groups consumed while NCD risk food groups a high consumption was observed in grain sweet baked foods and deep fried foods (Table 4.8)

Table 4.8: Number and proportion of women and children who consumed specific NCD-protect and NCD-risk food groups

NCD Protect food groups	Mothers		Child		NCD Risk food groups	Mothers		Child	
	n	%	n	%		n	%	n	%
Whole grains	83	16	128	25	Sugar sweetened beverages	29	6	12	2
Pulse	227	44	182	36	Grains sweet baked foods	78	15	73	14
Nuts and seeds	56	11	38	7	Other sweet	45	9	64	13
Vitamin A rich orange vegetables	16	3	6	1	Processed meat	0	100	0	100
Dark green leafy vegetables	361	71	279	55	Unprocessed red meat	38	7	30	6
Other vegetables	371	72	286	56	Deep-fried foods	169	33	137	27
Vitamin A rich fruits	127	25	103	20	Fast foods and instant noodles	2	0.03	2	0
Citrus	17	3	13	3	Processed packed salty snacks	2	0.03	2	0
Other fruits	165	32	135	26					

NCD Protective for Women and Children

The results show that more than 50% of the children consumed <3 protective food groups and only 8% consumed more than 4 food groups. Majority of women have a minimal protection with a consumption of less than 3 NCD protective food groups (58%) (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: NCD Protective categories for women and children

NCD risk for women and children

More than 90% of the women and children had NCD-risk scores of less than 3 hence low risk for NCDs (Figure 4.7). Although this result does not imply low risk of NCD, due consumption of risk food groups.

Figure 4.7: NCD Risk for women and children

Other child feeding practices

Breastfeeding is one of the ways to ensure child healthy and survival. World Health organization (WHO) and the United Nations International Children’s emergency Funds (UNICEF) recommends that all children should be breastfed, and initiation of breast feeding should be done immediately within one hour after delivery. In the survey done in these rural communities, all children were breastfed and 3 out of 4 (75%) were put on the breast within one hour after birth (Table 4.9). Most women fed their children breast milk alone within two days after delivery which means colostrum feeding was highly practiced with only a few (3.5%, n=18) who offered the infants with prelacteal feeds. All children were still breastfeeding either during the day or at night but about 26% gave their children something to

drink in a bottle with nipple. Almost all children (95%, n=486) were given something to drink in a day preceding the survey. Other common drinks were clear broth or clear soup (30.3%), fruit juice or flavored fruit drink (21.1%) and tea, coffee or herbal drink (20.7%). Surprisingly, milk was not among

Table 4.9: Breast feeding practices

	Breast feeding time	Observations	Percent
	Immediately after birth	156	30.47
Breast feeding	Before one hour	226	44.14
	Before 24 hours	123	24.02
	More than 24 hours	7	1.37
	No	376	73.44
Bottle feeding	Yes	136	26.56

Study on urban Consumers (Age, Education and Income) (Deliverable D2.4)

Respondents age

Descriptive results show that, average age of the respondents was 34.6 and 37.2 with a maximum age of 83 years and 75 years for Morogoro and Dar es salaam respectively. Majority of respondents were between 26 to 35 years (321), 36 to 45 years (236), 18 to 25 years (189) and few above 45 years (169) (Table 4.10).

Table 4.10: Distribution of respondents by age categories

Food Hubs	Age categories (years)			
	18-25	26-35	36-45	>45
Dares salaam	65	141	141	85
Morogoro	124	171	95	84
Total	189	312	236	169

Respondents Education

The results show that majority of respondents have attained a formal education. About 38.4 of the respondents in Dar es salaam, 42% in Morogoro had attained primary education. Only few respondents had no formal education that is 2% and 0.6% for Dar es salaam and Morogoro respectively (Figure 4.8). This implies the rate of illiteracy in urban is low compared to rural area. The results are consistent with the current situation as majority of the schools are located in urban compared to rural and this gives more opportunity for urban households to have access of such services compare to rural.

Figure 4.8: Respondents level of education

Gender of respondents

More than half of the respondents were females which means that women are more responsible in making household consumption decisions regarding food consumption compared to men (Table 4.11).

Table 4.11: Gender of respondents

Food Hubs	Male	Female
Dar es Salaam	43.98	56.02
Morogoro	48.10	51.90
Total	46.14	53.86

Respondents Income

Descriptive results show that there is a big income gap between the two regions. A large percent of respondents in Morogoro had a low income (42.4%) compared to Dar es salaam (24.8%) (Figure 4.9). The big difference in income in the two regions can be caused presence of business opportunities available in as Dar es Salaam compared to Morogoro.

Figure 4.9: Respondents income categories by Food Hubs

Food groups consumed and dietary diversity categories among household in urban Morogoro and Dar es Salaam.

In both regions, high proportion of the households consumed vegetables, staple foods made from grains, vitamin A-rich orange vegetables, dark green leafy vegetables. Foods such as whole grains, citrus, white roots and tubers, nuts and seeds, poultry, eggs, milk and milk products are consumed at low rate in both Food Hubs.

Household dietary diversity

In terms of Household Dietary Diversity Scores (HDDS), both regions had attained minimum dietary diversity at the time of survey based on the past 24 hours' recall. On average the mean HDDS was 7.8 for Morogoro and 7.7 for Dar es Salaam (Table 4.12). This implies that both urban localities had access to various groups of food.

Table 4.12: Household dietary diversity

Regions	N (%)	Mean (sd.dev)	Median
Dar es Salaam	432 (47.7)	7.69 (2.29)	8.0
Morogoro	474 (52.3)	7.79 (2.15)	8.0
Total	906 (100.0)	7.74 (2.22)	8.0

The level of dietary diversity was categorized into three groups namely low, medium and high dietary diversity. The results show that majority of households in Morogoro attain a medium dietary diversity (57%) compared to Dar es Salaam (53%) (Figure 4.10).

Figure 4.10: Dietary diversity categories for Morogoro and Dar es Salaam

Minimum dietary diversity among women of reproductive age

Unlike rural women, dietary diversity the results show that majority of women in urban area attain a required minimum dietary diversity with a consumption of at least six food groups. (Table 4.13).

Table 4.13: Minimum dietary diversity for women of reproductive age, Urban

Food Hubs	Yes		No	
	n	%	N	%
Dar es Salaam	18	88	26	12
Morogoro	199	95	10	5
Total	386	91.5	36	8.5

Consumption of NCD-Protective and Risk food groups for Morogoro and Dar es Salaam

The results show that majority of Morogoro respondents consumed vegetables, and cereal grains. Some of the risk food groups consumed includes deep fried foods unprocessed red meat and sugar sweetened beverages. In Dar es Salaam major protective food groups consumed are vegetables, vitamin A rich orange vegetables other fruits and vitamin A rich fruits while low intake was observed to other food groups such as citrus, nuts and seeds and whole grains. In term of risk food groups the results show a high consumption of unprocessed red meat, deep fried foods and sugar sweetened beverages for Dar es Salaam.

NCD-Protective categories for Morogoro and Dar es Salaam

Regarding NCD protect categories, majority of consumers (71%) fall under in high NCD protection categories followed by medium protection (23%) and few in minimal protection (6%) for Dar es Salaam. While in Morogoro Food Hub 50% of consumers were in high NCD protect categories followed by medium protection (37%) and few in minimal protection (13%) (Figure 4.11).

Figure 4.11: NCD-Protective categories for urban consumers

NCD-Risk categories for Morogoro and Dar es Salaam.

The results also suggest that only few consumers are in risk of getting NCD (7% and 6%) for Morogoro and Dar es Salaam respectively. However consumption of risk food groups was lower in Dar es Salaam as majority of consumers falls under a minimal risk category (71%) compared to Morogoro (67%) (Figure 4.12). Although, the results do not mean absence of exposure to other NCD risk foods due to high consumption of risk food groups such as deep fried foods and unprocessed red meat.

Figure 4.12: NCD Risk categories for urban consumers

NCD Protective and Risk categories for women of reproductive age between urban and rural.

When comparing NCD protect categories, 48% of women in rural had a minimal protection compared to those from the urban while 10% in rural and to 69% in the urban fall under the high protect with a consumption of at least 5 NCD-protect food groups for rural and urban respectively (Figure 4.13).

Figure 4.13: Women NCD Protective categories for Rural and Urban

Regarding NCD risk categories, a high proportion was found among women with a minimal risk category in rural (94%) compared to urban women (69%) (Figure 4.14).

Figure 4.14: Women NCD Risk categories for Rural and Urban

Summary of nutritional problems and gaps

The commonly observed nutritional problems include undernutrition, overweight and obesity among all age groups. It was also observed that micronutrient deficiencies such as anaemia are highly prevalent mainly among women of reproductive age and children below five years. In addition, low diversified diet is common among women of reproductive age and children below two years which could be the reason for the observed high rates of malnutrition. It was further observed that there is inadequate child feeding practices which could be associated with poverty, food insecurity and education level especially among rural households. The differences in nutrition status and food consumption behaviour were obvious among rural and urban areas and also variations were observed in Morogoro urban and Dar es Salaam. There is limited information on nutrition status among men, school children and adolescents. This calls for further research.

4.4 Nutritional Recommendations

Based on the observed situation analysis and results from rural and urban consumers, the following are the recommendations for the different age groups.

4.4.1 Children less than six months

- Monitoring of after delivery services provided in hospitals and health facilities to ensure larger proportional of women practicing early initiation of BF within 1 hour after delivery.
- Promote exclusive breastfeeding, feeding of colostrum to newborns and discourage bottle-feeding
- Monitoring provision of ANC and RHC services especially nutrition counselling to mothers as well as their escorts such as partners and relatives.

- Creating adequate nutrition awareness among people close to BF mothers will influence the provision of all necessary support to allow the mothers to practice BF adequately.
- Conduct outreach sessions in community level for nutrition counselling. This can also be done at work places in order to increase the proportion of individuals with nutritional awareness. This will sensitize the community to provide different forms of support to breastfeeding mothers in their respective communities.

4.4.2 Children 6-<59 months

- Promote recommended IYCF practices:
 - o Government should create a system for a close monitoring of nutrition related services provided during RCH visits, especially nutrition counselling. Quality nutrition counselling should be provided to the mother/caregiver-child pair to create awareness about the recommended IYCF practices as well as the outcomes of non-adherence to their children.
 - o Conduct community-based nutrition counselling to promote adherence of the recommended IYCF practices
 - o Provide RCH outreach services: This should be conducted not only to people living at the peripherals, but also at work places, such as in markets especially in urban settings. This will keep working mothers and caregiver updated on about child nutrition issues.
- Promote height assessment during growth monitoring for under 5 children; this would help early detection of stunting among children.
- Continue BF up to 24 months
- After six months, give children variety of foods from the 6 food groups (include eggs, at least three times per week)
- Ensure safe and clean drinking water

4.4.3 School going children and adolescents

- Promote the availability of health diets around school environment;
 - o Development of school feeding guideline, which should be used under strict supervision and monitoring to promote healthy diets around school environments.
 - o Extra curriculum activities especially in secondary schools that focuses on food production such as gardening and livestock keeping should be applied in schools in order to increase the consumption frequency of fruits, vegetables and animal proteins.
 - o Promotion of the use of fortified foods for adolescents in schools as well as at homes.
 - o Develop a guide to smart snack in schools, in order to limit unhealthy snacks consumption. Strict monitoring to ensure all snacks sold in schools comply with the guideline.

- Promote physical activities for weight management among school aged children and adolescents
- Basic nutrition education should be provided in all schools, from primary to secondary and advocate for making informed decisions for better food choices.
- Nutrition interventions targeting adolescents should be developed and implemented for improved adolescents nutrition
- Make use of social networks and printed media such as posters and brochures to deliver nutrition related messages among adolescents and school-aged children
- Promote inclusion of healthy snacks
- Limit intake of deep-fried foods and sweetened beverages
- Avoid intake of energy drinks

4.4.4 Women of reproductive age, pregnant, lactating and teenage mothers

Women of reproductive age (WRA) – Non pregnant

- Create nutrition awareness among WRA:
 - Nutrition counselling should be done from secondary schools, universities to work places emphasizing on consumption of iron rich foods along with iron absorption enhancers, as well as the consumption of foods rich in vitamin C, A, B12 and B9.
 - The counselling should also focus on advocate limited consumption of unhealthy foods that contribute to weight gain and pose NCD risks.
 - Also, the population group should be made aware on the importance of using of IFA supplements when planning to conceive.
 - They should further be informed on the importance of daily supplementation during pregnancy, and after delivery
- Promote the use of diversified foods among women of reproductive age
- Promote physical activities for weight management, at community level such as in different institutions and companies.
- Make use of mass media;
- Develop different jingles advocating for healthy eating and nutrition practices among WRA
- Broadcast television and radio sessions to create nutrition awareness among the population and the community
- Eat diversified diet for your health and the baby
- Include fruits and vegetables in your daily meals
- Include vitamin C rich fruits e.g. passion, baobab, tamarind or oranges for better absorption of iron from plant source foods
- Wild fruits e.g. *embe ng'ongo (ambarella)*, tamarind, baobab, java plum (*zambarau*), guava, lemon
- Limit intake of SSBs

Pregnant and lactating women

- Avoid deep fried foods, sugar sweetened beverages (SSBs) and foods high in salt
- Take IFAS supplements

- Eat diversified foods from all six food groups
- Used iodized salt
- Avoid alcohol intake and tobacco use
- Eat diversified food
- Promote recommended nutrition practices during practices and lactation:
 - o Close monitoring of RCH services should be conducted for both a child and the lactating mother.
- Quality nutrition counselling should be provided to the mother; Nutrition counselling should also advocate for daily intake of iron containing supplements and provide thorough explanation on its role towards pregnancy outcomes.
- Nutrition assessment of lactating women; the nutrition status of lactating women should be monitored during RCH visits.
- Implementation research should be conducted to assess the compliance of multiple micronutrients supplement, against IFA supplementation.
- Emphasize the implementation of BF policy across all sectors in the country for improved exclusive breastfeeding rates.
- Emphasize the use of iron supplement 3 months postpartum

4.4.5 Adult men

- Nutrition interventions targeting improving men nutrition should be designed and implemented;
 - o Nutrition assessment and counselling specially to emphasize the increased consumption of animal protein and maintain fruits and vegetables consumption.

4.4.6 Elderly persons

- Health and nutrition assessment specific programs should be designed and implemented to ensure routine checkup on elderly
- The government should introduce and monitor waiver on provision of health and nutrition related services among elderly individuals.

4.4.7 General Household

- Keep small and eat small animals e.g. rabbit, poultry
- Start you own fish pond
- Make your own vegetable garden
- Government should control the food price especially for fruits and animal source foods (ASF) to prevent excessive prices fluctuations that would affect the purchasing power of the population and hinder access to diverse foods
- Emphasize home gardening practice for fruits and vegetables production in order to maintain daily fruits/vegetables consumption regardless number of children a woman has.
- Promote small animal keeping to improve the availability of more diversified foods at household level

- Emphasize on the consumption of produced foods by the household in order to improve dietary diversification, especially the ASF whose consumption is affected by the level of income for food.
- Create nutrition awareness within the community about the nutritive value of foods, to enable an individual make an informed decision when considering types of foods to purchasing.
- Make use of multi-media to deliver nutrition related messages to the community
- Promote the use of family planning methods among women and men, in order to increase the potential of the parent(s) to provide their children with diversified diets.

4.4.8 Nutritional recommendations based on FoodLAND generated technologies

- Promote keeping small animals and fish to ensure availability of animal source foods
- Promote production and consumption of fortified and biofortified food
- Encourage Reading food labels to identify unhealthy foods

4.4.9 Nutritional recommendations based on diet quality indicators: NCD -protect/risk

- Make effective use of multi-media to advocate for increased consumption of food groups which are protective from NCD and reduce the consumption of those with potential to pose NCD risks.
- Promote the availability of NCD protective food groups around working areas
- Promote the production and consumption of NCD protective food groups in household level; such as Whole grains, Pulses, Nuts and seeds, Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables, Dark green leafy vegetables, Other vegetables, Vitamin A-rich fruits, Citrus, Other fruits
- Create food and nutrition awareness among WRA about proper food preparation and processing for targeted nutrients preservation
- Formation of young mothers nutrition groups for nutrition counselling in order to improve their nutrition awareness including restriction consumption of food groups with NCD
- Create awareness concerning NCD protect and risk food groups during street/village assemblies, such as village health and nutrition days and others
- Formation of policies and regulations that limit marketing and promotion of unhealthy foods

4.5 Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Tanzania

Table 4.14: Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Tanzania

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<p>1. Specific</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve after delivery services provided in hospitals and health facilities to ensure larger proportional of women practicing early initiation of BF within 1 hour after delivery. - Improve the quality of ANC and RCH services provided especially nutrition counselling to mothers. - Promote exclusive breastfeeding - Promote feeding of colostrum to newborns - Discourage bottle-feeding - Ensure quality child growth monitoring - Create adequate quality nutrition awareness among people close to BF mothers to influence the provision of 	Dar and Moro (8)	< 6 months	Health care worker/stakeholders	<p>In Dar es Salaam there is a poor practice of BF initiation within one hour after birth to almost half of the population (51%) and EBF is merely practiced (9.1%) as reported in TDHS 2015/16.</p> <p>Similar problem was reported in Morogoro, 63.2% of new-borns were initiated to BF within 1 hour after birth, and only 12.4% of children were EBF</p> <p>FoodLAND consumer study reported 26.4% bottle fed children (rural Morogoro)</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<p>all necessary support allowing mothers to practice EBF adequately.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct outreach sessions in community level for nutrition counselling. This will sensitize the community to provide different forms of support to BF mothers in their respective communities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Should be done in peripherals especially in rural settings o Should also be done at work places especially in urban areas in order to reach working women 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote recommended IYCF practices through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Improved nutrition counselling quality provided to the mother/caregiver-child pair to create awareness about the recommended IYCF practices as well as the outcomes of non-adherence to their children. 	Dar and Moro (3)	6 to 59 months		<p>In Dar es Salaam only 16% of the mothers with children of aged 6 to 23 months practiced at least 3 IYCF recommended practices, while in Morogoro it was less practiced (5.2%), TDHS 2015/16.</p> <p>In Dar es Salaam 52.5% of children aged 6–23 months did not meet the minimum dietary diversity requirement, while in Morogoro it was</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conduct community-based nutrition counselling to promote adherence of the recommended IYCF practices ○ Provide RCH outreach services: This should be conducted not only to people living at the peripherals, but also at work places, such as in markets especially in urban settings. This will keep working mothers and caregiver updated about child nutrition issues. - Advocate for the following practices; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Continue BF up to 24 months ○ Timely introduction of CFs (after six months) ○ Ensure dietary diversification by provide a child with variety of foods from the 6 food groups (include eggs, at least three times per week) 	Dar and Moro (5)		Health care worker/stakeholders	<p>only 19.4% met the minimum dietary diversity requirement in the same region.</p> <p>In both regions only 4 out of 10 children met the required minimum meal frequency.</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensure safe and clean drinking water - Ensure height assessment during growth monitoring for all under 5 children; this would help early detection of stunting among children. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advocate for healthy eating and healthy lifestyle among adolescents and school aged children ○ Promote healthy food choices among school-aged children and adolescents ○ Ensure the availability of healthy diets and healthy snacks around school environment; ○ Promotion of the use of fortified and biofortified foods for adolescents in schools as well as at homes. ○ Strict monitoring to ensure all snacks sold around schools do not 	Dar and Moro (8)	Adolescents and school aged children	Schools/Stakeholders/Government/Community/Families	<p>A high overweight and obesity prevalence (13% and 3.2% respectively) among children 5 to 19 years was observed in Dar es Salaam than Morogoro (6.8% and 1.3%) (MoHCDGEC, 2021).</p> <p>In SMNS 2019 report, 65.9% of school aged children and adolescents in Dar es Salaam were reported to consume snacks at school almost everyday, the highest percentage compared to other regions in the country.</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> have NCD risk properties such as deep fried foods, sweetened beverages, energy drinks, etc. ○ Promote inclusion of healthy snacks such as fruits - Promote physical activities for weight management - Conduct routine nutrition assessment, such as monthly Haemoglobin (Hb) level check among adolescents - Nutrition interventions targeting adolescents should be developed and implemented for improved adolescent's nutrition 			<p>Schools/Stakeholders/Government/Community/Families</p> <p>Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create nutrition awareness among WRA: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provision of nutrition education should be incorporated in schools from primary schools, secondary schools and universities 	Dar and Moro (16)	Women of reproductive age (WRA) – Non-pregnant and non-lactating (15 to 49 years)	Nutritionists/Stakeholders/Government	<p>In TDHS 2015/16 Dar es Salaam was reported as a region with leading prevalence of overweight/obese (47%) among the WRA.</p> <p>In Morogoro, Stuetz <i>et al.</i>, 2019 reported overweight and obesity prevalence of (23.4% and</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nutrition education sessions should be introduced in work places ○ The counselling should also focus on advocate limited consumption of unhealthy foods that contribute to weight gain and pose NCD risks. ○ Should promote the consumption of NCD protective foods ○ Also, the population group should be made aware on the importance of using of IFA supplements when planning to conceive. ○ They should further be informed on the importance of daily supplementation even during pregnancy and after delivery. ○ Increased intake of fortified foods 			<p>Health care worker/Families</p> <p>Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p>	<p>10.2% respectively) higher than underweight prevalence (4.8%) among WRA.</p> <p>Anaemia is a public health concern, 53% and 47.3% were anaemic in Dar es Salaam and Morogoro</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conduct routine nutrition assessment, such as monthly Haemoglobin (Hb) level check among adolescents - Promote the use of diversified foods among women of reproductive age, including; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Daily consumption of fruits and vegetables ○ Improved consumption of wild fruits and vegetables e.g. <i>embe ng'ongo (ambarella)</i>, tamarind, baobab, java plum (<i>zambarau</i>), guava, lemon, jute ○ Increased consumption of iron-rich foods such as red meat, liver, beans, sesame seeds ○ Intake of iron absorption enhancers include vitamin C rich fruits e.g. passion, baobab, tamarind or oranges 				

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limit iron absorption inhibitors intake such as tea and coffee along with iron-rich foods ○ Increase vitamin C, A, B12 and B9 rich foods consumption ○ Limit intake of SSBs - Promote physical activities for weight management at community level such as in different institutions and companies. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote recommended nutrition practices and healthy lifestyle during practices and lactation including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improved promotion for diversified foods consumption from all six food groups ○ Advocate for more IFA supplements intake during pregnancy ○ Government should introduce MMS as an alternative for IFA during pregnancy 	Dar and Moro (14)	Pregnant and lactating women	Mother/Family/Community Health care worker/stakeholders Government	Pregnant anaemia prevalence in the country was 57%, higher than that of lactating mothers and women who neither breastfeed nor lactating (TDHS 2015/16) In Dar es Salaam, 84% of pregnant women took iron tablets or syrup at any time of their pregnancies. However, only 29% of pregnant women took iron tablets or syrup for more than 90 days during their pregnancy.

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Implementation research should be conducted to assess the compliance of multiple micronutrients supplement against IFA supplementation in different parts of Tanzania. ○ Emphasize the use of iron supplement 3 months postpartum ○ Improved promotion of iodized salt and other fortified products (such as maize flour, cooking oil and wheat) uses ○ Avoid alcohol intake and tobacco use ○ Avoid deep fried foods, sugar sweetened beverages (SSBs) and foods high in salt - Government should introduce a clear guideline for nutrition assessment of lactating women during each RCH visit. 			<p>Research institutions/ Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p> <p>Health care worker/stakeholders</p> <p>Mother/Family Mother/Family</p> <p>Government</p> <p>Health care workers</p> <p>Health care workers</p> <p>Health care workers</p>	

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure quality nutrition counselling is being provided to mothers - Ensure quality of other RCH services provided for both a child and the lactating mother. - Encourage pregnant women to deliver at the health facility hence ensure early initiation of BF - Promote immunization, deworming and malaria prophylaxis for pregnant women - Check for NCDs risks among women attending antenatal and postnatal clinics 			Health care workers	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrition interventions targeting improving men nutrition should be designed and implemented at country level - Routine nutrition assessment for men should be advocated in the country 	Dar and Moro (4)	Adult men	Government Individuals/Nutritionists/Stakeholders Health care worker/stakeholders	In Dar es Salaam, 50% of the subjects consumed at least 8 food groups; however, ASF specifically eggs and milk and milk products were less consumed. Fruits and vegetables were highly consumed, 89% and 92% respectively (Majili <i>et al.</i> , 2017). Low fruits consumption (26% and 21.4% respectively) among adults 18 years and above was

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality nutrition counselling especially to emphasize the increased consumption of animal protein and maintain fruits and vegetables consumption should be ensured - 				<p>reported in studies conducted by Kinabo <i>et al.</i>, 2016 and Minja <i>et al.</i>, 2021 in Morogoro.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasize in healthy eating especially urban residing elderly - Encourage them to do routine health and nutrition assessment - Government should introduce and close monitor waiver program on provision of health and nutrition related services among elderly individuals. - Nutrition assessment outreach programs should be designed and implemented - Conduction of more geriatric nutrition research across the country 	Dar (5)	Elderly	<p>Health care worker/stakeholders</p> <p>Health care worker/stakeholders</p> <p>Government</p> <p>Health care worker/stakeholders</p> <p>Research institutions/ Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p>	<p>Balegu, (2014) mean fruits and vegetable consumption of 2.61 ± 1.19 servings per day among elderlies aged 60 to 95 years in Dar es Salaam</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
to help proper nutrition intervention designs for elderly				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase home gardening practice for fruits and vegetables production in order to maintain daily fruits/vegetables consumption regardless number of children a woman has. - Promote small animal keeping to improve the availability of more diversified foods at household level - Promote establishment of fish ponds for more diversification of diet - Emphasize on the consumption of produced foods by the household in order to improve dietary diversification, especially the animal source foods whose consumption is affected by the level of income for food. - Create nutrition awareness within the community about the nutritive 	Dar and Moro (5)	General household	Individuals/Households/extension workers (agriculture – crops, and livestock and fisheries)	<p>Cereals have been reported as the most frequently consumed food group by households while animal source foods consumed the least, especially eggs Kinabo <i>et al.</i>, 2016</p> <p>Similar findings were reported by Minja <i>et al.</i>, 2021 whereby cereals was consumed by 99.7% of the households followed by oil and fats (98.9%).</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
value of foods, to enable an individual make an informed decision when considering types of foods to purchasing.			Nutritionists/Stakeholders/ Community health workers	
<p>Nutritional recommendations based on diet quality indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make effective use of multi-media to advocate for increased consumption of food groups which are protective from NCD and reduce the consumption of those with potential to pose NCD risks. - Promote the availability of NCD protective food groups around working areas - Promote the production and consumption of NCD protective food groups in household level; such as Whole grains, Pulses, Nuts and seeds, Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables, Dark green leafy vegetables, Other 	Dar and Moro (7)	Women of reproductive age and Children aged 6 to 23 months	<p>Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p> <p>Nutritionists/Stakeholders</p> <p>Individuals/Households</p>	<p>In Dar es Salaam, adult females average NCD protective foods was at the borderline of medium protection 5.02 (1.76) significantly low than that of men 5.73 (1.69) at $p<0.001$.</p> <p>No differences in food consumption pattern between women and children observed.</p>

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
vegetables, Vitamin A-rich fruits, Citrus, Other fruits - Practice proper food preparation and processing for targeted nutrients preservation - Formation of young mothers nutrition groups for nutrition counselling in order to improve their nutrition awareness including restriction consumption of food groups with NCD - Create awareness concerning NCD protect and risk food groups during street/village assemblies, such as village health and nutrition days and others - Formation of policies and regulations that limit marketing and promotion of unhealthy foods			Individuals Nutritionists/Stakeholders Nutritionists/Stakeholders Government	
Sub-total	75			
2. Sensitive				

Recommendations Recommendation genre	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extra curriculum activities especially in secondary schools that focuses on food production such as gardening and livestock keeping should be applied in schools in order to increase the consumption frequency of fruits, vegetables and animal proteins. - Provision of deworming medication 	Dar and Moro (2)	Adolescents and school aged children	<p>School administration</p> <p>Families</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make use of mass media; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Develop different jingles advocating for healthy eating and nutrition practices among WRA o Broadcast television and radio sessions to create nutrition awareness among the population and the community o Print out posters with nutrition information 	Dar and Moro (1)	ALL	Nutritionists/Stakeholders/ Government	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of bio-fortified foods to increase micronutrients intake 	Dar and Moro (4)	General household	Families	

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote production and consumption of biofortified and fortified foods - Provide support to keep small animals and home gardens - Use of family planning methods among women and men, in order to increase the potential of the parent(s) to provide their children with diversified diets. 			<p>Agricultural extension officers</p> <p>Families</p>	
Sub-total	7			
3. Facilitative				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government should create a system for a close monitoring of nutrition related services provided during ANC and RCH visits. 	Dar and Moro (1)	0 to 59 months Pregnant and lactating women	Government/	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasize the implementation of BF policy across all sectors in the country for improved exclusive breastfeeding rates. 	Dar and Moro (2)	6 to 59 months	Government/Private sectors/NGOs	

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work places to allocate the space for practicing BF 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Basic nutrition education should be provided in all schools, from primary to secondary and advocate for making informed decisions for better food choices. - Develop a guide to smart snack in schools, in order to limit unhealthy snacks consumption. - Make use of social networks and printed media such as posters and brochures to deliver nutrition related messages among adolescents and school-aged children 	Dar and Moro (3)	Adolescents and school aged children	Nutritionists/Stakeholders/ Government Nutritionists/Stakeholders/ Government Nutritionists/Stakeholders/ Government	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government should control the food price especially for fruits and animal source foods (ASF) to prevent excessive prices fluctuations that would affect the purchasing power of the population and hinder access to diverse foods 	Dar and Moro (2)	General household		

Recommendations	No recs/area where rec is applicable	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
- Make use of multi-media to deliver nutrition related messages to the community				
Sub-total	8			
Grand total	90			

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5 CHAPTER FIVE: REPORT ON NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TUNISIA

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5.1 Introduction

The current Tunisian diet has led to the proliferation of non-communicable diseases. A healthier diet is therefore required. Hence, an investigation of the Tunisian nutritional profile is needed.

This report aims to evaluate the Tunisian diet profile: to determine the nutritional gaps in both rural and urban areas and suggest nutritional recommendations helping to solve the issues raised.

5.2 Protocol for nutritional recommendations

The data presented in Table 5.1 was derived from a FoodLAND data set and targets adolescents, WRA, pregnant and lactating women, adult men and the population; segregated as urban and rural. It depicts country specific nutritional gaps that are then the subject of recommendations. Data that could show the proportion of population groups that met or did not meet RDA was not available. The data illuminates lack of dietary diversity as a widespread issue across these life cycle groups.

Table 5.1: Country specific gaps for nutritional recommendations for adolescents and adult

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Life cycle age groups	Food groups/Foods (%) Consumed all five recommended food groups	MDD-W Unmet (<5 food groups) %	GDR Score	NCD-PS Score	NCD-RS Score	Food needs Sum options 1 and 2 of the indicator in the FoodLAND studies (%) (HDDS)
Adolescent Boys urban	52.5%	-	9.7%	9.7%	9.7%	9.8%
Boys rural	-	-	-	-	-	-
Girls urban	52.5%	72.2%	9.7%	9.7%	9.7%	9.8%
Girls rural	69.9%	88.7%	23.2%	23.2%	23.2%	-
WRA (15 to 49 years)						
Urban	57.8%	87.6%	48.2%	48.2%	48.2%	50.1%
Rural	53.4%	79.8%	46.4%	46.4%	46.4%	-
Adult Men	55.1%	-				
Urban	55.1%	-	51.8%	51.8%	51.8%	49.9%
Pregnant women	-		-	-	-	-
Urban	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rural	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lactating women						
Rural	53.4%		46.4%	46.4%	46.4%	
Urban	-		-	-	-	-
Household			-	-	-	-
Urban	56.4%		-	-	-	-
Rural						

According to a FoodLAND data set that contains only data for rural children (Table 5.2) shows that just slightly over half of the children are put to the breast within the recommended time of one hour after birth.

Table 5.2: Country specific gaps for nutritional recommendations for children 0-6 months

Life cycle age groups	Nutrient requirement in RDA – Met or Not (at Population level – use means/medians) unmet % <i>Focus on neglected nutrients such as Iron, VitK2</i>	Low birth weight (Children born at <2500g) %	Timely initiation of breastfeeding (children who are breastfed within 1 hour of birth) %	EBF (Children who are exclusively breastfed for 6 months) %	Bottle feeding (Children who are fed using feeding bottles) %	Mixed feeding (Children who are both breastfed and fed on other foods/drinks) %	Formula Feeding (Children who are fed on formula milk) %
Urban Male Female	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rural Male Female	-	-	55.5%	30.1%	45.5%	-	-

We used our national documents because the FoodLAND database does not provide all the information required in the protocol. The data displayed in Table 5.3, implies that if not addressed, overweight and probably obesity are likely to become an elevated problem among the young (adolescents).

Table 5.3: Country specific gaps for nutritional recommendations for children aged 6-59 months and 6-15 years

	Underweight (2018)	Wasting (2018)	Stunting (2018)	Overweight (2018)	Anaemia (2018)	Iodine deficiency (2016)	Diabetes (2016)	Hypertension (2016)	Dyslipidemia (2016)
6-59 months	-	-	-	-	30%	-	-	-	-
under 5 years	1.5%	2.1%	8.3%	17.2%	7.4%	-	-	-	-
6-12 years	-	-	-	11%	8.2%	Less than 220 microgr/Liter	-	-	-
More than 15 years	-	-	-	59.9%	22.8%	-	15.5%	28.7%	40.9%

5.3 Situational Architecture

5.3.1 Desk Review

The significant political, socio-economic and lifestyle changes experienced in the country, has considerably influenced the diet patterns of Tunisians. For a long time, Tunisians thrived on a typical Mediterranean diet that has been modulated through introduction of the western type of diet that has altered food consumption patterns. Although the Mediterranean diet differs by region and country, generally, it is high in vegetables, fruits, legumes, nuts, beans, cereals, grains, fish and unsaturated fats such as olive oil and usually includes meat and dairy foods albeit at a low intake level. Westernised diets, that include fast foods, such as, pizza, hamburger and soft drinks and comprise more processed foods that are high in sugars, salt and fat. Noteworthy, food consumption transition in Tunisia is characterised by an elevated demand for meat and dairy products, a decline in cereal consumption and moderation in consumption of vegetables and fruits. In general, individual and household food consumption data show a trend of increasing food intake and westernisation of the diet especially in urban areas towards higher consumption of dairy and meat products, sugar, fat and salt. Even though the consumption of fruits and vegetables is increasing, it is still below the WHO recommended level.

The stunting levels in Tunisia are generally under 10%, on the other hand, obesity is becoming a big public health challenge. Over the last 20 years, the prevalence of obesity among women has tripled. The rates of overnutrition are higher among women than men (22.7% vs. 6.7%). Half of the women in Tunisia (50.9%) are either overweight or obese. Notably, the chances of being overweight increases with age and seems to take hold in adolescence especially among girls. In general, obesity is more prevalent in urban areas (19.4%) than in rural areas (13.4%). It is possible that an underlying cultural belief or practice promotes over-nutrition in women as they reach childbearing age. With the exception of iodine, which does not seem to be a problem for Tunisians, micronutrient deficiencies (iron, vitamin A and D) exist, albeit differentially, among age groups. With regard to deficiencies, the selected studies mention that diets fail to meet nutritional requirements for calcium, copper, iron, magnesium, potassium, vitamin D, B2 and vitamin E. Dietary intake of the above nutrients is below WHO recommendations.

5.3.2 FoodLAND findings

Study on rural Consumers: Rural consumer research: evidence from Fernana Food Hub, Tunisia

Introduction

Tunisia is the smallest North African country, with a population estimated at 11.7 million inhabitants (INS, 2021). More than 70% of the population lives in urban areas. Residents of Greater Tunis exceed 25% of the total population, most of which live all along the coastal zone in the east of the country. While the south and west are the areas with the lowest population density. According to the last national survey on budget, consumption and living standards conducted by the National Institute of statistics (INS, 2017), poverty rates regressed to 15% in 2015. However, due to the geographic development inequities, the poverty rate in rural areas is more than double compared to urban areas (26% versus 10%). Higher unemployment rates, lack of equitable distribution of wealth, gender inequality (mainly due to the unequal participation in the workforce) lead to the widening of the social, economic and health gaps between Tunisians. The covid-19 pandemic added to the economic and social difficulties presents a serious threat to food security in Tunisia. Strategic studies analysing the four pillars of food and nutrition security in Tunisia show that neither availability, nor use, nor stability represents a serious challenge for food security. However, physical, and financial access is increasingly difficult (ITES, 2017; FAO, 2016). A disparity in consumption is notable between the two sexes in Tunisia with women consuming less than men, and between regions with the urban population consuming more than the rural population (Saidi & Mekki, 2020). The north-west and central west are the two regions that consume the least. In Tunisia, eating habits seem to be more modernised in urban areas, in better-off households or in households where the mother has a higher level of education (El Rhazi et al., 2015). In this context the H2020 FoodLAND project was established to develop innovative technologies aiming at supporting the nutrition performance of local food systems in six Northern and Eastern African countries namely Morocco, Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, and Tunisia. FoodLAND's purpose is also to enhance biodiversity and food diversity, strengthen healthy diet diversity, and promote local food products. Tunisia, as one of the six countries under the FoodLAND project, has seen the emergence of food-related non-communicable diseases. Indeed, the current food diet has led to a high prevalence of obesity, overweight, and micronutrient deficiencies, especially anaemia and iron deficiency. This study on consumers' food behaviours and on dietary diversity and associated factors in Tunisia was carried out within the framework of the FoodLAND project. The

objectives of this research were to deepen the understanding of the behaviours in food consumption in rural areas, namely in the selected food hub of Fernana and to evaluate the economic access to food, and women's empowerment according to socioeconomic conditions.

Characteristics of the study area

Fernana is a delegation of the governorate of Jendouba which is located in the Northwest of Tunisia about 150 km from the capital, and covers an area of 393.5 km² (API, 2018). The north-west of Tunisia is the least anthropized region. Indeed, the north-west is mainly rural (Alouane et al., 2013) with an urbanisation rate of 27.9% in Jendouba.

Sociocultural and economic situation

Jendouba has 404 thousand inhabitants in 2019 with 3,144 new-borns (INS, 2021a) with a demographic density of around 130 inhabitants/km² (API, 2018). Jendouba has a negative population growth rate of -0.37% and a high poverty rate estimated at 21.5%(INS, 2020). It has 325 primary schools for 37,240 pupils, 52 secondary schools for 34,702 students and 4 universities (API, 2018). However the delegations with highest poverty rate namely Fernana (36.9%), Ghardiamou (27.2%), and Ain Drahem (24.8%) are characterised by the highest school drop-out rates with 3,8% in Fernana (INS, 2020). Jendouba has 673 Km of paved roads, a Railway linking Tunis to Ghardimaou, and an airport in Tabarka with around 300 thousands travels/year (API, 2018).

Nutritional status

Jendouba is located in the Northwest of Tunisia, and therefore follows similar characteristics as the whole area. Northwest of Tunisia is the region that consumes the most soft-wheat with 96,8Kg/person in 2015. Indeed around 53,3% of calories originate from cereals. It has also the highest oil consumption, mainly subsidised vegetable oils with about 14,6% of calorie consumption. It is the second region in the term of calorie consumption with 2,625 calories/person in 2015. It is also characterised by the lowest calcium (714) intake and a low iron consumption (17,2) (INS, 2015).

Education level and woman's role in the household

The age ranges between 19 and 45 (median 32) and 34% of them have at least two children. 38% of women have secondary education, and the illiteracy rate is higher among women over the age of 35 years old (31.8%). Only 9% of the surveyed women are household head and that the main forms of employment are distributed as follow:

- * 9% are farmers, almost 10% have non-farm household employment,
- * 13% are off-farm workers and
- * 70 % are homemakers.

The age of respondents, ranges between 23 and 45 (median 32) and 45% have at least three children. 79% of women have at least primary education, and the illiteracy rate is higher among women over the age of 35 years old (32.1%).

Sources of income of the household's head

According to the survey, there is significant variability between household incomes. In fact, the Average monthly household income varies between 0 and 1500 (TND) for farm income (ST.Dev=897.32), while it ranges between 0 and 4,000 (TND) for non-farm income (ST.Dev=876.33);

Study on urban consumers (Deliverable D2.3)

Introduction

The significant change in food systems has led to the emergence of new forms of malnutrition. Countries around the world suffer from stunting and wasting, while others suffer from overweight and obesity. This disparity is observed even in African countries as evidence of obesity is found in the northern part of Africa while the eastern part still suffers from wasting and stunting. Tunisia, as one of the six countries under the FoodLAND project, has seen the emergence of food-related non-communicable diseases. Indeed, the current food diet has led to a high prevalence of obesity, overweight, and micronutrient deficiencies, especially anaemia and iron deficiency. These burdens were essentially caused by the westernisation of the Tunisian diet. Indeed, Tunisia has seen its Mediterranean Adequacy Index (MAI) indicating the degree of adherence of a diet to the traditional Italian model of the Mediterranean diet, drop from 4.67 in the 1960s to 2.65 in the 2000s (Sahyoun & Sankavaram, 2016). This transition is mainly influenced by the Tunisian social policies based on the subsidy system which enhanced the consumption of staple food mainly imported namely wheat flour, vegetable oils, and sugar (Drogue et al., 2020). Indeed, the most consumed group is cereals which account for 46.9% of energy intake for urban areas and 54% of energy intake for rural ones (INS, 2015). However, the intake of cereals' is mainly in the form of refined soft wheat mostly due to the westernisation of the diet such as the introduction of pizza, hamburgers, pasta, and white bread. The combination of traditional food and western one has led to more complex culinary dishes involving the use of great amounts of fats and sugar and a less attention to vegetables (El Rhazi et al., 2015). Indeed, the Tunisian diet has become energy dense (Abassi et al., 2019). One of the main reasons behind the westernisation of the Tunisian diet is urbanisation. Westernised diet is more common in urban areas, in affluent households, and homes with highly educated mothers. On the other hand, the traditional diet is still common in the elderly population, low-income households, and rural areas (El Rhazi et al., 2015). The high demand for staple foods made the country dependent on imports subjecting it to the influence of global price fluctuations. This import dependency is explained not only by the consumers' behaviour, the population increase leading to the need of satisfying the food security but also by the low diversity of some crops in Tunisian agriculture caused by the non-suitability to the Tunisian climate (FAO, 2016). Climate changes have worsened the low diversity of crops as the ones dependent on rainfall are more cultivated than others. Which influenced even more the import and the consumer behaviour toward food. Indeed, the country is caught in a vicious circle between the need to ensure food security, healthy diet, and environmental impact. Which led to the need for the emergence of a more sustainable diet.

Characteristics of the study area

The survey targets 500 households living in Greater Tunis. The household members questioned ought to be responsible for food shopping within the family and over 18. The area of study is Greater Tunis including its four states namely Ben Arous, Ariana, Tunis, and Manouba. Greater Tunis is divided into 49 delegations distributed over the four states as 12 are in Ben Arous, 8 in Manouba, 7 in Ariana, and

21 in Tunis. Greater Tunis is bordered on the north by Bizert, on the south by the governorate of Zaghuan, on the east by Nabeul and the Mediterranean Sea, and on the west by the state of Beja.

Sociocultural and economic situation

Greater Tunis has the highest urbanisation rate with 100% at Tunis, 90,5% at Ben Arous, 74,3% at Manouba, and 88,8 % at Ariana with an electrification rate of 100% in urban the urban areas except for Manouba (99,7%) (API, 2018). It is the most prosperous region in Tunisia, where poverty rates at the governorate level do not exceed 15.2% (INS, 2020a).

Nutritional Status

Greater Tunis has a high obesity rate with the emergence of double burden, an iron deficiency, and a low calcium intake (Appendix A). Some studies also showed high iodine and sodium consumption originated essentially from bread consumption. As it is the region that consumes the most market white bread with 84,6Kg/person in 2015 (INS, 2015).

Education level and woman's role in the household

A total of 501 households questioned consisting of 1983 individuals. 152 households have 5 members or more which represents nearly 30% of the surveyed households. This could be explained by the constant decrease in marriage age of 28.6 for women and 33 for men in 2014 (INS, 2016) and the current social unacceptability for non-married members, especially women to be living alone. This is also shown by the 20 questioned persons that live alone as only 7 of them are women 2 of which are students waiting for the end of their study to return home, and 4 are widows over the age of 50. The result of our survey indicated that 89% of the surveyed households do not have kids under the age of two, 63% don't have kids between 2 and 14 years old, and 60% don't have any kids under the age of 14. Indeed, the 1983 individuals are composed of 1619 adults over the age of 14, 301 children between 3 and 13 years old, and 54 under the age of 3.

Sources of income of the household's head

6.5% of the surveyed households have an income lower than the minimum wage (365dt) while 9% have an income higher than 4000 dt. Most of the households (59%) lie in the interval 359dt, 2000dt with 147 households having an income between 356dt and 1000dt and 138 households earning between 1000dt and 2000dt per month. Indeed only 28% of the households willing to disclose their income, have a monthly income greater than 2000dt. However, these numbers don't represent the real financial situation of the Tunisian households as it is important to take into consideration the size of the households to be able to evaluate their financial situation. Indeed, a real assessment would be to take into consideration the income of the family per capita.

Head of the household form of employment

The head of household form of employment is theoretically important as it could influence the income, have an overview of the educational level, and therefore could influence the household consumer behaviour. As expected, the form of employment most frequently encountered in our survey is a regular worker. Indeed, 206 consumers responded to the question about the head of household form of employment by the regular worker (41.45%), followed by "other" 102 persons.

Among them, 95 consumers responded either retired or have a widow pension. This indicates that over 19% of the surveyed families have a household head over the age of retirement or is a widowed woman; slightly less than one out of ten, that is 9.66% of the surveyed households willing to answer have a head of household working as a casual worker while, 12.27% are sole traders, 6.44% are businessmen, 3.42% are clerks, 3.82% are managers, and 2.41% are unemployed.

Stakeholders engagement

Stakeholders' engagement and participation in generating nutritional recommendations was done on July 28th, 2023 during a workshop at the National Institute of Agronomy. "A workshop to restore and discuss the results of this survey was held on, at the National Institute of Agronomy (INAT), with the participation of national and regional public institutions, scientific researchers (INAT, ISACM, INRAT, INNNTA), international cooperation agencies (FAO, WFP, IFAD, AICS), the NGO CEFA, our partner in the project, and representatives of civil society, such as Culinary strolls and Dairy Club ».

Intended beneficiaries of the nutritional recommendations

Referring to the outputs of the meeting with stakeholders at the workshop, and taking guidance from the national strategy of nutritional recommendations, the intended beneficiaries of the nutritional recommendations are:

- Children
- Women in Reproductive Age (WRA)
- Rural consumers
- Urban consumers

Implementers of the proposed nutritional recommendations

The implementers of the proposed nutritional recommendations will be respectively:

- The Tunisian government (policy maker) through its institutional structures: health care centres, community health promoters, schools, etc.
- Civil society and volunteers
- Funders and financing organisations

5.4 Nutritional recommendations

The reservoir contains the probable recommendations, it is a combination of existing recommendations in form of ongoing interventions and novel recommendations.

Referring to the outputs of the meeting with stakeholders at the workshop held on July 28, 2023 at INAT, we present the recommendations in the shape of **four groups**, by taking guidance from the **national strategy** of nutritional recommendations.

1. Recommendations for children
2. Recommendations for Women in Reproductive Age (WRA)
3. Recommendations for urban consumers
4. Recommendations for rural consumers

5.4.1 Nutritional Recommendations for children

The nutritional recommendations presented in Table 5.4

Table 5.4: Nutritional recommendations by genre population groups and stakeholders responsible for action

Recommendations genre	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
1. Direct <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administer routine iron supplementation for low birth weight babies • Extended maternity leave (up to 6 months with paid salary for woman) to enable new-borns to benefit from breastfeeding • Give additional 2 months maternity leave for fathers of families • Educate on EBF for six months. • Practice continued breastfeeding (18-23 months) 	0-23 months	Health care centres Government and private-sector employers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversify the diet using the recommended 5 food groups • Nutrition education on proper food preparation that preserve nutrients, diverse diet, enrich porridge with recommended food groups • Increase consumption of fruits and vegetables in school cantina • Establishment of legislative and regulatory framework for advertising food products to children • Ban on plastic packaging snacks. • Renovating youth centres and introducing low-cost sports activities 	5-12 years	Caregivers/ school cantina/ household/ Government/ manufacturers
2. Sensitive <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing social and societal behaviour through the promotion of healthy eating habits • Inclusion of classes on healthy, balanced eating • Teach and encourage mothers on varied nutrient dense diet 	From 5 years old	school household Government Health care centres
3. Facilitative		

Recommendations genre	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop policies, regulations and legislate to support uptake and scaling up of the novel technologies. • Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND: cold storage, solar driers, bio-based packaging materials • Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND 		<p>Manufacturers/ Policy makers and regulators</p>

5.4.2 Recommendations for Women in Reproductive Age (WRA)

Table 5.5: Recommendations for Women in Reproductive Age (WRA)

Recommendations genre	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
<p>1. Direct</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups • Completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats • Implementation of the iron and folic acid supplementation in particular for pregnant and breastfeeding women 	WRA	<p>Government/ Health care centre/ household</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research- based recommendations • Conduct longitudinal studies at county level to establish iron/anaemia/overweight status • Conduct research on the consumption behaviour (quantities and quality of products consumed) • Conduct research on nutritional status and diet quality of women in rural area 	WRA	<p>Research institutions/ Government</p>
<p>2. Sensitive</p>		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revive/establish kitchen gardens (individual or households in groups). Establish means of generating their own income to reduce dependency on remittances Encourage increased consumption of animal-product foods Development of communication tools to raise awareness on a larger scale about consumption of product enriched with iron and folic acid 	WRA	Government/ Funders/ Civil Society/ Household
<p>Technology-based</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use novel food produced by FoodLAND technology innovation 	All Women	Farmers/ manufacturers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND: solar drier and bio-based packaging materials 	All Women	Manufacturers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND 	All Women	FoodLAND project through Media

5.4.3 Recommendations for urban consumers

Table 5.6: Recommendations for urban consumers

Recommendations genre	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
<p>2. Direct</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups Raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the five (5) designated food groups Adopt healthy habits by reducing the number of meals consumed in a day- helps in weight management, glycemia regulation and management of insulin resistance. Reduce consumption of carbohydrates and salts highly processed and salted meals Completely avoid consumption of saturated fats Intake of a diversified diet and encourage physical exercises Create intention to read food labels and to act appropriately 	All population	Government/ Health care centre/ household

Recommendations genre	Age/ populatio n groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All processed meals should have a clear label with health facts (protein, fats, sodium percentages) Review the government's subsidy strategy for flour and sugar in particular Ensure a traceability and control system for agricultural and agri-food products Setting up an access platform for organic agricultural products 		
<p>Research- based recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct longitudinal studies at county level to establish iron/anaemia/overweight status Conduct research on the consumption behaviour (quantities and quality of products consumed) with focus on the high consumption level of processed products. Conduct research on nutritional status and diet quality 	All populatio n	Research institutions/ Government
<p>2. Sensitive</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote urban farming (individual or households in groups). Raising awareness and promoting healthy eating Encourage production and consumption of organic fruits and vegetables 	All populatio n	Government/ Funders/ Civil Society/ Household
<p>Technology-based</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use novel food produced by FoodLAND technology innovation 		Farmers/ manufacturers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND: solar drier and bio-based packaging materials 		Manufacturers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND 		FoodLAND project through Media

5.4.4 Nutritional recommendations for rural consumers

Table 5.7: Nutritional recommendations for rural consumers

Recommendations genre

Recommendations genre	Age/ populatio n groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
<p>1. Direct</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups • To raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the five (5) designated food groups • Review the government's subsidy strategy for flour and sugar in particular • Ensure a traceability and control system for agricultural and agri-food products • Setting up an access to agricultural products from farmers to consumers: short/direct distribution channels • Increasing use of rainwater for irrigation and soilless cultivation • Establish kitchen and school gardens 	All populatio n	Government/ Health care centre/ household
<p>Research- based recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct longitudinal studies at county level to establish iron/anaemia/overweight status • Conduct research on the consumption behaviour (quantities and quality of products consumed) with focus on the deficiency and problem of access (physical and economic) to food. • Conduct research on nutritional status and diet quality 	All populatio n	Research institutions/ Government
<p>2. Sensitive</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting of kitchen and school gardens • Raising awareness and promoting healthy eating • Encourage increased production and consumption of organic fruits and vegetables • Promotion of agricultural and craft small-scale projects 	All populatio n	Government/ Funders/ Civil Society/ Household

Recommendations genre	Age/ populatio n groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR
Technology-based <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use novel food produced by FoodLAND technology innovation 		Farmers/ manufacturer s
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND; solar drier and bio-based packaging materials 		Manufacturer s
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND 		FoodLAND project through Media

5.4.5 Additional nutritional recommendations:

To avoid some nutritional gaps, here are a few recommendations:

- **Underweight:** Correction of the diet is required: consumers should eat at least five small meals and snacks each day/ Drink healthy beverages/Drink nutritional supplements/ Choose foods high in protein/ Add high-fat foods to meals and snacks
- **Stunting:** the first step is to make sure that stunted growth is not due to illness, but rather to malnutrition. The first thing to do is to make sure that stunted growth is not due to illness, but rather to malnutrition. In this case, we need to identify the probable causes (iron deficiency, vitamin deficiency, etc.) and provide appropriate treatment.
- **Overweight:** Over-feeding during infancy, childhood and adolescence predisposes to overweight. In addition, the tendency of familial obesity seems to be inherited. To avoid or limit this problem it is recommended to encourage regular physical activity/ Eat small meals regularly at frequent intervals/ Cut down sugar, salt, fatty foods, refined foods, soft drinks and alcohol/Eat complex carbohydrates, low glycemic foods and fibre rich diets/ Increase consumption of fruits and vegetables, legumes, whole grains and nuts/ Limit fat intake and shift from saturated to unsaturated fats.
- **Anaemia:** The treatment of Nutritional Iron deficiency anaemia involves taking iron supplements and changing the diet. Iron supplements could be given to babies in the form of a drinkable syrup, or in pill form for older children. Diets that include the following foods can

help treat or prevent iron deficiency: red meat, leafy vegetables, dried fruits, nuts, iron-fortified cereals...

- **Dyslipidemia, hypertension, and diabetes:** The tendency of familial problems seems to be inherited. Treatments can be divided into non-pharmacological (Non-pharmacological treatment includes medical nutrition therapy, weight loss, and physical activity) and pharmacological (statins...).

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6 CHAPTER SIX: REPORT NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UGANDA

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6.1 Introduction

Uganda, like many developing countries is faced with the triple burden of malnutrition including under-nutrition, micronutrient deficiencies and increasing levels of over-nutrition. According to the 2016 Uganda Demographic and Health Survey, 42% of the children below five years of age are underweight and 53% have anaemia. The significance of over-nutrition and associated non-communicable diseases in the country has also become apparent in recent years with the prevalence of obesity among women rising from 17% in 2006 to 24% in 2016. Between 2011 and 2016, the country implemented the Uganda Nutrition Action Plan I - UNAP I (GOU, 2011). Evaluation of changes in nutrition status in the country since the launch of UNAP I (OPM, 2020) and other studies (Ogenrwoth et al., 2022) have revealed a decline in prevalence of under-nutrition among children and women of reproductive age. However, the prevalence of overweight and obesity have been on rise, especially among adult women. Despite the rising levels of overweight and obesity in Uganda, most nutrition interventions in the country, including development of dietary guidelines, have targeted under-nutrition and nutritional deficiencies, with particular attention to children below 5 years and women of reproductive age. The country has, for a long time had, dietary guidelines for the feeding of infants, children, pregnant and breastfeeding mothers. Recent dietary guidelines (guidelines for maternal, infants, young children and adolescent nutrition - MIYCAN) also address the dietary guidelines for adolescents (MoH, 2021). However, save for the general guidelines in the context of COVID 19 (MOH, 2020), the country lacks dietary guidelines for adults (males and females that are neither pregnant nor breastfeeding) and the elderly. In light of the widespread food insecurity in the country, this population is also at risk of under-nutrition and micronutrient deficiencies.

In the cognizance of the aforementioned dietary problems and gaps in nutrition guidelines, the Food and local agricultural and nutritional diversity (FoodLAND) project team, in consultation with health and nutrition practitioners affiliated to government, academia and non-governmental organisations identified development of dietary guidelines for the adults and the elderly as a gap worthy addressing. Development of dietary guidelines for adults and the elderly is in line with the government of Uganda's aspirations. The guidelines would contribute to 5 of 11 primary outcomes specified in the Uganda Nutrition Action Plan 2020-2025 - UNAP II (OPM, 2020). The five primary outcomes include:

- 30% relative reduction in mean population intake of salt/sodium.
- 25% relative reduction in the prevalence of raised blood pressure.
- A 10% reduction in prevalence of insufficient physical activity.
- No increase in the prevalence of obesity.
- No increase in the prevalence of diabetes.

Dietary guidelines for adults and the elderly would also support strategy 1.5 of UNAP II, which seeks to integrate nutrition in the control, prevention and management of non-communicable diseases; and strategy 2.3, which highlights the development of food-based dietary guidelines as one of five proposed priority actions.

Objectives

The objectives of the nutritional guidelines development activities were to:

- I. Identify gaps that can be filled by availing nutritional guidelines
- II. Develop, in consultation with key stakeholders, nutritional guidelines based on current status of knowledge
- III. Disseminate developed nutritional guidelines

6.2 Protocol For Nutritional Recommendations

The process used to develop nutritional guidelines is briefly described below.

Identifying nutritional gaps

This entailed extensive desk review of published literature. The review resulted in 2 journal articles and key aspects emerging from the desk review are summarized in section 3 below. Identification of gaps in nutrition also entailed study of the FoodLAND food consumption survey report.

Engagement of stakeholders

Stakeholder engagement was done virtually through email communication and on-line meetings. Stakeholders consulted included staff of the Ministry of Health, Nutrition Unit, staff of Ministry of Agriculture, health staff of local governments, staff of non-governmental organisations, food processors, nutrition researchers and community representatives. Stakeholder consultations consisted of the following:

- Discussing the prevailing nutrition problems and available interventions in order to identify gaps to be addressed by the proposed nutrition guidelines
- Soliciting of suggestions to be included in the guidelines
- Dissemination of draft guidelines and soliciting of stakeholder inputs

Formulation of nutrition recommendations

Drafting of nutrition guidelines was done by the project team basing on suggestions from stakeholder consultations and recommendations from literature. Drafts were progressively revised based on inputs from stakeholders.

6.3 Situational architecture

6.3.1: Desk review findings

Desk review of literature on nutrition status in Uganda (Ogwenrwoth et al., 2023) revealed that the country is faced with high levels of undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies but is also experiencing a rise in overnutrition. The country is ranked 77th out of 95 countries in terms of undernutrition prevalence. Under-nutrition is closely linked to 40% of all mortalities among children below 5 years of age in the country. The review also revealed differences in prevalence of undernutrition between urban and rural areas and between regions. Stunting among children under 5 years of age

was higher in the rural areas (37%) than in the urban areas (34%). Wasting and underweight among the same age group were most rampant in northern region, with prevalence rates of 7.5% and 14.6%, respectively, while stunting was most prevalent in western region (33.2%). With respect to overnutrition, the review revealed an increase in the proportion of women aged 15-49 years who were overweight or obese from 17% in 2006 to 19% in 2011 and 24% in 2016 (Figure 6.1). On the other hand, prevalence of thinness among women aged 15-49 years declined from 12% in 2006 and 2011 to 9% in 2016. Among the different forms of micronutrient deficiencies, anaemia was reported to be highly prevalent, affecting 50% of children aged 6-59 months (2011 data) and 32% of women aged 15-49 years (2016 data). Vitamin A deficiency, goiter and folate deficiency (among women of reproductive age) were the other micronutrient deficiencies reported to be relatively widespread. One key observation from the review was the dearth of literature on nutrition for the elderly, adolescents and young adults.

Figure 6.1: Trends in the nutrition status of women aged 15-49 years in Uganda

Source: Ogwenrwoth et al. (2023)

Review of literature on dietary patterns in Uganda (Akumu et al., 2023) revealed that diets in Uganda were mainly composed of starchy staples, especially cereals, roots, tubers and bananas, with legumes constituting the main protein source (Figure 6.2). The review revealed low consumption of fruits and vegetables as well as animal protein sources. Assessment of household food consumption patterns and the share of food expenditure allocated to the different food groups showed that household consumption of (as a proportion of total food consumed) and expenditure on cereals and other starchy staples decreased with increasing wealth quantile and was lower among urban households. On the contrary, consumption of and expenditure on animal protein sources was higher among the higher income quantiles. The contribution of the different food groups to the total energy intake (Figure 6.2) Across the different studies reviewed, the mean dietary diversity score was above three (3). Nonetheless, intake of micronutrients and the mean dietary energy consumption were reported to be lower than the daily recommended values.

Figure 6.2: Contribution of different food items to the daily energy consumption

Source: Akumu et al. (2023). <https://doi.org/10.18697/ajfand.117.22345>

The review also revealed that micronutrient intake was largely through supplements, despite various interventions to promote consumption of biofortified and fortified foods, fruits, and vegetables. Some of the fortified foods include vitamin A fortified cooking oil, micronutrient fortified maize flour and wheat flour, table salt and fortified baby food. The biofortified foods include iron-rich beans and Vitamin A biofortified sweet potatoes. Children aged 6-59 months are supposed to receive vitamin A capsule supplements every six months and 62% received them. Pregnant women are provided iron and folic acid supplements to take during pregnancy. However, 12% of pregnant women did not take the supplements and their mean intake of vitamin A and zinc was lower than the recommended values. In a nationwide survey, rural children were less likely (38%) to have eaten iron-rich foods than urban children (47%), a difference attributed largely to disparities in access. Consumption of iodine should be from the iodized salt and luckily 99% of the households use iodized salt. Up to 85% of the oil in the market is fortified with vitamin A and fortified sugar, contribute significantly to meeting vitamin A requirements.

Regarding food choice and behaviour, the review revealed the drivers to include incomes, prices, household demographics, availability by production and production diversity, presence of outlets and other socio demographic factors. An increase in farm production diversity was reported to be associated with better household dietary diversity score (HDDS). Farm production diversity (FPD) was also positively and significantly associated with increased daily intake of energy, iron, zinc, and vitamin A by 0.3, 0.5, 0.4, and 1.4 points respectively. Several household socio-demographic factors, such as education level, household size, personal characteristics of the household head and income have been

found to influence food consumption patterns and dietary diversity. Increasing age of the household head has been associated with improved household food and nutrition security and diversity and children with caregivers between the age of 30 – 39 years have been reported to have 11% higher dietary diversity than those with caregivers aged below 20 years ($p < 0.05$). Very old age of the parents negatively impacts the food security and nutrition of the children. Price is a key determinant of food choices, consumption, and dietary patterns. A study in northern Uganda revealed that higher prices of foods disincentivized household consumption of milk and milk products, vitamin A-rich vegetables and fruits, and eggs. Persuasion through promotion and advertisement plays a role in shaping consumption patterns especially among the young population. Location plays a key role especially in determining access to food. Shorter distances not only improve access to buy food but also to sell food thus increasing income.

6.3.2 FoodLAND Findings

FoodLAND undertook a survey, covering parts of Kapeka and Kampala, to determine food consumer behavior. Gender and age. Females were the majority in the survey sample, constituting 67% while the male constituted 33% (Figure 6.3). The majority (60.4%) of the urban consumers were aged within the age-group 18-35 years (Figure 6.3). The age group with the highest population is 26-35 years (34%), followed by 18-25 years (26%), 36-45 (22%) and above 45 years (18%).

Figure 6.3: Proportion of in the consumers in the different age groups and gender by location

Education. Majority (83%) of the consumers had attended some education, from primary to secondary school level (Figure 6.4). The consumers with primary, secondary, and above secondary as the highest education levels were 30%, 31.9% and 21% respectively. There was a significant proportion (17%) of the consumers without any level of education.

Figure 6.4: Education level of the consumers

Income. The majority (94.2%) of the consumers were poor with the income level lying between lower to average. Most consumers (65%) have a somewhat lower income level, followed by lower income levels (17.9%), and about average income level (10.9%). The rest of the consumers (6%) had somewhat high-income levels (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5: Income levels of the urban consumers

6.3.3 Stakeholders engagement

Stakeholders engaged consisted mainly of implementers of the proposed recommendations. They included the following:

- Representatives of non-governmental organisations involved in nutrition
- Nutrition practitioners from central government (Ministry of Health and Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry and Fisheries)
- Representatives of local governments of target districts
- Representatives from farmer groups in target districts
- Nutrition researchers

The engagement was aimed at the following:

- Soliciting suggestions of aspects to be covered by the guidelines
- Obtaining specific recommendations to include in the guidelines
- Review of draft guidelines

6.4 Nutritional recommendations

6.4.1 Nutritional recommendations for adults and elderly

On the basis of the gap identified, guidelines were developed for **normal adults and the elderly**. The recommendations are summarised below.

Eat a variety of locally available foods from all the main food groups below:

- Fruits and vegetables
- Starchy staples: Cereals, roots, tubers and starchy fruits and vegetables
- Legumes and nuts
- Foods of animal origin
- Healthy oils and fats.

Eat a variety of fruits and vegetables a day. Eat at least five servings of fruits and vegetables (at least 400 g) daily. Fruits and vegetables like amaranths (*ddodo*), spinach (*nakatti*), eggplant (*bilinyanya* and *ntula*), cow pea leaves (*ggobe*), cabbage, avocado, mangoes, paw paws, jackfruit, banana, pineapples and watermelon should make up at least one third of one's total food intake in a day. Fruits and vegetables are good sources of vitamins, minerals, fibre and a variety of compounds (phytochemicals) that help to prevent diseases like cancers, diabetes and hypertension. The more the diversity of fruits and vegetables consumed the better. Eat 3 - 4 servings of fruits and 2 - 3 servings of vegetables daily. A serving may consist of a whole fruit for fruits like banana, mango or apples; a slice for fruits like pineapple and jackfruit; a cup of cooked leafy vegetables *dodo*, *nakatti* or *cabbage*. Use healthy oils to stir fry vegetables as this improves bioavailability of beta-carotene (vitamin A precursor).

To ensure availability of fruits and vegetables, do the following:

- Grow a variety of these crops
- Utilise appropriate technology like solar drying to preserve fruits and vegetables for off-season consumption.

Agriculture extension agents should support farming households to learn how to grow, preserve and utilise a variety of fruits and vegetables, including lesser known crops like grain amaranth.

Eat a variety of whole starchy staples like millet (*karo*), sorghum, unrefined maize (*posho* or porridge), sweet potatoes (unpeeled is better), cassava, yams, pumpkins and cooking bananas (*matooke*). Starchy staples supply energy and if whole, provide fibre, vitamins and minerals. Refined cereals like very white posho and white bread are low in nutrients and fibre and therefore inferior in nutritional value to the unrefined ones. Whole grain bread should therefore be chosen instead of white one. Starchy food should make up just over a third of the food we eat. Eat 3 - 6 servings of starchy staples daily. A serving consists approximately 120 g of starchy staple or 40 g (one slice) of bread and other baked products or chapati.

Food processors should adopt use of whole cereals in production of food products as food products made from unrefined foods contain more nutrients and health promoting components. Households should also adopt the incorporate locally grown nutrient rich foods like orange fleshed sweet potatoes and pumpkins in different recipes, including as substitutes for wheat in making snacks like *chapati*. Nutrition educators should educate farmers on recipes using locally available foods and on preservation of starchy staples that are highly perishable.

Farming households should grow a variety of starchy staples and apply appropriate storage and preservation techniques to ensure year round access of these foods in safe and wholesome forms. Grains can be stored in domestic silos or in triple bags. Foods like orange-fleshed sweet potatoes, white and yellow-fleshed sweet potatoes, cassava and yams can be dried and kept for future use.

Eat a variety of protein rich foods, including beans, peas, nuts, fish, eggs and poultry. These foods, in addition to supplying proteins provide the body with vitamins and minerals. The body requires proteins to replace tissue that wears off and to make important materials required for proper body functioning and health. Fish also supplies healthy lipids. Eat 2 - 3 servings (227 - 340 g) of different fish types, including *mukene* (silverfish) per week. Pulses like beans and cowpeas are also good sources of fibre and health promoting compounds (phytochemicals). Eat beans, peas, lentils, cow peas, pigeon peas, soya, nuts and edible seeds regularly (at least four times a week). Eat lean meat, fish and seafood, poultry, insects or eggs at least twice a week. Limit consumption of processed meat as it is associated with increased risk for cancer. Limit the consumption of red meat like beef and pork and full fat milk and other full fat dairy products. Consumption for foods in this category should be 2 to 3.5 servings per day for legumes, nuts, meat, fish, poultry and eggs and 2 - 3 servings for dairy products. Serving sizes are approximately 65 - 100 g of cooked meat (flesh) or poultry; 2 eggs; 100 g of fish; approximately 150 g of cooked pulses; 30 g of nuts and approximately 250 ml of milk (fresh or fermented milk).

Mukene and other fish species can be preserved by drying. To store well, dry protein rich foods including pulses, nuts and dry fish should be adequately dried, packaged in well sealed containers and kept away from vermin. Extension workers should train households on preservation of protein rich foods. Like *mukene*.

Include healthy fat or oils in your diet: Unsaturated spreads like peanut or sesame butter and unsaturated fats and oils used in food preparation do supply the body with energy as well as essential fatty acids and fat soluble vitamins. The unsaturated oils are highly susceptible to aerial oxidation thus should be properly stored in cool and covered containers. Intake of these should be 28-40 g per day for males under 70 years and 14-20 g for females and for males over 70 years.

Adjustments for high physical activity

The recommendations above are for people having moderate physical activity. Individuals with high to very high physical activity like athletes and those that do a lot of manual work should add 1-2.5 servings of each food category depending on the level of physical activity.

Limit consumption of foods rich in fat, sugar, salt and alcoholic beverages. These increase the risk for developing diseases such as hypertension. Limit consumption of fried foods such as chips and high energy foods such as ice cream, margarine, soda and sweet snacks. Whenever possible, consume boiled or steamed instead of fried foods. Healthy snacks such as nuts and dried fruits should be eaten instead of the high energy, high salt or high fat ones. When choosing fat/oil for use, opt for unsaturated fats/oils over saturated ones. Unsaturated fats are healthier fats and include vegetable, olive and sunflower oils. Whenever using oil, opt for fortified ones. Limit sugar consumption to less than 6 level teaspoons (25 g) per day. Limit salt consumption to less than 2.3 g (1 level teaspoonful per day). Only use iodised salt. Limit consumption of salted snacks and adding salt at table. Avoid alcohol consumption or limit consumption to no more than one drink (300 ml bottle of beer, 150 ml glass of wine or 40 ml tot of spirit) a day for females and no more than two drinks a day for males, on days when alcohol is consumed. Drinking less is better for health than drinking more.

Take plenty of fluids. Fluid requirements are 2.7 litres for women and 3.7 litres for men per day, taken in the form of water and beverages. Water helps hydrate the body enabling it to function properly.

Complementary non-dietary recommendations

Maintain healthy weight

Body weight can be monitored using the body mass index (BMI).

$$BMI = \frac{\text{Mass in kg}}{\text{Height (in metres) squared}}$$

BMI should be maintained between 18.5 and 24.9 Kgm⁻²

Physical exercise

Avoid sedentary lifestyle including sitting for long periods and using vehicles even for moving short distances. Use stairs instead of lifts wherever possible. Engage in moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity like brisk walking, digging, swimming, aerobics and cycling for 150 – 300 minutes or high intensity physical activity like running or playing football for at least 75 - 150 minutes a week .

Family members should encourage the elderly to engage in regular exercise that they are able to do.

Seeking of health care, including biannual medical examination

Seek treatment for illness from qualified medical professionals as soon as symptoms appear.

To ensure timely detection of ailments (including diabetes, hypertension, high plasma cholesterol and common cancers) and to facilitate appropriate treatment when required, it is advisable to take medical examination at intervals of no longer than 6 months. During these examinations tests for body mass index, blood pressure, blood sugar levels, plasma lipid profile, heart health and cancer markers will be undertaken.

Family members should support the elderly to access health care, including regular medical examinations as recommended.

6.5 Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Uganda

Table 6.1: Reservoir of nutritional recommendations for Uganda

Recommendations	No recs	Age/ population groups	Stakeholder responsible for implementing NR	Comments
Recommendation genre				
1. Direct	10	Adults and the elderly	Consumers	Applicable to rural and urban and to all education and income levels
Sub-total				

2. Sensitive	13	Adults and the elderly	Farmers SMEs Food preparers	Applicable to rural and urban and to all education and income levels
Sub-total				
3. Facilitative	7	Adults and the elderly	Family members, health workers and extension agents	Applicable to rural and urban and to all education and income levels

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7 CHAPTER SEVEN: REPORT NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ETHIOPIA

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7.1 Introduction

Ethiopia is one of the densely populated countries in Africa with an estimated population of 120 million, with a large proportion living in rural areas. The country faces significant challenges in health and nutrition, with malnutrition being a key concern, especially among children and mothers. Factors such as conflict, drought, desert locust infestations, COVID-19, and climate change have exacerbated the situation (1). Food and nutrition insecurity is a growing global issue, with the percentage of people affected rising from 7.5% in 2019 to 9.1% in 202. While it affects many countries, low-income nations like Ethiopia are disproportionately impacted. The 2024 Global Report on Food Crises highlights Ethiopia as one of the top ten countries affected, with 4.1 million children under five experiencing acute malnutrition (2, 3).

The humanitarian crisis in Northern Ethiopia, which began in November 2020, has heavily affected the Tigray region. Over 2.6 million people have been displaced, and vital services such as healthcare, livelihoods, and water, sanitation, and hygiene (WaSH) facilities have been destroyed, leaving millions unemployed, sick, and food insecure (4). Surveys show that over 84% of the population in Tigray is food insecure (5), 89% of health facilities are damaged (6), and only 3.9% of people have access to safe water (7). Pre-existing high levels of undernutrition in the region have worsened due to limited services, especially affecting vulnerable groups like pregnant and lactating women, adolescent girls, and children under five. The rate of wasting among children has surged from 9.2% to 17.6%, above the emergency threshold, and chronic malnutrition continues to be a significant public health issue with a prevalence rate of 48.1% (7, 8).

To further understating dietary practice among urban and rural communities, the FoodLAND project conducted a desk review on the nutrition status of different populations, primarily focusing on mothers, children and adolescent girls. Primary data collection was also carried out among urban and rural consumers in Laelay Maichew and Mekelle city, Tigray region

Ethiopia. Both the desk review and the primary surveys provided the team to clearly understand the dietary practices and the nutritional situation of the community in the study areas and the country at large.

7.2 Desk review findings

Methods: An initial desk review was conducted to assess the nutritional status of children under five, dietary diversity of pregnant mothers, and adolescents. It also aimed to explore the target community's food consumption behaviour and their inclinations towards healthy and diversified food consumption. The review included a thorough PubMed search for articles related to maternal, child, and adolescent nutritional status, separately. A similar search strategy was also used to investigate consumers' food consumption behaviour. Google Scholar was also utilized to find gray literature. Government policies, strategies, reports and unpublished works were considered in this review. A comprehensive list of search terms was used for each group, and search terms/symbols such as [tw] and * were employed to explore more articles. Finally search results were filtered to include studies published between 2011 and 2021.

7.2.1 Nutritional status of under- five children and associated factors in Ethiopia

Under nutrition is the leading cause of childhood morbidity and mortality in Ethiopia (9). The major forms of under nutrition identified are stunting, underweight and wasting. According to the Ethiopian Mini DHS 2019 report, 37% of under-five children are stunted with a higher prevalence in rural areas compared to urban areas. There is also significant regional variation, with the highest prevalence observed in Tigray (49%), and the lowest in Addis Ababa, (14%). Evidence on the trends of under nutrition reduction among children under five shows sluggish progress over the last ten years. The reduction in undernutrition from 2011 to 2019 was as follows: stunting decreased from 44% to 38% to 37%; underweight decreased from 29% to 24% to 21%; and wasting decreased from 10% to 7% (10). Another study on trends of underweight among under-five children between 2005 and 2019 by Haile Mekonnen Fenta, Lijalem Melie Tesfaw, and Muluwerk Ayele also report a decrease from 41% to 33% to 29% to 24 (11).

Nutrition during adolescence, the second window of hope to break intergeneration cycle of malnutrition, is critical time next to the first 1000 days for intervening in the prevention of child malnutrition. Stunting, wasting, and underweight are common forms of under-nutrition

in Ethiopia. A nationwide study from EDHS 2016 data reported a 15% prevalence rate of stunting in Ethiopia, with significant variations among regions (12, 13). Other small-scale studies assessing adolescents' nutritional status have been conducted in different parts of the country. Studies from the Amhara region have reported prevalence rates ranging between 15% and 16.3% for stunting, and 4.9% and 29.0% for thinness. Similar studies from Tigray have reported prevalence rates of stunting ranging from 12.2% to 33.3% (14, 15).

7.2.2 Dietary diversity of pregnant mothers in Ethiopia

Pregnancy demands extra nutrient intake as the unborn child's nutrient requirements are received from the mother. Inadequate nutrient intake during pregnancy leads to intrauterine growth retardation /restrictions that would lead to negative birth outcomes, including low birth weight (16-18). A report from a nationwide systematic review and Meta-analysis in 2021 showed that more than half (56.6%) of pregnant mothers had an inadequate dietary diversity score (<5). The study also found that about two-thirds of the mothers had poor dietary practices (19).

7.2.3 Dietary diversity among lactating women in Ethiopia

Childhood nutritional status is influenced both negatively and positively by the nutritional status of lactating mothers and their child feeding practices. Limited studies conducted in Ethiopia on lactating mothers' dietary diversity show that most lactating mothers do not fulfil the minimum dietary diversity score (20,21). A study conducted among lactating women from Southern Ethiopia reported that about 65% of lactating mothers did not fulfil the minimum dietary diversity score (65.2%) (22). Other studies from the Amhara region in Northern Ethiopia also reported that more than 50% of lactating mothers had low dietary diversity (23).

7.2.4 Consumers food choice/consumption behaviour in Ethiopia

Individual's dietary behaviours are influenced by many factors (24). Studies in Ethiopia have identified various factors affecting individuals' and families' food consumption behaviours, summarized as follows. While quantitative assessments of food choice or consumption are possible, qualitative exploration provides an in-depth understanding of the subject matter. Therefore, qualitative studies on food choice/ behaviour in Ethiopia have been considered in this review. Different studies have identified several factors affecting individuals' and families' food choice/ consumption behaviour, with the main ones summarized as follows: Food safety concerns: A study conducted to assess factors influencing the dietary behaviours of adolescents in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, reported that food safety was their main concern when choosing food. Available food was perceived as unhealthy and unsafe, promoting adolescents to seek

packed foods in their surroundings (25). A similar perception was reported in another study, where mothers were concerned about preparing of safe and healthy foods for their children (26). Religious influences: The roles of religious fasts in deciding which foods to eat and avoid, have been reported (27, 28). Participants in these studies indicated that all adults, including pregnant and lactating mothers, are expected to observe religious fasts which forbid the consumption of all forms of animal source foods (ASFs). For example , Orthodox followers abstain from ASFs and Muslim followers fast from sun rise to sun desk (29). Social norms and beliefs: Animal products are considered as luxury foods, prioritized during special occasions, and not typically consumed on daily basis (34). For instance, ASFs were identified by mothers as difficult to incorporate into a routine diet but were part of holiday meals (30). Food taboos and avoidance have also been reported to negatively affect the healthy and diversified food intake of pregnant women in Ethiopia (31). These studies indicate that the intake of fatty foods, including meat, milk, yoghurt (32), as well as intake of green leafy vegetables, yoghurt, cheese, and green paper (33), were considered as taboo during pregnancy and were avoided by pregnant mothers.

Accessibility and affordability: Diversified and healthy food intakes were reported as expensive by many studies (34). caregivers took responsibility which foods to prepare for the family. The types of food to prepare were predominantly determined by the affordability and accessibility Livestock ownership was reported as a facilitator of milk consumption by household family members (35). The unavailability of foods mainly, fruits and vegetables in nearby markets was also reported as a barrier to having healthy and diversified food by the local community (36). Low education status and lack of nutrition information: Education was reported as a main factor for the practice of healthy and diversified food intakes. Educated mothers and adolescents were reported to easily adapt to nutrition services (35). Moreover, people with limited nutrition information consumed less diversified food and sold nutritious foods to the market (36). Poor linkage between health and agriculture: Although health experts promote child dietary diversity through the consumption of ASFs, the agriculture sector mainly focused on increasing farmers' income by selling the agricultural products, including ASFs. It was reported that the low consumption of ASFs is fuelled by agricultural experts, who encourage farmers to produce a surplus and sell livestock and their products to save money in banks (36).

7.3 Findings of the FoodLAND urban and rural consumers' survey

7.3.1 Background and objectives

The urban and rural consumers surveys were conducted in Mekelle city and Laelay Maichew district of Central Tigray Zone, respectively.

The objectives of the survey were:

- To assess the dietary practices among the urban and rural communities
- To assess the dietary diversity among the urban and rural households
- To assess the dietary diversity among women in the study areas
- To assess the dietary practices among children 0-59 months among the rural consumers

7.3.2 Findings of the rural consumers' survey

Methods: The rural consumers' survey was conducted in Laelay Maichew, one of the FoodLAND food hub in Ethiopia. Data were collected from 561 households and the primary respondents being women of reproductive age (15-49 years old). Household with a child aged 0-59 months were randomly selected and invited for an interview. Face -to -face interviews were conducted using an interviewer-administered survey questionnaire with CAPI (Computer- Assisted Personal Interview). The survey questionnaire was developed by the research team, pretested and piloted before being administered to the respondents.

7.3.1.1 Socio demographic characteristics

The mean age of the participants was 32.81 years. Regarding their educational status, 40% had attended secondary school, 34.6% had attended primary school and 22.3% were illiterate. This indicates that a significant number of mothers were uneducated despite their young age. Maternal education status has been significantly associated with household and child dietary practices, with educated mothers having fewer undernourished children and better dietary practices. However, in the study area, the low dietary diversity among the mothers, households and children could be influenced by the mother's low educational status (35).

7.3.1.2 Dietary practice among women of reproductive age group in Laelay Maichew, Central zone, Tigray region, Ethiopia

The minimum dietary diversity among women of reproductive age group was far less than the minimum requirement, only 3.1% consumed five or more food groups during the survey period, indicating low nutrient intake that could lead to poor pregnancy and delivery outcomes (Tab.1). The most consumed foods in the last 24 hours before the survey were grains, roots/tubers and pulses. Almost all animal source foods and micronutrient rich diets were notably absent from the mothers' diet during the survey (Fig 1). Prior evidence has also shown

that inadequate consumptions of such foods predispose mothers to micronutrient deficiencies, including iron, iodine and folic acid. These deficiencies are responsible for major micronutrient related morbidities and mortalities, such as iron deficiency anaemia and goitre. Poor nutrient intake during pregnancy is also associated with abnormal pregnancies and congenital malformations. A 2021 study conducted in public hospitals in the Tigray region has reported that iron folic acid deficiencies resulted in congenital malformations, described as a “silent epidemic” causing thousands of abnormal births and preterm deliveries (36).

Table 1. Minimum dietary diversity among women of reproductive age group, rural consumer, Tigray Ethiopia, 2024

MDD women categoral		
Value/food gorups	Frequen cy	%
0-4 Groups	540	96.9
> 5 food groups	17	3.1

Fig 1. Women dietary practice & dietary diversity score, rural consumer, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

7.3.1.3 Household dietary diversity score and food consumption score

Based on the rural consumers’ survey, the household dietary diversity score (HDDS) and the food consumption score (FCS) were found to be far less than the minimum country recommendations. The tables below show that less than 10% of the households consumed six or more food groups (Tab. 2). Additionally, the survey revealed that over 85% of households had either poor or moderate food consumption scores, while only 13.1% had acceptable food consumption scores (Fig.2).

Table 2. Household dietary diversity score (HDDS), rural consumer, Tigray Ethiopia, 2024

Food groups	(%), N= 505
Two and less food groups (IPC 4 & 5)	8
Three to four food groups (IPC 3)	16.2
Five food groups (IPC 2)	65.2
Six or more food groups (IPC1)	9.3

Figure 2. Household food consumption score, rural consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

7.3.1.4 Infant and young child feeding (IYCF) practices

Breast feeding indicators

Early Initiation of breast feeding (EIBF): Among the 389 mothers with children aged 6-23 months surveyed for the IYCF practices, 294 (77.8%) reported that their children were put to the breast with in one hour of delivery.

Exclusive breast feeding for the first two days after delivery: While exclusive breast feeding is recommended for the first six months, 96.1% of mothers reported practicing of exclusive breastfeeding in the first two days after birth.

Ever breastfed: All surveyed mothers (100%) reported that their children ever breastfed.

Colostrum Discard: The practice of colostrum discard was report by 3% of the survey participants

Complementary feeding indicators:

All surveyed mothers reported that children aged 6-23 months were given complementary feeding while continuing to breastfeed. However, the mothers also indicated that animal source foods, fruits, and vegetables are rarely given to their children. The most frequently given food groups were grains, roots, tubers and plantains and pulses (beans, peas, and lentils), nuts and seeds. Further evidence (see Fig. 3 & 4) from regional and national child undernutrition and IYCF practices was generated to enrich the findings of the FoodLAND project.

Fig 3. Undernutrition trends in under five children (%)

Fig 4. Undernutrition trends in under five children (%)

7.3.1.5 Water, Hygiene and Sanitation situations among the surveyed households

The survey revealed that the water, hygiene, and sanitation practices among the study community are poor, with about 50% of the community practicing open defecation. This can increase the risk of diarrheal diseases and intestinal parasitic infestations, which are known risks for undernutrition, especially mainly among children (Fig 5- 7).

Fig 5. Household main source of drinking and cooking water, rural consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

Fig 6. Practice and types of toilet use rural consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024 (%)

Fig 7. Critical times for hand washing rural consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024 (%)

7.3.2 Findings of the urban consumers’ survey, Mekelle city, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

Methods: The urban consumers’ survey was conducted in Mekelle, the capital city of Tigray region, Ethiopia. Data were collected from 505 households through face- to -face interviews using an interviewer-administered survey questionnaire developed, pretested and piloted by the research team.

7.3.2.1 Educational background& household monthly income urban consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

In the survey, 505 participants were interviewed. Women account 38.0% of the participants. The mean age of the participants was 42.06 years (Tab. 3 &4).

Table 3. Surveyors' educational status urban consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

Educational status	Percent
No qualification, literate	4.8
Primary school	22.8
Secondary School	33.7
more than secondary	32.9
Illiterate	5.9

Table 4. Surveyors' household income urban consumers, Tigray, Ethiopia, 2024

Monthly income (ETB)	Frequency	%
400 and less	1	0.2
401-10000	403	79.8
1001-20000	69	13.7
20001-30000	20	4.0
40000 and above	12	2.4

7.3.2.2 Household dietary diversity score (HDDS) and food consumption score (FCS)

According to the survey findings, the household dietary diversity among the urban consumers was significantly below the minimum recommendation of six or more food groups. About 46% of the survey participants had HDDs of five or fewer food groups. Furthermore, 18% of the survey participants had poor to moderate FCS, while 82% had acceptable FCS. The most frequently missed food groups among the households were meat, egg and fish (Fig 8-10).

Fig.8 Household dietary diversity score (HDDS), urban consumers Ethiopia, 2024. %, N =565

Fig. 9. Urban consumers household food consumption score (FCS), Ethiopia, 2024

Fig 10. Household dietary diversity and feeding practices, urban consumers, Ethiopia 2024

7.4 Nutritional recommendation for urban and rural consumers

7.4.1 Nutritional recommendation for children 0-6 months

- In accordance with the national adolescent, maternal, young child and infant feeding practice (AMYCF), guideline, the following nutrition recommendation were generated
 - Put newborn into their mothers’ breast immediately after birth even before the placenta cut.
 - Feed every newborn the first milk colostrum
 - Give only breast milk for the first six months of life
 - Feed newborn as frequent as possible; give breast every two hours whenever possible
 - Encourage mothers/caregivers for hygienic breast-feeding practice including hand washing practice during the critical times before breast feeding
 - Design culturally appropriate Nutrition education to mothers

7.4.2 Nutrition recommendations for children 6-23 months

According to the WHO 2023 complementary feeding guideline: -

- Initiate complementary food at six months (181 days)

- Provide nutrient dense diversified complementary foods
- Provide safe complementary foods
- Prepare hygienic complementary foods
- Provide vitamin A supplementations every six months
- Provide anti-helminthic: deworm children with Albendazole/Mebendazole twice a year to prevent parasitic infestation
- Enrich complementary food with animal source foods and multiple micronutrient supplements/powders
- Food fortification should target staple food

7.4.3 Nutrition recommendation for mothers of reproductive age group

- Enrich maternal diet with ASFs
- Provide multiple micronutrient supplementation to all pregnant mothers to prevent micronutrient deficiencies and related congenital malformations
- Provide/encourage one extra meal for pregnant mothers and two extra meals for lactating mothers
- Encourage/ counsel mothers to delay pregnancy among births to build mothers' micronutrient storage for upcoming pregnancy

7.4.4 Nutrition recommendations for adolescent girls

- Enrich adolescent girls' diet with nutrient dense menu
- Supplement adolescent girls with weekly iron folic acid (WIFA)
- Improve adolescent girls' school environment with healthy food cafeterias and food environments
- Deworm adolescent girls with Albendazole/Mebendazole to prevent infestation
- Delay pregnancy among adolescent girls to build micronutrient storage
- Improve school environment with clean and safe water supply and hand washing practices

7.4.5 Nutrition recommendations for the urban and rural community

In addressing malnutrition in Ethiopia, we recommend the holistic approach that demands the involvement of different actors/ stakeholders that should be fully implemented and monitored by the GoE and policy makers.

- Involvement of different sectors in the nutrition prevention including the health, education, the water, the social protection and the agriculture for holistically address malnutrition
- Impose mass food fortification for all food producers in Ethiopia
- Engage scholars to innovate nutrient dense foods from locally available foods like the Teff-Moringa blended flour
- Scale up the production of the “Teff- Moringa” blended flour across the country and beyond
- Engage local communities in the design and implementation of nutrition programs to ensure they meet the real needs of the population. Empower local leaders to become nutrition champions.

- Build local capacity to sustain nutrition programs including train health workers, and community leaders to continue educating and counselling the community including malpractice during child feeding practice
- Safe drinking water is essential for maintaining good nutrition therefore improving access to safe and clean water supply and promoting hygiene to prevent waterborne diseases would play big role.
- Introduce home garden even among the urban community to enhance food diversification
- Transforming the plantation of non-fruit trees to fruit-trees to increase access to fruits and diversify community diet
- Consider livelihood enhancing interventions among households including poultry production to improve access and affordability to ASFs among the different community groups.
- Ensure girls education as education is directly associated with good child feeding practice

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APPENDIX 1: An Additional Reservoir of Nutritional Recommendations

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
0 - < 6 months	Administer routine daily iron supplementation to children < 6 months (1Mg/Kg of child's body weight per day)		Improve after delivery services provided in hospitals and health facilities to ensure larger proportional of women practising early initiation of breastfeeding (BF) within 1 hour after delivery.	Administer routine iron supplementation for low birth weight babies	N/A
	Adopt Innovative ways of elevating and protecting exclusive breastfeeding		Improve the quality of Antenatal Care (ANC) and Reproductive Child Health (RCH) services provided especially nutrition counselling to mothers.	Extended maternity leave (up to 6 months with paid salary for woman) to enable new-borns to benefit from breastfeeding	
	Address re-emergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)		Promote exclusive breastfeeding	Give additional 2 months maternity leave for fathers of families	
			Promote feeding of colostrum to newborns	Educate on exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) for six months.	
			Discourage bottle-feeding		
			Ensure quality child growth monitoring		
			Create adequate quality nutrition awareness among people close to BF		

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			mothers to influence the provision of all necessary support allowing mothers to practise EBF adequately.		
6 – 23 months	Improving diet quality of children by diversifying the diet to ensure inclusion of the per day recommended eight (8) food groups to meet the minimum target of five out of eight for breastfeeding and four out of seven for non-breastfeeding children.		Promote recommended infant and young child feeding (IYCF) practices through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improved nutrition counselling quality provided to the mother/caregiver-child pair to create awareness about the recommended IYCF practices as well as the outcomes of non-adherence to their children. ○ Conduct community based nutrition counselling to promote adherence of the recommended IYCF practices ○ Provide RCH outreach services: This should be conducted not only to people living at the peripherals, but also at work places, such as in markets especially in urban settings. This will keep working mothers 	Practice continued breastfeeding up-to 23 months	N/A

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			and caregiver updated about child nutrition issues.		
	Implement actions towards reducing malnutrition (stunting, underweight, wasting, overweight, and obesity)		Advocate for the following practices; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Continue BF up to 24 months ○ Timely introduction of complementary feeds (CFs) after six months ○ Ensure dietary diversification by provide a child with variety of foods from the 6 food groups (include eggs, at least three times per week) ○ Ensure safe and clean drinking water 		
	Administer routine iron supplementation to children		Ensure height assessment during growth monitoring for all under 5 children; this would help early detection of stunting among children.		
	Address re-emergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)				
2 - < 5 years	Improve diet quality of children by diversifying the		Promote recommended IYCF practices through:		N/A

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
	<p>diet to ensure inclusion of the per day recommended seven (7) food groups to meet the minimum target of four out of seven.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improved nutrition counselling quality provided to the mother/caregiver-child pair to create awareness about the recommended IYCF practices as well as the outcomes of non-adherence to their children. ○ Conduct community based nutrition counselling to promote adherence of the recommended IYCF practices ○ Provide RCH outreach services: This should be conducted not only to people living at the peripherals, but also at work places, such as in markets especially in urban settings. This will keep working mothers and caregiver updated about child nutrition issues. 		
	<p>Implement actions towards reducing malnutrition (stunting, underweight,</p>		<p>Advocate for the following practices;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Timely introduction of complementary foods (after six months) 		

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
	wasting, overweight, and obesity)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensure dietary diversification by provide a child with variety of foods from the 6 food groups (include eggs, at least three times per week) ○ Ensure safe and clean drinking water 		
	Mitigate uptake of poor dietary habits		Ensure height assessment during growth monitoring for all under 5 children; this would help early detection of stunting among children.		
	Administer routine iron supplementation to children				
	Address reemergence of rickets (vitamin D deficiency)				
10 – 19 years (Adolescents)	Adopt diet diversification to improve diet quality		Advocate for healthy eating and healthy lifestyle among adolescents and school aged children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Promote healthy food choices among school-aged children and adolescents 	Changing social and societal behaviour through the promotion of healthy eating habits	N/A
	Adopt healthy snacking behaviour			Inclusion of classes on healthy, balanced eating	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensure the availability of healthy diets and healthy snacks around school environment; ○ Promotion of the use of fortified and biofortified foods for adolescents in schools as well as at homes. ○ Strict monitoring to ensure all snacks sold around schools do not have NCD risk properties such as deep fried foods, sweetened beverages, energy drinks, etc. ○ Promote inclusion of healthy snacks such as fruits 		
	Curb iron and other micronutrient deficiencies			Teach and encourage mothers on varied nutrient dense diet	
	Drink the recommended quantities of water; 6 – 8 glasses (240 ml) per day			Develop policies, regulations and legislate to support uptake and scaling up of the novel technologies.	
	Reduce and prevent overweight and obesity			Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND: cold storage, solar driers, bio-based packaging materials	
				Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND	
			- Promote physical activities for weight management		
			- Conduct routine nutrition assessment, such as monthly Haemoglobin (Hb) level check among adolescents		

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			- Nutrition interventions targeting adolescents should be developed and implemented for improved adolescent's nutrition		
Women of reproductive age, Pregnant women, Lactating women, Teenage mothers	Improve diet quality by diversifying the diet using at least the 10 recommended food groups to achieve a minimum of five food groups a day		Among women of reproductive age (WRA): Nutrition counselling should be done from secondary schools, universities to work places emphasizing on consumption of iron rich foods along with iron absorption enhancers, as well as the consumption of foods rich in vitamin C, A, B12 and B9.	Alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups	N/A
	Reduce and prevent iron and calcium deficiencies		The population group should be made aware on the importance of using of Iron and folic acid (IFA) supplements when planning to conceive.	Completely avoid consumption of soft drinks and saturated fats	
	Develop a better nutritional environment for teenage mothers		They should be informed on the importance of daily supplementation during pregnancy, and after delivery	Implementation of the iron and folic acid supplementation in particular for pregnant and breastfeeding women	
			Promote the use of diversified foods among women of reproductive age	Research-based recommendations	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			Promote physical activities for weight management, at community level such as in different institutions and companies.	Conduct longitudinal studies at county level to establish iron/anemia/overweight status	
			Develop different jingles advocating for healthy eating and nutrition practices among WRA	Conduct research on the consumption behaviour (quantities and quality of products consumed)	
			Broadcast television and radio sessions to create nutrition awareness among the population and the community	Conduct research on nutritional status and diet quality of women in rural area	
			Include fruits and vegetables in daily meals	Revive/establish kitchen gardens (individual or households in groups).	
			Limit intake of sugar sweetened beverages (SSBs)	Establish means of generating their own income to reduce dependency on remittances	
				Encourage increased consumption of animal-product foods	
				Development of communication tools to raise awareness on a largerscale about consumption of product enriched with iron and folic acid	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
				Use novel food produced by FoodLAND technology innovation	
				Engage in transfer and multiplication of novel technologies developed by FoodLAND: solar drier and bio-based packaging materials	
				Social market and promote adoption of the novel technologies developed by FoodLAND	
			Among pregnant and lactating women: Avoid deep fried foods, sugar sweetened beverages (SSBs) and foods high in salt		
			Take IFAS supplements		
			Eat diversified foods from all six food groups		
			Used iodized salt		
			Avoid alcohol intake and tobacco use		
			Eat diversified food		

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			Promote recommended nutrition practices during practices and lactation:		
			Close monitoring of RCH services should be conducted for both a child and the lactating mother.		
			Quality nutrition counselling should be provided to the mother; Nutrition counselling should also advocate for daily intake of iron containing supplements and provide thorough explanation on its role towards pregnancy outcomes.		
			Nutrition assessment of lactating women; the nutrition status of lactating women should be monitored during RCH visits.		
			Implementation research should be conducted to assess the compliance of multiple micronutrients supplement, against IFA supplementation.		
			Emphasize the implementation of BF policy across all sectors in the country for improved exclusive breastfeeding rates.		

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
			Emphasize the use of iron supplement 3 months postpartum		
Adult men	Improve diet quality through diet diversification using the recommended 10 food groups		Nutrition interventions targeting improving men nutrition should be designed and implemented at country level	N/A	Eat a variety of locally available foods from all the main food groups
	Limit/eliminate consumption of foods and substances that are hazardous to health		Routine nutrition assessment for men should be advocated in the country		Eat variety of fruits and vegetables a day
	Offer transformational nutrition education on importance of nutritious healthy eating		Quality nutrition counselling especially to emphasize the increased consumption of animal protein and maintain fruits and vegetables consumption should be ensured		Eat a variety of whole starchy staples
	Improve level of physical activity				Eat a variety of protein rich foods, including beans, peas, nuts, fish, eggs and poultry

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
	Adult men to ensure that they get health facility based regular nutritional and medical check-ups (a must- blood glucose, blood pressure, prostate)				Include healthy fat or oils in the diet
					Limit consumption of foods rich in fat, sugar, salt and alcoholic beverages
					Take plenty of fluids.
Elderly persons	Improve diet quality through food diversification		Emphasize in healthy eating especially urban residing elderly	N/A	Eat a variety of locally available foods from all the main food groups
	Improve nutritional and health status of the elderly		Encourage them to do routine health and nutrition assessment		Eat variety of fruits and vegetables a day

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
	Conduct research for evidence-based action for the elderly		Government should introduce and close monitor waiver program on provision of health and nutrition related services among elderly individuals.		Eat a variety of whole starchy staples
			Nutrition assessment outreach programs should be designed and implemented		Eat a variety of protein rich foods, including beans, peas, nuts, fish, eggs and poultry
			Conduction of more geriatric nutrition research across the country to help proper nutrition intervention designs for elderly		Include healthy fat or oils in the diet
					Limit consumption of foods rich in fat, sugar, salt and alcoholic beverages
					Take plenty of fluids.

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
General household	(For both rural and urban households :) Improve household diet quality by adopting better diet diversification		(For both rural and urban households :) Increase home gardening practice for fruits and vegetables production in order to maintain daily fruits/vegetables consumption regardless number of children a woman has.	(For urban households :) Alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups	N/A
	Increase consumption of nuts and seeds across age groups among households		Promote small animal keeping to improve the availability of more diversified foods at household level	Raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the five (5) designated food groups	
	Diversify the diet using the recommended eight food groups		Promote establishment of fish ponds for more diversification of diet	Adopt healthy habits by reducing the number of meals consumed in a day- helps in weight management, glycemia regulation and management of insulin resistance.	
	Reduce overweight and obesity rates		Emphasize on the consumption of produced foods by the household in order to improve dietary diversification, especially the animal source foods whose consumption is affected by the level of income for food.	Reduce consumption of carbohydrates and salts highly processed and salted meals	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
	innovate means of generating their own income to reduce dependency on remittances		Create nutrition awareness within the community about the nutritive value of foods, to enable an individual make an informed decision when considering types of foods to purchasing.	Setting up an access platform for organic agricultural products	
				Ensure a traceability and control system for agricultural and agri-food products	
				Review the government's subsidy strategy for flour and sugar in particular	
				All processed meals should have a clear label with health facts (protein, fats, sodium percentages)	
				Create intention to read food labels and to act appropriately	
				Completely avoid consumption of saturated fats	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
				Intake of a diversified diet and encourage physical exercises	
				Promoting of urban farming (individual or households in groups).	
				Raising awareness and promoting healthy eating	
				Encourage production and consumption of organic fruits and vegetables	
				(For rural households :) To alert them of their border-line status and the need to raise their consumption to the 5 recommended food groups	
				To raise their consumption by at least three (3) of the five (5) designated food groups	
				Review the government's subsidy strategy for flour and sugar in particular	
				Ensure a traceability and control system for agricultural and agri-food products	

Age and physiological group	Kenya	Morocco	Tanzania	Tunisia	Uganda
				agricultural products from farmers to consumers: short/direct distribution channels	
				Increasing use of rainwater for irrigation and soilless cultivation	
				Establish kitchen and school gardens	